

D1.1 Homomorphic Encryption, Functional Encryption and Function Hiding

Federated Data Sharing and Analysis for Social Utility

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3 Status, Change History and Glossary

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Table 1 – Status Change History

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Version	Date	Pages	Author	Modification
0.1	20.03.2024	12	TUNI	Template Made
0.2	29.03.2024	37	TUNI	Added Functional Encryption and Homomorphic Encryption Background
0.3	08.04.2024	77	TUNI	Added Functional Encryption Constructions
0.4	17.04.2024	109	TUNI	Added HHE Background
0.5	22.04.2024	118	TUNI	Added GuardML Sections
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Table 2 – Deliverable Change History

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

HE	Homomorphic Encryption
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
PHE	Partially Homomorphic Encryption
SHE	Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption
HHE	Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption
FE	Functional Encryption
MIFE	Multi-Input Functional Encryption
IPFE	Inner-Product Functional Encryption
pk	Public Key
sk	Secret Key
evk	Evaluation Key
dk	Decryption Key
mpk	Master Public Key
msk	Master Secret Key
ADV	Adversary
IND-CPA	Indistinguishability under Chosen Plaintext Attack
IND-CCA	Indistinguishability under Chosen Ciphertext Attack
EUF-CMA	Existential Unforgeability under Chosen Message Attack
ADV	Adversary
ECC	Elliptic Curve Cryptography
PKE	Public Key Encryption
SKE	Symmetric Key Encryption
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
ACH	Additive Ciphertext Homomorphism
AKH	Additive Key Homomorphism
ED	Edge Devices
(D)O	(Data) Owner
SS	Storage Server

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(D)A	(Data) Analyst
KC	Key Curator
U	Users
PPT	Probabilistic Polynomial Time
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment

Table 3 – List of abbreviations and acronyms

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Executive Summary

The HARPOCRATES project aims to develop solutions for private and secure data analysis and sharing. As such, this deliverable (D1.1 Homomorphic Encryption, Functional Encryption and Function Hiding) covers the cryptographic solutions developed to aid operating on encrypted data as if it was unencrypted. As such, this document covers the development of Functional Encryption (FE) as well as Homomorphic Encryption (HE) and Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption (HHE) solutions, which can be used for secure data analysis and improving the privacy of users as well as keeping proprietary models and protocols secure. Throughout this document, we cover the preliminaries of constructing both FE, HE and HHE based solutions and provide three FE constructions as well as an HHE construction for different usecases. The contents of this deliverable can be summarised as such:

- In accordance to the Symmetric and Asymmetric Functional Encryption with Function Hiding task, we analyse the constructions of FE schemes and implement two FE constructions, *Need for Speed* and *SPADE*, which can be used for efficient data aggregation and data analysis without revealing the original data.
- To protect proprietary software as well as provide privacy on *how* users analyse their data, we constructed a generic FE framework that can be appended to any message-private, multi-input FE scheme and transform it to a function hiding FE scheme. By doing this, an analyst can still use an FE to analyze encrypted data in privacy-preserving way but apart from keeping the data private we also hide the functions applied to the data – thus keeping the confidentiality and privacy of both the data and the utilized statistical functions.
- Following the Efficient Homomorphic Encryption Schemes task, we analyse the advantages and limitations of HE and HHE schemes by evaluating the efficiency of HHE when compared to standard HE. Additionally, we analyse the security of these schemes and show their robustness against malicious adversaries.
- We build upon HHE schemes and expand them to a new use case for Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning (PPML). This results in GuardML, a realistic solution that allows to run secure machine learning on encrypted data for a variety of users and devices.

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4 Introduction

One of the significant leaps in cryptography in the last decade was the switch from traditional encryption schemes to schemes treating encrypted data as plaintext. Although its practical applications are still lagging behind, throughout the HARPOCRATES project, we attempt to encourage and enable this transition and provide practical solutions for various industrial sectors such as healthcare and others. To achieve this, we have committed to analyzing and researching privacy-preserving techniques such as Functional Encryption (FE) and Homomorphic Encryption (HE) to achieve the goal of practical and secure protocols for real-life applications.

4.1 Functional Encryption

FE is a cryptographic scheme that allows **selective computations over encrypted data**. FE schemes use a key generation algorithm that outputs decryption keys with remarkable capabilities. More precisely, each functional decryption key dk_f is associated with a function f . In contrast to traditional cryptographic techniques, using dk_f on a ciphertext $Enc(x)$ does *not* recover x but a function $f(x)$ – thus keeping the actual value x private. While the first constructions of FE allowed the computation of a function over a *single* ciphertext, more recent works [4, 5] introduced a more general notion of multi-input FE (MIFE). Additionally, in this deliverable, **we provide two constructions for using MIFE to solve different use-cases**. In a MIFE scheme, a ciphertext is a vector $(Enc(pk_1, x_1), \dots, Enc(pk_n, x_n))$ that encrypts each entry of a message $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ with different keys pk_1, \dots, pk_n . This set of n keys is also called master public key. Subsequently, a user can use dk_f to recover $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$. The function f can allow only highly processed forms of data to be learned by the functional key holder. Unfortunately, while MIFE seems to be a perfect fit for many real-life applications – especially cloud-based ones where multiple users store large volumes of data in remote and possibly corrupted entities – most of the works in the field revolve around constructing *generic* schemes that support only a narrowed class of functions, as inner product functional encryption (IPFE) [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13] for example, that only supports the inner product functionalities. We, however, believe that in the near future, we will start seeing more nuance in the functions supported by FE schemes.

Having identified the importance of FE and believing that only a family of modern encryption schemes could thread the way through this as yet uncharted technological territory, we started looking into new and unexplored problems that may arise from their use. As the research on FE evolved, we realized that developing FE schemes themselves is only *a part of the challenge* – possibly, not even the hardest part. At first, we focused on the important, till now overlooked, problem of **function-privacy (or function-hiding)**. That is, how to make sure that the cloud

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service provider (CSP) who is performing a functional decryption will output the correct result without learning anything about the computed function. Moving forward, another important challenge, entirely absent from the literature, came into view. Namely, how to classify ciphertexts with regard to the functions that can be applied to them. In the standard FE model, the function is applied to the entirety of the users' data. However, this may be extremely problematic in many cases, as the function may not be defined over some of the data.

FE schemes can be either symmetric [14] or asymmetric [15]. The problem of function privacy needs to be treated differently for each setting.

Function-privacy in the public-key setting and the private-key setting are two notions that, unfortunately, differ dramatically. The difference derives from the fact that in a public-key FE scheme, given a functional decryption key dk_f for a function f , a malicious user can use the public key to encrypt any message x of her choice and then evaluate $f(x)$. In other words, it is possible to evaluate the function f on infinitely many points – a process that reveals non-trivial information about f . However, in the private-key setting where the private key is hidden, this attack cannot work as the malicious user lacks the ability to encrypt messages. Hence, it is possible to formulate a level of security in which nothing else beyond $f(x)$ is leaked.

Function Privacy in the private-key setting was formalized in [16], where authors proposed a method to hide the description of the function from the evaluator. Since then, and due to the lack of a rich function family, researchers are trying to deploy function-privacy techniques for the inner-product functionality [17, 18, 19, 20, 11]. These works focus on functions of the form $f(x, y) = \langle x, y \rangle$, where x is provided by the user, and y takes the role of the functionality. Hence, given an encryption $\text{Enc}(x)$ of some x and a functional decryption key dk_y for y , the decryption algorithm outputs $\langle x, y \rangle$. The notion of function-privacy in these approaches comes from generating dk_y so that information about y remains hidden. However sophisticated, the problem with these approaches is that the evaluator always knows that an inner-product functionality is being computed – even when both x and y remain private.

However, through our study of FE and function hiding, we found that despite the fine-grained computation capabilities, it comes with some drawbacks that make it not suitable for all use cases. As such, we aimed to look into HE schemes to provide solutions to use cases that could not be easily attained through FE. Alongside the modern developments of FE, HE has been seen as a prospective method to encourage secure communications and operations on encrypted data. This method, relying on the mathematical concept of homomorphism, has been recognized in cryptography since the late 1970s; however, the practical developments started at much the same time as FE.

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4.2 Homomorphic Encryption

HE has long been regarded as the “holy grail” of cryptography due to its potential for versatile cryptographic primitives and its wide range of applications. In 1978, year after the introduction of RSA [21], Rivest et al. proposed HE as a solution to the conflict between user privacy and the need to delegate data and computational requirements [22]. HE allows computations to be performed on encrypted data, producing an encrypted result that can be decrypted to the same result as if the computations had been done on unencrypted data.

A general example of HE would be given an arbitrary number of encrypted inputs $\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x_1), \dots, \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x_n)$, and by using an evaluation key evk , an HE scheme would be able to evaluate an arbitrary function f , e.g. addition or multiplication, while the inputs are still encrypted, so that $\text{Eval}(\text{evk}, f, (\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x_1), \dots, \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x_n))) = \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x_1 + \dots + x_n)$ [23]. In this case, decrypting the resulting ciphertext would produce the sum of all inputs x , i.e. $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, x_1 + \dots + x_n)) = x_1 + \dots + x_n$.

Several existing public-key cryptosystems, including RSA [21], ElGamal [24], and Goldwasser-Micali [25], have some homomorphic properties, but none support the computation of arbitrary functions on ciphertexts. The search for a fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) scheme continued until Gentry’s breakthrough in 2009 [23]. Gentry’s scheme relies on the difficulty of specific mathematical problems concerning ideal lattices, **enabling unrestricted computations on encrypted data**. Nevertheless, the high computational cost, demand for significant computing resources as well as rising communication costs due to ciphertext expansion [26] presented challenges. As stated in [27], HE schemes are not optimized for efficient communication and computation on the client side, hindering their applicability in real-world scenarios. To tackle this problem, researchers put forth the concept of Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption (HHE).

HHE involves the integration of one or more HE schemes with a symmetric cipher to create a more robust and efficient encryption system [27]. In an HHE scheme, the user’s data is initially encrypted using a Symmetric Key Encryption (SKE) scheme. The encrypted data is then transmitted to a Cloud Service Provider (CSP), which employs a homomorphic symmetric decryption circuit to *transform* the symmetric cipher into a homomorphic cipher. Subsequently, CSP **performs the actual computation on the ciphertext homomorphically** and sends the cipher results back to the user **in such applications such as Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning (PPML)**. By combining SKE and HE schemes, an HHE system gains the capacity to perform more computations while **reducing the communication overhead** typically associated with using HE schemes [26].

As such we aimed to benefit clients with lower capability devices by utilising the significantly reduced bandwidth requirements and computational costs of HHE and show this improvement

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through experimental results. However, these reduced costs come with a higher computational cost for computations in the encrypted domain (also known as server-side computations).

4.3 Contributions

This document covers the contributions we have achieved both with FE and HE/HHE. These contributions can be summarised as:

- C1. We design two FE constructions which are applicable to a variety of use-cases. The first construction is Need for Speed (NFS) – lightweight MIFE scheme based on Elliptic Curves (ECC) used for adding data. NFS is constructed to be usable on resource-constrained devices. Additionally we provide a novel use case of FE, SPADE, which allows an analyst to partially decrypt a ciphertext, revealing only the occurrences of the value within a vector.
- C2. To provide a solution for function-privacy in FE schemes, we constructed a universal FE framework, named Forward and Function Private (FFP). Through this generic framework we enable any message-private, multi-input FE scheme to provide function-privacy, that is, it ensure the correctness of the functional decryption, while not leaking any information about function being performed to the computing party. Through a theoretical evaluation, we show that our construction can be successfully used by constrained devices due to its low storage and computational costs.
- C3. We analyze the theoretical principles of HHE schemes and their constructions, as well as provide a comprehensive comparison between different schemes. We analyze various implementation aspects such as processing power, memory allocation, security, and ease of running a scheme. We provide a fair and solid comparison of the examined works by running all schemes in the Go programming language.
- C4. We present GuardML, a two party or three party protocol, enabling an authorized entity (e.g., an analyst) to process HHE-encrypted data as if it were unencrypted efficiently. Through extensive experiments, we showcase the practicality of our protocol in an ML scenario using a sensitive medical dataset. The experimental results indicate that our PPML protocol achieves nearly comparable accuracy to the plaintext version while safeguarding both the dataset and the neural network's privacy. Additionally, most of the computation cost is effectively outsourced to a CSP.

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4.4 Organisation

Throughout the project, we have analysed both the advantages and disadvantages of FE and HE as well as developed constructions which make use of both of them to produce exemplary results in the field. As such this document first provides in [section 5](#) the theoretical details of how FE schemes are constructed, explaining their notation and core mathematical theorems. Following this, we introduce three FE constructions that were developed throughout the HARPOCRATES project, namely “Need for Speed” in [section 6](#), “SPADE” in [section 7](#), and “Forward and Function Private (FFP)” in [section 8](#). The document continues by covering the theoretical constructions of HE in [section 9](#), explaining the different schemes that have been developed and their security. After describing the different HE schemes, we cover the HHE schemes in [section 9](#), which have been developed to optimize the applicability of HE for real-life applications more precisely for users. We complete the HHE section by providing the construction of GuardML in [section 11](#), an efficient way of performing PPML through HHE. Finally, we conclude the deliverable in [section 12](#) by providing the core takeaways of the document and the constructions we prepared.

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5 Functional Encryption

In this section, we cover the common notation used for FE, general definitions, theorems and their correctness. Additionally, we cover how FE is constructed from the ElGamal encryption schemes as well as expand them to constructions from ECC-based schemes.

5.1 Background

Notation A public/private key pair of a public-key encryption scheme PKE is denoted as (pk, sk) . If the public/private key pair is associated with an entity E , then we write (pk_E, sk_E) . Vectors are denoted in bold as $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$. A Probabilistic Polynomial Time (PPT) adversary \mathcal{ADV} is a randomized algorithm for which there exists a polynomial $p(z)$, such that for all valid inputs z , the running time of $\mathcal{ADV}(z)$ is bounded by $|p(z)|$. A function $negl(\cdot)$ is called negligible, iff $\forall c \in \mathbb{N}, \exists n_0 \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq n_0, negl(n) < n^{-c}$.

Definition 1 (Cyclic Group). A cyclic (multiplicative) group is a finite group \mathbb{G} generated by a single element $g \in \mathbb{G}$. g is called generator of \mathbb{G} and we denote $\mathbb{G} = \langle g \rangle$.

Definition 2 (Fermat number). A Fermat number is a prime number of the form $2^{2^k} + 1$, where $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Note that any prime number of the form $2^n + 1$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ is a Fermat number. Moreover, there is an infinite number of Fermat numbers. The proof of these statements is omitted here as it goes beyond the scope of this article.

Theorem 1 (Lagrange's theorem). Let \mathbb{G} be a finite group of cardinal n and neutral element 1. For an element $g \in \mathbb{G}$, call order of g the smallest $k \in \mathbb{Z}^*$ such that $g^k = 1$. Lagrange's theorem states that the order of any element of \mathbb{G} divides n . It follows that if \mathbb{G} is a cyclic group of generator g , the order of g is equal to n .

We omit the proof of Lagrange's theorem, as it is a well-known result in group theory.

5.1.1 Public Key Encryption

Definition 3 (Public-Key Encryption). A public-key encryption scheme PKE for a message space \mathcal{X} , consists of three algorithms $PKE = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$. A PKE scheme is said to be correct if:

$$\Pr[\text{Dec}(sk, c) \neq x \in \mathcal{X} \mid [(pk, sk) \leftarrow \text{Gen}(1^\lambda)] \wedge [c \leftarrow \text{Enc}(pk, x)]] = negl(\lambda) \quad (1)$$

where $negl(\lambda)$ is a negligible function in the security parameter λ .

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Definition 4 (Additive Ciphertext Homomorphism (ACH)). *We say that a public-key encryption scheme PKE is additive ciphertext homomorphic if:*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Enc}(\text{pk}_i, x_i) = \text{Enc}\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \text{pk}_i, \sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right) \quad (2)$$

where the first sum is the addition on the ciphertext space, the second the addition on the public key space and the third the addition on the message space.

Definition 5 (Additive Key Homomorphism (AKH)). *We say that a public-key encryption scheme PKE is additive key homomorphic if for every two public/private key pairs $(\text{pk}_1, \text{sk}_1)$ and $(\text{pk}_2, \text{sk}_2)$ generated by PKE.Gen , we can generate a new valid public/private key pair as $(\text{pk}_1 + \text{pk}_2, \text{sk}_1 + \text{sk}_2)$, where $\text{pk}_1 + \text{pk}_2$ is the addition in the space of public keys and $\text{sk}_1 + \text{sk}_2$ is the addition in the space of secret keys.*

Definition 6 (selective-Indistinguishability-Based Security). *For a PKE scheme $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ we define the following experiments:*

$\text{Exp}^{s\text{-IND-CPA-}\beta}(\mathcal{ADV})$	
<p>Initialize(λ, x_0, x_1) $(\text{pk}, \text{sk}) \xleftarrow{\\$} \text{Gen}(1^\lambda)$ Return pk Challenge$()$ $c_\beta \xleftarrow{\\$} \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m_\beta)$</p>	<p>Finalize(β') $\beta' = \beta$</p>

The advantage ϵ of \mathcal{ADV} is defined as:

$$\epsilon = \left| \Pr[\text{Exp}^{s\text{-ind-CPA-}0}(\mathcal{ADV}) = 1] - \Pr[\text{Exp}^{s\text{-ind-CPA-}1}(\mathcal{ADV}) = 1] \right| \quad (3)$$

We say that PKE is $s\text{-IND-CPA-}\beta$ secure if

$$\epsilon = \text{negl}(\lambda)$$

5.1.2 ElGamal Over Elliptic Curves

As previously stated, the proposed construction relies on the ElGamal cipher defined over elliptic curves. Hence, we begin by informally recalling how the cryptosystem works [28]. Let E be an elliptic curve defined over $GF(p)$, where p is a large prime. The ElGamal secret key is then an element $s \in GF(p)$, while the corresponding public key is computed as $Y = s \cdot G \in E$, where G is a generator of E . To encrypt a message $x \in GF(p)$, we first pick a random $r \in [1, N - 1]$,

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where N is the order of the curve, and in the end, we compute $c = \text{Enc}(x) = (P, Q) = (r \cdot G, x \cdot G + r \cdot Y)$. Finally, for decryption, we can recover the original message using the private key s , by computing $-s \cdot P + Q$. A more formal description is illustrated in [Figure 1](#).

EIGamal Over Elliptic Curves

Let E be an elliptic curve of order N , defined over $GF(p)$, where p is a large prime. Then, the EIGamal cryptosystem over elliptic curves is defined as a tuple $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$, such that:

PKE.Gen(1^λ)

1. Pick a generator G of E
2. Sample the private key as $s \xleftarrow{\$} GF(p)$
3. Compute the public key as $Y = s \cdot G$
4. Output (s, Y)

PKE.Enc(Y, x)

1. Sample $r \xleftarrow{\$} [1, N - 1]$
2. Compute $c = (P, Q) = (r \cdot G, x \cdot G + r \cdot Y)$
3. Output c

PKE.Dec(s, c)

1. Output $-s \cdot P + Q$

Figure 1 – EIGamal Over Elliptic Curves

5.1.3 From Points to Integers

While addition over an elliptic curve is possible, we can only add points on the curve, which is not very useful in the context of FE. To this end, we define a mapping function as in [29] with the purpose of mapping elements of $GF(p)$ to the curve as follows:

Definition 7 (Mapping function). *Let E be an elliptic curve defined over $GF(p)$, where p is a large prime. Moreover, let G be a generator of E . Then we define a mapping function $f_{map} : GF(p) \rightarrow E$ such that:*

$$\forall x \in GF(p) : f_{map}(x) = x \cdot G = X \in E, \quad (4)$$

where \cdot refers to point multiplication over E . For the rest of this deliverable, we write xG to simplify reading.

Note that when the curve is defined over a field of prime order, every element in the field is a generator of the curve. Hence, finding a generator is trivial. With the help of f_{map} , we can add elements in $GF(p)$, using points on the curve. This is possible because by definition, we have that:

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$$f_{map}(x_1) + \cdots + f_{map}(x_n) = x_1G + \cdots + x_nG = (x_1 + \cdots + x_n)G = f_{map}(x_1 + \cdots + x_n), \quad (5)$$

where each $x_i \in GF(p)$ and $f_{map}(x_i) \in E$. Note that, unambiguously, we use the same notation for addition in $GF(p)$ and its underlying addition in E . While the inverse function f_{map}^{-1} exists, computing it is equivalent to solving the DLP over an elliptic curve. However, when each x_i is small (i.e. not of cryptographic size), this is possible by relying on a list of pre-computed values. Considering x_i small is realistic as data generated or collected by the devices in question will not be of cryptographic size.

5.1.4 Multi-Input Functional Encryption

Definition 8 (Multi-Input Functional Encryption). *A Multi-Input Functional Encryption (MIFE) scheme for a message space \mathcal{X} , where \mathcal{X} is a vector space of dimension n , is a tuple of four algorithms $MIFE = (\text{Setup}, \text{Enc}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Dec})$ such that:*

- $\text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$: *The Setup algorithm takes a security parameter λ as input and outputs a master public/private key (mpk, msk) .*
- $\text{Enc}(\text{mpk}, \mathbf{x})$: *The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. Upon input the master public key mpk and a vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathcal{X}$ outputs a ciphertext $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, \dots, c_n)$.*
- $\text{KeyGen}(\text{msk}, f)$: *The key generation algorithm KeyGen is a deterministic algorithm. Upon input the master secret key msk and a function f , outputs a functional decryption key sk_f .*
- $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}_f, \mathbf{c})$: *The decryption algorithm Dec is a deterministic algorithm. Upon input a functional decryption key sk_f and a ciphertext \mathbf{c} , outputs $f(\mathbf{x}) = f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$.*

A MIFE scheme is said to be correct if and only if:

$$\Pr[\text{Dec}(\text{sk}_f, \mathbf{c}) \neq f(\mathbf{x})] \mid [(\text{mpk}, \text{msk}) \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)] \wedge [\mathbf{c} \leftarrow \text{Enc}(\text{mpk}, \mathbf{x})] \wedge [\text{sk}_f \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(\text{msk}, \text{sk}_f)] = \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (6)$$

Definition 9 (MIFE Indistinguishability-Based Security). *For a MIFE scheme $MIFE = (\text{Setup}, \text{Enc}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Dec})$, we define the following experiments:*

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$Exp^{s-IND-FE-CPA-\beta}(\mathcal{ADV})$

Initialize(λ, x_0, x_1)

$mpk, msk \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$

$L \leftarrow \emptyset$

Output mpk

Key Generation(f)

$L \leftarrow L \cup \{f\}$

$sk_f \xleftarrow{\$} \text{KeyGen}(msk, f)$

Output sk_f

Challenge()

$c_\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Enc}(mpk, x_\beta)$

Finalize(β')

If $\exists f \in L$:

$f(x_0) \neq f(x_1)$

Output \perp

Else

$\beta' = \beta$

The advantage ϵ of \mathcal{ADV} is defined as:

$$\epsilon = \left| Pr[Exp^{s-ind-FE-CPA-0}(\mathcal{ADV}) = 1] - Pr[Exp^{s-ind-FE-CPA-1}(\mathcal{ADV}) = 1] \right|$$

We say that MIFE is s-IND-FE-CPA- β secure iff $\epsilon = \text{negl}(\lambda)$

5.1.5 Generic Multi-Input Functional Encryption Scheme for the Summation of a Vector's Components

We now recall the generic construction from [30], and in the next section, provide our lightweight instantiation from ECC.

Definition 10 (MIFE for the summation of a vector's components (MIFE_{sum})). *Let* $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ *be an IND-CPA secure cryptosystem that also fulfills the ACH and AKE properties. Then we define* MIFE_{sum} *as* $\text{MIFE}_{sum} = (\text{Setup}, \text{Enc}, \text{KeyGen}, \text{Dec})$ *where:*

1. $\text{Setup}(1^\lambda, n)$: *The Setup algorithm invokes the PKE's Gen algorithm and generates n public/private key pairs as $(pk_1, sk_1), \dots, (pk_n, sk_n)$. It outputs a master public/private key pair as mpk, msk , where $mpk = (\text{params}, pk_1, \dots, pk_n)$ and $msk = (sk_1, \dots, sk_n)$.*
2. $\text{Enc}(mpk, x)$: *The Encryption algorithm Enc, takes as input the master public key mpk and a vector x and outputs $c = \{c_1, \dots, c_n\}$, where $c_i = \text{Enc}(pk_i, x_i)$.*
3. $\text{KeyGen}(msk)$: *The Key Generation algorithm takes as input the master secret key msk and outputs a functional key sk as $sk = \sum_1^n sk_i$.*
4. $\text{Dec}(sk, c)$: *The Decryption Algorithm takes as input the functional key sk and an encrypted vector c and outputs $\text{PKE.Dec}\left(sk, \sum_{i=1}^n c\right)$.*

Theorem 2. *Let* $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ *be an IND-CPA secure public-key encryption scheme that is both additive key and cipher homomorphic. Moreover, let MIFE be the generic multi-*

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input FE scheme for the summation of a vector's components presented in [30], that can be instantiated from PKE. Then MIFE is s -IND-FE-CPA secure.

5.1.6 Proof of Theorem 2

Proof. Let $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ be a public-key encryption scheme and \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} be two independent PPT algorithms. We set game 1 as the game for PKE shown in Definition 6, in which \mathcal{B} is the adversary for a challenger \mathcal{C} . Besides, we set game 2 as the game for MIFE shown in Definition 9, in which \mathcal{A} is the adversary and \mathcal{B} is the challenger.

Setup of game 1 The adversary \mathcal{B} randomly samples an element x in the message space of PKE and sends it to the challenger \mathcal{C} . The latter generates a pair of keys $(pk_C, sk_C) \leftarrow \text{PKE.Gen}(1^\lambda)$, randomly picks $b \leftarrow \{0, 1\}$ and sends back both pk_C and $c_b \leftarrow \text{PKE.Enc}(pk, b \cdot x)$ to \mathcal{B} .

Generation of keys for game 2 First of all, \mathcal{B} calls \mathcal{A} , who provides two messages \mathbf{x}_0 and \mathbf{x}_1 such that:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{0,i} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_{1,i} \quad (7)$$

\mathcal{B} generates a basis for a vector space $\mathcal{V} \in \mathcal{M}$ such that $\forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{V}, \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 0$ in order to ensure that every decryption key query will be made for vectors $\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n x_{1,i} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_{0,i}$. She samples $n - 1$ independent vectors $\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n-1}$, such that $\forall i \in [n - 1], \mathbf{r}_i$ is independent of $\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0$ and sets the basis to $(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n-1})$. $\forall i \in [n]$, set $\alpha_i = \frac{x_{1,i} - x_{0,i}}{\|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0\|_2}$. This construction induces the canonical vectors $\mathbf{e}_i = \left[\alpha_i \cdot (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0) + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \mathbf{r}_j \right]$. Finally, \mathcal{B} produces $(pk_{\alpha_j}, sk_{\alpha_j}) \leftarrow \text{PKE.Gen}(1^\lambda), \forall j \in [1, n - 1]$ and sets:

$$pk_i = \alpha_i \cdot pk_C + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} pk_{\alpha_j} \quad \text{and} \quad mpk = (pk_1, \dots, pk_n).$$

Remark that the associated secret keys $sk_i = \alpha_i \cdot sk_C + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} sk_{\alpha_j}$ are unknown from \mathcal{B} , who does not know sk_C . In the end, the challenger \mathcal{B} sets the functional decryption key to $sk = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} sk_{\alpha_j}$ using the previous construction.

Challenges for game 2 The adversary \mathcal{A} sends \mathbf{x}_0 and \mathbf{x}_1 such that $\sum_{i=1}^n x_{0,i} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_{1,i}$. \mathcal{B} samples at random $\beta \leftarrow \{0, 1\}$. In theory, she should pick \mathbf{x}_β and send back its encryption.

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However, in order to break the game 1, she instead computes:

$$c = \alpha \cdot c_b + \text{PKE.Enc} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \text{pk}_{\alpha_j}, 0 \right) + \text{PKE.Enc}(0, \mathbf{x}_\beta) \quad (8)$$

and sends c to \mathcal{A} . Finally, the latter outputs a guess for β . If her guess is correct, then \mathcal{B} guesses that \mathcal{C} encrypted 0. If not, \mathcal{B} guesses that \mathcal{C} encrypted x . We treat those cases separately.

If \mathcal{C} encrypted 0, then [Equation 8](#) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} c &= \text{PKE.Enc}(\alpha \cdot \text{pk}_{\mathcal{C}}, 0) + \text{PKE.Enc} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \text{pk}_{\alpha_j}, 0 \right) + \text{PKE.Enc}(0, \mathbf{x}_\beta) \\ &= \text{PKE.Enc}(\alpha \cdot \text{pk}_{\mathcal{C}} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \text{pk}_{\alpha_j} + 0, 0 + 0 + \mathbf{x}_\beta) = \text{PKE.Enc}(\text{pk}_i, \mathbf{x}_\beta) \end{aligned}$$

In this case, \mathcal{B} simulates a perfect view of the environment for \mathcal{A} . Therefore, if \mathcal{A} guesses β in game 2 with an advantage $\epsilon_{\mathcal{A}}$, \mathcal{B} , guesses b in game 1 with an advantage $\epsilon_{\mathcal{B}}$. Finally, $\epsilon_{\mathcal{A}} = \epsilon_{\mathcal{B}}$.

If \mathcal{C} encrypted x , then [Equation 8](#) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} c &= \text{PKE.Enc}(\alpha \cdot \text{pk}_{\mathcal{C}}, \alpha \cdot x) + \text{PKE.Enc} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \text{pk}_{\alpha_j}, 0 \right) + \text{PKE.Enc}(0, \mathbf{x}_\beta) \\ &= \text{PKE.Enc}(\alpha \cdot \text{pk}_{\mathcal{C}} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \text{pk}_{\alpha_j} + 0, \alpha \cdot x + 0 + \mathbf{x}_\beta) = \text{PKE.Enc}(\text{pk}_i, \alpha \cdot x + \mathbf{x}_\beta) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\alpha = \frac{\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0}{\|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0\|_2^2}$, we have

$$\alpha \cdot x + \mathbf{x}_\beta = \frac{x}{\|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0\|_2^2} (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{x}_\beta = \frac{x}{\|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0\|_2^2} (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{x}_0 + \beta (\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0)$$

If we set $\mu := \frac{x}{\|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0\|_2^2} + \beta$, we obtain $c = \text{PKE.Enc}(\text{pk}_i, \mu \cdot \mathbf{x}_1 + (1 - \mu) \cdot \mathbf{x}_0)$, which corresponds to the challenge ciphertext. Remark that $\mu \cdot \mathbf{x}_1 + (1 - \mu) \mathbf{x}_0$ is well defined, as a linear combination of elements of the vector space V with unitary norm. Finally, the value of β being hidden, the advantage $\epsilon_{\mathcal{B}}$ of \mathcal{B} is negligible.

Conclusion The overall advantage of \mathcal{B} on game 1 is thus $\epsilon_{\mathcal{B}} = \epsilon_{\mathcal{A}}$, which means that the adversary \mathcal{A} can break our MIFE protocol if \mathcal{B} is able to break the PKE construction. By con-

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trapolation, since PKE is IND-CPA secure, our construction is also IND-CPA secure, which concludes. \square

5.2 Instantiation from ECC - Formal Construction

5.2.1 Instantiation from ECC

We introduce a construction relying on the Additive Ciphertext and Key homomorphic properties as per [Definition 4](#) and [Definition 5](#). In short, an ElGamal ciphertext for a message x is given by:

$$\text{Enc}(x) = (P, Q) = (rG, xG + rY), \quad (9)$$

where r is sampled randomly in \mathbb{Z}_N^* , N is the order of the curve, G is a generator of the curve and Y is the public key. As we see, each ciphertext consists of two points on the curve. Thus, we need to define a new operation that will allow us to add ciphertexts together:

Randomness Re-Use In a setting involving multiple clients, ElGamal maintains its security even when the same random value r is reused, as shown in [31]. This differs from the traditional single-client ElGamal setup, where reusing the same randomness r would compromise security. However, in scenarios with $n > 1$ distinct key pairs, this vulnerability does not apply.

Definition 11 (Addition of ElGamal ciphertexts over elliptic curves). *Assuming that we have two messages x_1 and x_2 with corresponding ciphertexts $\text{Enc}(x_1)$ and $\text{Enc}(x_2)$, we define the following operation, denoted by \oplus :*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Enc}(x_1) \oplus \text{Enc}(x_2) &= (rG, x_1G + rY_1) \oplus (rG, x_2G + rY_2) = \\ &= (2rG, (x_1 + x_2)G + r(Y_1 + Y_2)) = (P', Q'), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where the '+' symbol on the right side of the equation, denotes the standard addition and $P', Q' \in E$.

To prove that the generic MIFE construction can be instantiated from ElGamal over ECC, all we need to do is prove that the ECC variation of ElGamal is both ACH and AKH as per [Definition 4](#) and [Definition 5](#). In particular, we prove the following theorem;

Theorem 3. *Let MIFE be the generic multi-input FE scheme presented in [30]. Then, it is possible to instantiate MIFE using ElGamal's variation over elliptic curves as the public-key encryption scheme PKE.*

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Proof. As already stated, we prove that ElGamal's variation over elliptic curves is both additive key and cipher homomorphic as per [Definition 4](#) and [Definition 5](#).

- **Additive Key Homomorphic:** Let $s_1, \dots, s_n \in GF(p)$ be n private keys and Y_1, \dots, Y_n be their respective public keys. Recall that $Y_i := s_i G, i \in [n]$. Therefore,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i = \sum_{i=1}^n s_i G = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n s_i \right) \cdot G$$

Since $GF(p)$ is closed under addition, $\sum_{i=1}^n s_i \in GF(p)$. Hence, $\sum_{i=1}^n s_i$ is a valid secret key and $\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i$ is a valid corresponding public key by construction. Thus, the variation of ElGamal over elliptic curves is additive key homomorphic.

- **Additive Cipher Homomorphic:** Let $x_1, \dots, x_n \in GF(p)$ be n measurements and c_1, \dots, c_n be their respective ciphertexts. Recall that $c_i := (rG, x_i G + rY), i \in [n]$, for a randomness $r \in \mathbb{Z}_N^*$ and the public key $Y \in E$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n c_i &= \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (rG, x_i G + rY) \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^n rG, \sum_{i=1}^n x_i G + \sum_{i=1}^n rY \right) \\ &= \left((nr) \cdot G, \sum_{i=1}^n x_i G + (nr) \cdot Y \right), \end{aligned}$$

where \oplus is the operation defined in equation 10. Hence, $\bigoplus_{i=1}^n c_i$ is a valid encryption of $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i$ for the same public key Y and a randomness $nr \in \mathbb{Z}_N^*$ – since \mathbb{Z}_N^* is closed under addition – and thus the variation of ElGamal over elliptic curves is additive cipher homomorphic. □

A direct result of [Theorem 2](#) and [Theorem 3](#), is that our instantiation is $s - IND - FE - CPA$ -secure as per [Definition 9](#).

In this section, we introduce our notation and recall the definitions of MIFE in the private-key setting.

Correctness For correctness we require that for every $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and for every $x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i$ it holds:

$$\text{Dec}(\text{KeyGen}(\text{msk}, f), \text{Enc}(\text{msk}, x_1), \dots, \text{Enc}(\text{msk}, x_n)) = y \in \mathcal{Y},$$

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with all but a negligible probability over the internal randomness of Setup, Enc, KeyGen and Dec.

Two desirable properties of FE schemes are those of message-privacy and function-privacy.

Definition 12 (Message-Privacy). *An FE scheme is said to be message-private, if any two messages x_0 and x_1 are computationally indistinguishable for any adversary that can adaptively obtain decryption keys for any function such that $f(x_0) = f(x_1)$.*

Naturally, the above definition is quite restrictive when we deal with a rich family of functions. To this end, in [16], authors proposed a stronger security definition for function-privacy.

Definition 13 (Function-Privacy). *An FE scheme is said to be function-private if any adversary that obtains encryptions of x_0 and x_1 , and functional decryption keys sk_{f_0}, sk_{f_1} for two functions f_0, f_1 such that $f_0(x_0) = f_1(x_1)$, cannot distinguish between them.*

For a formal presentation of the security games for message and function privacy, we refer the reader to [16].

Following these preliminaries we are able to construct various FE protocols, which can solve a variety of problem cases. As such, we have developed 3 FE constructions, which can be applied to various usecases and on a variety of devices. We present these three constructions:

- Need for Speed – an FE construction, which can be used on heavily resource-constrained devices for vector addition;
- SPADE – a selective access FE construction, which allows counting the occurrences of specific values in a vector;
- Forward and Function Private (FFP) – a generic function hiding construction which can be applied to various FE schemes and constructions.

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6 Function Encryption Construction 1: Need for Speed

6.1 System Model

Before presenting the formal use case of the proposed construction, we first provide a description of the system model we consider. Our setup consists of four entities: (i) Edge Devices (**ED**), (ii) Data Owner (**O**), (iii) Storage Server (**SS**), and (iv) Analyst (**A**).

- **Edge Devices (ED):** Let $\mathcal{D} = \{d_1, \dots, d_n\}$ be a set of resource-constrained sensor devices deployed in an environment to collect data x . Each device encrypts collected data and sends it to the storage server.
- **Data Owner (O):** We assume the existence of a fully trusted data owner **O**, who administers and is responsible for a set of edge devices in a specific environment. **O** is responsible for generating functional decryption keys for the particular function for data collected by the devices.
- **Storage Server (SS):** We assume the existence of a storage server **SS**, an abstract external storage platform that will store encrypted data received from each device d_i . Once access to data is requested, **SS** returns the data to the requesting party.
- **Analyst (A):** Let **A** be an entity that wishes to learn the result of a specific function computed for the encrypted data collected from a set of devices \mathcal{D}' such that $\mathcal{D}' \subseteq \mathcal{D}$.

6.2 Use Case Protocol

We now formally describe a detailed protocol to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed construction. For this use case, we consider a scenario where **O** possesses n number of sensor devices (d_1, \dots, d_n) . Additionally, we assume the existence of a storage server **SS** where encrypted data from the sensor nodes will be stored. In our use case, each device d_i collects environmental or event data x_i , encrypts and uploads the data to **SS**. The main building blocks of our protocol are as follows:

- An IND-CCA2 secure public key encryption scheme $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$;
- An EUF-CMA secure signature scheme $S = (\text{sign}, \text{verify})$;
- A first and second pre-image resistant cryptographic hash function H ;
- A synchronized clock between all entities.

As a first step, each device d_i runs the MIFE.Setup algorithm to generate a private/public key pair (s_i, Y_i) for ElGamal's cryptosystem. On completion, **O** computes msk and mpk as demonstrated

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Algorithm 1 Setup($1^\lambda, n$)

Device d_i :

- 1: Generate n private keys as $s_i \xleftarrow{\$} GF(p)$
- 2: For each s_i , generate the corresponding public key as $Y_i = s_i G \in E$

Device Owner O :

- 3: Output msk as $\text{msk} = (s_1, \dots, s_n)$
 - 4: Output mpk as $\text{mpk} = (Y_1, \dots, Y_n)$
-

Algorithm 2 Enc(mpk, c)

Device d_i :

- 1: Generate a measurement $x_i \in GF(p)$
- 2: Compute $f_{\text{map}}(x_i) = x_i G = X_i \in E$
- 3: Pick a random $r \in \mathbb{Z}_N^*$, where N is the order of the curve
- 4: $c_i = \text{Enc}(x_i) = (P, Q) = (rG, X_i + rY_i)$
- 5: Send $m_1 = \langle t_1, c_i, \sigma_{d_i}(H(t_1 \| c_i)) \rangle$ to **SS**

SS:

- 6: Verify the freshness and the integrity of m_1
 - 7: If any verification fails, output \perp and abort the protocol
 - 8: Store c_i
-

Algorithm 3 KeyGen(msk)

Analyst A :

- 1: Send a request for a functional decryption key, for a function f , to the data owner via m_2

Data Owner O :

- 2: Verify the freshness and the integrity of m_2
 - 3: If any verification fails, output \perp and abort the protocol.
 - 4: Otherwise, compute the functional decryption key sk_f as $\text{sk}_f = \sum_1^n s_i$
 - 5: Send sk_f to A via m_3
-

in Algorithm 1¹.

Subsequently, we assume that each device d_i generates some data x_i , e.g. generated data about an event. Upon generation, d_i computes $f_{\text{map}}(x_i)$, samples a random r and encrypts it as shown in line 5 of Algorithm 2 to get c_i . Finally, the encrypted measurement is outsourced to **SS** via:

$$m_1 = \langle t_1, c_i, \sigma_{d_i}(H(t_1 \| c_i)) \rangle, \quad (11)$$

where t_1 is a timestamp and σ_{d_i} is d_i 's signature. Upon reception, **SS** verifies the freshness and the integrity of the message m_1 by checking the timestamp and the signature, respectively. **SS** outputs \perp and aborts the protocol if any verification fails. Otherwise, it will store all c_i .

On completion of the encryption phase, we assume that an analyst **A** wishes to compute a function on encrypted data collected by a set of devices \mathcal{D}' stored on **SS**. To do so, **A** first requests permission from **O** to do so by sending a request of the following form:

¹Note: we assume the data owner has secure access to the key pair generated by each device in its ownership.

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$$m_2 = \langle t_2, \text{req}(f), \sigma_A(H(t_2 \parallel \text{req}(f))) \rangle, \quad (12)$$

where $\text{req}(f)$ denotes a request for the specific function f . Upon reception, **O** verifies the freshness and integrity of the message. If any verification fails **O** outputs \perp and aborts the protocol. Otherwise, **O** first computes the functional decryption key sk_f for the specific function by running the MIFE.KeyGen algorithm as described in Algorithm 3. As a next step, **O** encrypts sk_f using the public key of the analyst **A** to get a ciphertext c_{sk_f} , and finally sends it to **A** via the following message:

$$m_3 = \langle t_3, c_{sk_f}, \sigma_O(H(t_3 \parallel c_{sk_f})) \rangle \quad (13)$$

Finally, and upon successful completion of the previous algorithm, **A** holds the functional decryption key sk_f . At this point, **A** sends a request for the encrypted data to the **SS** via:

$$m_4 = \langle t_4, \text{req}(\text{data}), \sigma_A(H(t_4 \parallel \text{req}(\text{data}))) \rangle \quad (14)$$

where $\text{req}(\text{data})$ denotes a request for encrypted data collected by the set of devices \mathcal{D}' . Upon reception, **SS** will verify the message's integrity and freshness. **SS** will output \perp and abort the protocol if the verification fails. Otherwise, **SS** will compute $c_{res} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^n c_i = (P_{res}, Q_{res})$ and reply to **A** with the following message:

$$m_5 = \langle t_5, c_{res}, \sigma_{SS}(H(t_5 \parallel c_{res})) \rangle \quad (15)$$

Upon reception, **A** will verify the freshness and integrity of the message. If the verification fails, **A** will output \perp and abort the protocol. Otherwise, **A** will run the functional decryption algorithm as shown in Algorithm 4 using sk_f to recover $f(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_1^n x_i$. A complete overview of this protocol is illustrated in Figure 2.

Possible Extension Our protocol can be enhanced to also facilitate the verification of the decryption process. This feature is crucial as it paves the way for addressing stronger threat models. In particular, if we assume an external malicious adversary that corrupts or colludes with **SS**, there's a potential risk of releasing manipulated statistics to deceive data analysts. We, therefore, argue about the importance of an analyst, possessing only $\{Y_i\}_{i \in [1, n]}$, c_{res} , and X_{res} , confirming that $f_{\text{map}}^{-1}(X_{res})$ matches $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i$, without additional information disclosures. Note

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Algorithm 4 $\text{Dec}(sk_f, c_1, \dots, c_n)$

Analyst A:

- 1: Send a request for the encrypted data to SS via m_4

Storage Server SS:

- 2: Verify the freshness and the integrity of m_4
- 3: If any verification fails, output \perp and abort the protocol
- 4: Otherwise compute the sum of the ciphertexts as $c_{res} = \bigoplus_{i=1}^n c_i = (P_{res}, Q_{res})$, where $P_{res}, Q_{res} \in E$
- 5: Send c_{res} to A via m_5

Analyst A:

- 6: Verify the freshness and the integrity of m_5
 - 7: If any verification fails, output \perp and abort the protocol
 - 8: Otherwise Compute n^{-1} the modular inverse of n in $GF(p)$
 - 9: Compute $-(n^{-1}sk_f) \cdot P_{res} + Q_{res}$ to get $X_{res} \in E$
 - 10: Run $f_{map}^{-1}(X_{res}) = x_1 + \dots + x_n \in GF(p)$
-

Figure 2 – Use Case Protocol Overview

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that this verification can be performed in a zero-knowledge fashion without access to the master secret key or the functional decryption key corresponding to the function. More specifically, it relies on a zero-knowledge proof related to a discrete logarithm over an elliptic curve. However, the topic of conducting zero-knowledge proofs on devices with limited resources is not studied in this work and is left as future work.

6.3 Security Analysis and Threat Model

In this subsection, we define a threat model as a list of attacks on our protocol and prove that our protocol is secure against these attacks. The security analysis of the construction relies on [Theorem 2](#) and is proven in [subsection 5.1.6](#). Additionally, the detailed security analysis of the protocol is provided in [subsection 6.3.1](#). Now, to evaluate the security of our construction, we consider an active adversary \mathcal{ADV} as a probabilistic polynomial time (PPT) algorithm and estimate its capabilities by a set of attacks she might try to launch. We assume that \mathcal{ADV} can interact with the messages m_1, \dots, m_5 and model her capabilities by the following attacks.

Attack 1 (Substitution Attack). *Let \mathcal{ADV} be a PPT adversary. \mathcal{ADV} successfully performs a Substitution Attack on a message m_i if she manages to replace m_i by $m_i^{\mathcal{ADV}}$ in an indistinguishable way.*

Attack 2 (Replay Attack). *Let \mathcal{ADV} be a PPT adversary. \mathcal{ADV} successfully launches a Replay Attack if she can send an outdated message m_i to a valid recipient and successfully convinces it that this message is fresh.*

6.3.1 Security Analysis

Based on the threat model defined in [subsection 6.3](#), we consider an active adversary \mathcal{A} who can interact at each protocol step through the messages m_1, \dots, m_5 . To demonstrate the security of our protocol, we prove the following theorem:

Theorem 4. *Let $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ be an IND-CCA2 secure public key encryption scheme and $S = (\text{sign}, \text{verify})$ be an EUF-CMA secure signature scheme. Let H be a first and second pre-image resistant cryptographic hash function, and assume that there exists a synchronized clock between all entities. Under these assumptions, our protocol defined in [subsection 6.2](#) is secure against an active PPT adversary \mathcal{A} for the threat model [subsection 6.3](#).*

Proof. We successively consider the attacks defined earlier in our threat model.

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Substitution Attack Soundness: Let \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} be two distinct parties in the set $\{\mathbf{ED}, \mathbf{O}, \mathbf{SS}, \mathbf{A}\}$ and m_1, \dots, m_5 be the messages sent during the protocol. Remark that a message m_i sent from \mathcal{S} to \mathcal{R} is of the form $m_i = \langle t_i, x, \sigma_{\mathcal{S}}(H(t_i||x)) \rangle$, where x is either a ciphertext or a request. To successfully perform a Substitution Attack, \mathcal{ADV} intercepts m_i sent by \mathcal{S} to \mathcal{R} and replace x by $x^{\mathcal{ADV}}$. Assume that \mathcal{ADV} is able to generate a valid value for $x^{\mathcal{ADV}}$. To replace $\sigma_{\mathcal{S}}(H(t_i||x))$ by $\sigma_{\mathcal{S}}(H(t_i||x^{\mathcal{ADV}}))$, \mathcal{ADV} has to forge the signature $\sigma_{\mathcal{S}}$. Since \mathcal{S} is EUF-CMA, this can only happen with a negligible probability. Thus, if λ is the security parameter for \mathcal{S} , the adversary's advantage for this attack is $\epsilon_1 = \text{negl}(\lambda)$.

The proof for the security against replay attack is similar since it also relies on the unforgeability of the signature.

Replay Attack Soundness: Let \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} be two distinct parties in the set $\{\mathbf{ED}, \mathbf{O}, \mathbf{SS}, \mathbf{A}\}$ and m_1, \dots, m_5 be the messages sent during the protocol. Remark that a message m_i sent from \mathcal{S} to \mathcal{R} is of the form $m_i = \langle t_i, x, \sigma_{\mathcal{S}}(H(t_i||x)) \rangle$, where x is either a ciphertext or a request. To successfully perform a Replay Attack, \mathcal{ADV} eavesdrops on a message m_i sent by \mathcal{S} to \mathcal{R} , store it, and send it again to \mathcal{R} later without him noticing that the message is outdated. To do so, she needs to convince \mathcal{R} that m_i is fresh by updating the timestamp t_i to $t_j, i \neq j$. However, to replace t_i by t_j in $\sigma_{\mathcal{S}}(H(t_i||x))$, \mathcal{ADV} has to forge the signature $\sigma_{\mathcal{S}}$. Since \mathcal{S} is EUF-CMA, this can only happen with a negligible probability. Thus, if λ is the security parameter for \mathcal{S} , the adversary's advantage for this attack is $\epsilon_2 = \text{negl}(\lambda)$.

Since the finite sum of negligible functions is also a negligible function, the overall advantage of an adversary \mathcal{ADV} on this protocol is $\epsilon = \text{negl}(\lambda)$. \square

Now we provide the proof of the [Theorem 2](#). Remark that this proof is already provided in [\[30\]](#) for the general construction; hence, we follow its outline and address the specific case of addition.

6.4 Experimental Evaluation

This subsection provides an evaluation of our proposed construction's performance and energy efficiency on two commercially available resource-constrained devices. To this end, our test bed consisted of the two sensor devices: an Arm Cortex-M4 nrf52840dk board², and an ARM Cortex-M3 Zolertia Re-Mote board³. For the rest of this subsection, we refer to the nrf52840dk

²<https://www.nordicsemi.com/Products/Development-hardware/nrf52840-dk>

³[https://docs.contiki-ng.org/en/develop/doc/platforms/zolertia/Zolertia-RE-Mote-platform-\(revision-B\).html](https://docs.contiki-ng.org/en/develop/doc/platforms/zolertia/Zolertia-RE-Mote-platform-(revision-B).html)

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Figure 3 – nrf

Figure 4 – Zolertia

Figure 5 – Standard

board as *nrf* and the Zolertia Re-Mote board simply as *zolertia*. Additionally, to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of our implementation, we measured its performance on a standard Desktop – referred to as *standard*. To test the necessary functions, we developed a Contiki-NG [32] application using the c25519⁴ cryptographic library for all cryptographic operations. Due to the resource constraints of the devices involved in these experiments, we focused primarily on analyzing the execution times and energy consumption of each algorithm. Also, for each device, we implemented all the algorithms introduced in subsection 6.2, i.e. instead of limiting our evaluations to only algorithms that a resource-constrained device would ideally execute, we executed all algorithms on each device to demonstrate the overall efficiency of our work. All programming for this subsection was written in C, and each experiment was conducted 50 times with the average results taken. We provide the open-source implementation for our experiments and construction on GitHub⁵.

6.4.1 Performance of Cryptographic Algorithms

To measure the performance of our work, we primarily focused on the computational performance of each algorithm. More precisely, we measured each device's time to execute a specific algorithm successfully. In Contiki-NG, the system time is measured in CPU ticks and is represented as long unsigned values. As a result of this implementation feature, all performance values observed from our experiments were recorded in ticks and converted to seconds. The specific figures were derived by dividing the number of recorded ticks by 128 (CPU ticks per second is 128, as defined in Contiki-NG). For these experiments, we resorted to the use case protocol described in subsection 6.2, which we used as the basis of our evaluations. However, we did not measure the computational costs of the public key encryption and secure signature

⁴<https://www.dlbeer.co.nz/oss/c25519.html>

⁵https://github.com/iammrgenie/sumFE_v2

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schemes used to provide confidentiality and authentication of the exchanged messages or any communication costs involved.

First, we assume that each device executes the Setup and Encryption algorithms. Subsequently, we consider a scenario where a device, upon receiving n number of ciphertexts, where $n \in [2, 100]$ executes the Keygen algorithm, and finally, the Decryption algorithm to retrieve the results in plain. Overall, it took the nrf board 0.97 seconds to run Setup, 3.07 seconds to run Encryption, and 1.22 seconds to run the Decryption for 2 ciphertexts. For the zolertia board, the execution times were 3.9 seconds for Setup, 12.3 seconds for Encryption, and 5.41 seconds for Decryption for 2 ciphertexts. Finally, on the standard machine, the execution times were 0.005 seconds for Setup, 0.015 seconds for Encryption, and 0.006 seconds to run the Decryption algorithm for 2 ciphertexts (Table 4). The KeyGen algorithm was executed for all devices with negligible computational overhead (e.g., for both zolertia and nrf boards, it registered 0 ticks). These results show that the cost of generating the functional decryption key using the KeyGen algorithm did not incur any computational overhead. Additionally, the most expensive algorithm for all devices is the Encryption algorithm, which involves three ECC point multiplications (Algorithm 2).

Functions	nrf		zolertia		standard
	CPU Ticks	Time(sec)	CPU Ticks	Time(sec)	Time(sec)
Setup	125	0.97	506	3.9	0.005
Encryption	393	3.07	1577	12.3	0.015
KeyGen	0	0	0	0	0.000
Decryption	156	1.22	693	5.41	0.006

Table 4 – Function Execution Times

As a next step, we measured the cost of executing the Setup and Encryption algorithms for a varying number of inputs from 1 to 100 on the nrf board (Figure 3), 1 to 20 on the zolertia board (Figure 4), and 1 to 1000 on the standard machine (Figure 5). Experiments on the zolertia board were limited to 20 due to memory constraints; the board froze when we tried to allocate memory for more than 20 key pairs and ciphertexts. To generate 100 unique key pairs by executing the Setup algorithm, it took the nrf 89.82 seconds, while it took the zolertia board 83.9 seconds to generate 20 unique key pairs. On the other hand, the standard device required only 2.81 seconds to generate 1000 unique key pairs. Meanwhile, the nrf board encrypted 100 inputs in 180.84 seconds, the zolertia board encrypted 20 data inputs in 172.7 seconds, and the standard device encrypted 1000 data inputs in 5.58 seconds. The cost of executing the Encryption algorithm continued to be the most expensive operation compared to the Setup algorithm. In our use case scenario, we note that the device is only responsible for running the Encryption algorithm.

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Finally, we measured the execution times of the KeyGen and Decryption functions for n number of ciphertexts, where $n \in [2, 100]$. Once again, due to resource constraints of the zolertia board, we could only run both functions for 20 ciphertexts. From our experiments, we observed that as the number of ciphertexts increased, there were negligible increases in the execution time of the Decryption function, due to the different computational capabilities between the nrf and zolertia boards. For example, the nrf board executed the Decryption function for two ciphertexts in 1.22 seconds and 1.39 seconds for 100 ciphertexts. Likewise, the standard machine executed the Decryption function in 0.006 seconds for two ciphertexts and 0.014 seconds for 1000 ciphertexts. The results from this subsection prove that our proposed construction is practical and efficient when deployed on devices with very limited resources, much like the devices used in our experiments.

Functions	nrf		zolertia	
	Time (s)	Energy (mJ)	Time (s)	Energy (mJ)
Setup	0.97	18.2	3.9	468
Encryption	3.07	57.7	12.3	1476
KeyGen	0	0	0	0
Decryption	1.22	22.9	5.41	649.2

Table 5 – Energy Consumption

6.4.2 Energy Consumption

In this phase of our evaluations, we utilized the Energest module provided by Contiki-NG to measure energy consumption. The Energest module provides lightweight software-based energy estimations for resource-constrained devices by monitoring the operations of the device's various hardware components (i.e., CPU and Radio). The active modes during our evaluations were the CPU active and radio listening. We observed that the energy measurements correlate directly to the execution times of the underlying algorithms (i.e., the longer it takes to run an algorithm, the more energy is consumed). To compute the energy values, we utilized current consumption values for the CPU active and radio listening modes of the chosen boards. Finally, we only focused on the nrf and zolertia boards for these experiments as these have constrained resources, and energy consumption is essential. The nrf board used 18.2 mJ to run Setup, 57.7 mJ to run Encryption, and 22.9 mJ to execute the Decryption for 2 ciphertexts. While the zolertia board consumed 468 mJ for Setup, 1.476 J for Encryption, and 649.2 mJ to execute Decryption for 2 ciphertexts (Table 5). Once again, from these results, we observe that our construction is energy efficient.

Finally, we acknowledge that our experiments would have been more comprehensive if we

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compared our evaluations with other implementations; however, it is worth noting that we found no FE schemes (including the construction in [30]) capable of being implemented on our sensor devices due to key size and memory constraints (one of the motivating factors for this work).

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7 Functional Encryption Construction 2: SPADE

Aside from our initial objectives, a question has been raised during our collaboration in the Harpocrates project: “Can we utilize privacy-preserving techniques on qualitative data?”. We responded with a positive answer, as we successfully designed an FE protocol, namely SPADE, that provides an authorized external data analyst access to selective information on hypnograms. In accordance with the specifications we set with our partners, SPADE supports the following functional queries from an analyst:

- Q1.** How often does a specific value appear in the hypnogram?
- Q2.** How often does a patient transition from one sleep stage to another?
- Q3.** How long does a patient stay in the same stage of sleep?

These specifications are detailed in [subsubsection 7.4.2](#) along with the other use cases we can consider.

7.1 Core Construction of SPADE

In this subsection, we present the algorithms that constitute the construction of SPADE. We rely on the MIFE construction defined in [Definition 8](#).

Parameters The space of messages is $\mathcal{M} = \mathbb{Z}_t^n$ where $n > 0$ is the number of entries and $t > 0$ their range. For a power of prime $q > t + 1$, the space of secret keys $\text{msk} = (s_1, \dots, s_n)$ is \mathbb{Z}_q^n . The corresponding public key $\text{mpk} = (g^{s_1}, \dots, g^{s_n})$ lies in \mathbb{G}^n where \mathbb{G} is a (cyclic) group of order q . Additionally, we denote $\alpha_j \in \mathbb{Z}_q$ the personal secret identifier of a user u_j . The generation and use of this identifier is detailed in [In this subsection we do not specify the parameters \$t\$ and \$q\$ but in practice we take \$q\$ a Fermat number, \$t < q - 1\$ and \$\mathcal{S} = \{2k + 1, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\lfloor q/2 \rfloor - 1}\}\$ the set of odd integers in \$\mathbb{Z}_q\$, as detailed in \[subsubsection 7.1.2\]\(#\).](#)

Following, we introduce our system model’s entities to describe the main construction. The full system model, including the security assumptions, is detailed in [section 7.2](#).

System’s Entities In order to present the algorithms, we provide a basic system model that will be elaborated in [subsection 7.2](#). The model we consider consists of three entities: (i) Key Curator (KC), (ii) Users (U) and (iii) Data Analyst (DA).

7.1.1 Algorithms

First of all, KC generates the master secret key and master public key (msk, mpk) through the setup [Algorithm 5](#). Every user u_j who wants to register to the system samples an element

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$\alpha_j \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ and sends a registration request containing g^{α_j} to **KC**. The latter stores these values to generate the decryption keys as detailed in [Algorithm 7](#).

Algorithm 5 Setup ($1^\lambda, n$)

- 1: Generate the master secret key $\text{msk} = (s_1, \dots, s_n) \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q^n$
 - 2: Compute the master public key $\text{mpk} \leftarrow (g^{s_1}, \dots, g^{s_n})$
 - 3: **for** each user u_j **do**
 - 4: Generate $\alpha_j \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ and sends g^{α_j} to **KC**
 - 5: **end for**
-

A user u_j encrypts a message $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ using both the master public key mpk and her private key g^{α_j} , as described in [Algorithm 6](#). To do so, she first generates a n -tuple of random integers, or noise, sampled in a subset \mathcal{S} of \mathbb{Z}_q . The specification of \mathcal{S} is detailed in [subsubsection 7.1.2](#). Then, for each entry x_i , she produces both a *helping information* for the decryption $h_i = g^{\alpha_j + r_i}$ and the encryption itself $c_i = g^{\alpha_j s_i} g^{r_i x_i}$. Eventually, she sends the ciphertext to the curator **KC**.

Algorithm 6 Enc ($\text{mpk}, \mathbf{x}, \alpha_j$)

User u_j :

- 1: Samples $r_1, \dots, r_n \xleftarrow{\$} \mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_q$
 - 2: **for** $i \in [n]$ **do**
 - 3: Compute $h_i \leftarrow g^{\alpha_j + r_i}$ and $c_i \leftarrow g^{\alpha_j s_i} g^{r_i x_i}$
 - 4: **end for**
 - 5: Sets $\mathbf{h} = (h_1, \dots, h_n)$ and $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, \dots, c_n)$
-

Consider now an external data analyst **DA** who wants to partially decrypt \mathbf{c} to know the position of $v \in \mathbb{Z}_t$ in the vector \mathbf{x} . To do so, he sends $\text{req}(j, v)$ to **KC**, where $\text{req}(j, v)$ is a request for the identifier j of u_j and a value v . The key curator runs [algorithm 7](#) and computes the decryption key $\text{dk}_{j,v} = (k_1, \dots, k_n)$, where each $k_i = g^{\alpha_j (v - s_i)}$ is constructed with the entry s_i of the secret key msk . Note that this decryption key is specific to both the user's identifier and the value v . Eventually, the curator sends back $\text{dk}_{j,v}$.

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Algorithm 7 KeyDer (msk, v, j)

- 1: **for** $i \in [n]$ **do**
 - 2: $k_i \leftarrow g^{\alpha_j (v-s_i)}$
 - 3: **end for**
 - 4: Outputs $dk_{j,v} = (k_1, \dots, k_n)$
-

With the knowledge of $dk_{j,v}$, **DA** can run [Algorithm 8](#) to decrypt partially c . For each entry of c , **DA** computes $y_i \leftarrow c_i \cdot h_i^{-v} \cdot k_i$, that is $y_i = g^{r_i (x_i - v)}$. If the parameters are chosen according to [subsubsection 7.1.2](#), $y_i = 1$ if $x_i = v$ and $y_i' \neq 1$ otherwise, with y_i' providing no information on the plaintext x_i . Therefore, **DA** obtains the expected result, and nothing more.

Algorithm 8 Dec (dk_{j,v}, c)

- 1: **for** $i \in [n]$ **do**
 - 2: Computes $y_i \leftarrow c_i \cdot h_i^{-v} \cdot k_i$; it follows:
 - 3: $y_i = g^{\alpha_j s_i + r_i x_i} g^{-v \alpha_j - v r_i} g^{\alpha_j (v-s_i)}$
 - 4: $= g^{r_i (x_i - v)}$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: Outputs $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$
-

As stated. each entry of the vector $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$ is equal to 1 *iff* q divides $r_i (x_i - v)$, where q is the modulus of the group $\mathbb{G} = \langle g \rangle$ and $r_i \in \mathcal{S}$ a noise sampled during the encryption. We claim that if \mathcal{S} is well-chosen, $y_i = 1$ *iff* $x_i = v$ hence the result. This matter is discussed in [subsubsection 7.1.2](#).

7.1.2 Sampling the Noise

Below we prove that the set $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathbb{Z}_q$ from which the noise is sampled can be adaptively chosen to guarantee the correctness of SPADE.

By theorem 1, the order of g is $q - 1$, since g is the generator of the cyclic group \mathbb{G} of order $q - 1$. Hence, $g^{r_i (x_i - v)} = 1$ *iff* $r_i (x_i - v)$ is a multiple of the order of g , that is $q - 1$. If $x_i = v$, we obviously retrieve the desired result. However, we want to guarantee that this is the only case, by making sure that $r_i (x_i - v)$ is not a non-trivial multiple of $q - 1$. To do so, we propose to choose a Fermat number $2^{2^k} + 1$, for $k \in \mathbb{N}$, as described in definition 2. In that case, $q - 1$ is a power of 2. By choosing $r \in \mathbb{Z}_q$ odd, we ensure that $q - 1$ and r_i are relatively prime, hence $q - 1$ divides $r_i (x_i - v)$ *iff* $q - 1$ divides $(x_i - v)$, that is $x_i - v = 0 \pmod{q - 1}$. If we choose $x_i, v \in \mathbb{Z}_t$ with $t < q - 1$, this equation has a single solution $x_i = v$.

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7.2 SPADE Protocol

This subsection defines the entities, system model and threat model we endow to our algorithms from [subsubsection 7.1.1](#) when building our protocols. Our first protocol relies on a pragmatic approach ([subsubsection 7.2.1](#)), where an authority manages the keys and the users simply register to the system. Commonly called SPADE, this is the protocol we refer to unless stated otherwise. Our second approach relies on a *decentralized* setup, requiring a greater involvement from the users. This particular model is defined in [subsubsection 7.2.2](#).

7.2.1 System and Threat Model

System Model The model we consider consists of three entities: (i) Key Curator (**KC**), (ii) Users (**U**) and (iii) Data Analyst (**DA**).

- **Key Curator (KC)**: The curator is a fully trusted authority responsible for the generation of the master keys msk , mpk and the storage of the private keys $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m$ of the users registered into the system. Upon request of an analyst **DA** for a value v and user u_j , it is responsible for the generation of the corresponding decryption key $\text{dk}_{j,v}$;
- **Users ($\mathbf{U} = (u_1, \dots, u_m)$)**: The users are the owners of the data. They register to the system by sending their private key α_j to **KC**. They are responsible for the encryption under mpk and α_j of these data into ciphertexts. They have to trust **KC** with their data but do not have to trust each other and do not interact with **DA**. The set of users is not fixed, and we assume that a rightful user u_{m+1} can dynamically register to the system by sending a request containing their private key α_j to **KC**;
- **Data Analyst (DA)**: The analyst is an external party who wishes to learn the number of times a value v occurs in a message \mathbf{x} . Having only access to this message as a ciphertext, **DA** sends a request to **KC** for this value and a specific user u_j , which provides the corresponding decryption key $\text{dk}_{j,v}$, hence the result of the computation.

Threat Model We assume the key curator is a fully trusted authority. Indeed, on the users side, **KC** has the capability to generate all the functional decryption keys hence has access to all the data. On the analyst side, **KC** knows the information v and j requested by **DA**. Furthermore, the latter can not check if $\text{dk}_{v,j}$ is indeed the key for the requested values v and j . Remark that *verification* methods relying on discrete logarithm exist to solve this last issue, but it is out of the scope of this deliverable. Finally, users do not have to trust each other and the data of user u_m remain safe if users u_1, \dots, u_{m-1} are malicious. The existence of the secret integer α_j not only ensures the privacy of the data but also guarantees that a user can not encrypt under the identifier of another user.

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7.2.2 Decentralized Protocol

Relying on a trusted authority permits perfect management of both the encryption and decryption keys. However, trusting a third party appears to be a big constraint for privacy-preserving protocols. To solve this problem, we propose an alternate protocol, called *decentralized*, that supports the same functionalities as the classical SPADE presented in [subsection 7.2.1](#).

The principle of a *decentralized* FE scheme is to rely only on users for the key management. As such, they are responsible for generating the public and private keys, as well as the functional decryption key. To this end, users need to be directly in communication with the analyst.

System Model The decentralized construction consists of three entities: (i) Server (S), (ii) Users (U) and (iii) Data Analyst (DA).

- Server (S): The server is responsible for the storage of the ciphertexts produced by the users. Upon request of an analyst, it can provide specific ciphertexts.
- Users ($U = (u_1, \dots, u_m)$): The users are the owners of the data. In the decentralized protocol, they are responsible for the setup of the system. They altogether generate the master public key mpk using *multi-party computation* (MPC) techniques. They encrypt their data under mpk and α_j and store the corresponding ciphertexts on S. of these data into ciphertexts. They do not have to trust the server, nor have they to trust each other. Upon request of DA, a user u_j generates the decryption key $dk_{j,v}$ corresponding to their own identifier and a value v ;
- Data Analyst (DA): The analyst is an external party who wishes to learn the number of times a value v occurs in a message x . Having only access to this message as a ciphertext, DA sends a request to a user u_j , who provides the corresponding decryption key $dk_{j,v}$, hence the result of the computation.

Remark that an external user u_{m+1} can dynamically register to the system by generating their own key α_{m+1} and encrypting their data under $g^{\alpha_{m+1}}$ and mpk , which is public. However, since the system has already been set up, she has to trust the users u_1, \dots, u_m with the master key mpk .

Threat Model We propose a threat model very similar to [subsection 7.2](#) except that there is not trusted authority anymore.

- Users ($U = (u_1, \dots, u_m)$): If the MPC generation of the master public key is done in a secure way, the users do not have to trust each other. However, if an external user u_{m+1} dynamically registers to the system after the generation of the keys, she has to trust at

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least one of the users u_1, \dots, u_m who participated in the generation of the master key. Regarding the functional decryption, we prove in [subsubsection 7.3.2](#) that a malicious data analyst, given a decryption key for a user, can not forge a decryption key for another user. It follows that the data of a user remains secure if a malicious data analyst colludes with any number of other users.

- **Data Analyst (DA):** To retrieve the result of a computation, the data analyst interacts with a user on one side and the server on the other side. He has to trust both parties with the data, as we do not provide verification feature. Thus, he has to trust that a ciphertext c is well-formed by the owner of the data, stored properly by the server, and that the decryption key $dk_{j,v}$ indeed corresponds to the value v and user j .

7.3 Security Analysis

This subsection establishes the *semantic* security of the construction given in [subsection 7.1](#) and the protocols described in [subsection 7.2](#). We recall this notion of semantic security in [Definition 6](#). First of all, we consider security against an external eavesdropper, that is, security in the sense of Public Key Encryption.

7.3.1 Semantic Security of SPADE

In this subsection, we prove that SPADE satisfies the security assumption of [Definition 6](#). We do a reduction to Multi-Users Additive ElGamal, recalled below. Note that in a setting involving multiple users, ElGamal maintains its security even when the same random value r is reused, as shown in [\[31\]](#). This differs from the traditional single-user ElGamal setup, where reusing the same randomness r would compromise security. However, in scenarios with $n > 1$ distinct key pairs, this vulnerability does not apply.

ElGamal Game The challenger generates n pairs of keys $(pk_i, sk_i) \leftarrow \text{EG.KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ and sends (pk_1, \dots, pk_n) to \mathcal{B} . The latter picks two n -tuples of messages $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$ and sends them to \mathcal{C} , who randomly picks one of them. Without a lack of generality, assume that \mathcal{C} encrypts \mathbf{x} . She produces a ciphertext $\mathbf{c} \leftarrow (g^r, c_1, \dots, c_n)$, with $c_i = (g^r, g^{x_i + r \cdot sk_i})$ to \mathcal{B} .

SPADE Game \mathcal{B} forwards $(g^{sk_1}, \dots, g^{sk_n}, g^r)$ to \mathcal{A} . Then, \mathcal{A} generates a noise $r' \xleftarrow{\$} \mathcal{S}$ according to SPADE parameters and produces the ciphertext $\mathbf{c}' \leftarrow (g^{r \cdot r'}, g^{r' \cdot x_1 + r' \cdot sk_1}, \dots, g^{r' \cdot x_n + r' \cdot sk_n})$ from \mathbf{x} . By renaming $\alpha \leftarrow r \cdot r'$ and computing $g^{\alpha + r'} \leftarrow g^\alpha g^{r'}$ she can submit $(g^{\alpha + r'}, g^{r' \cdot x_1 + \alpha \cdot sk_1}, \dots, g^{r' \cdot x_n + \alpha \cdot sk_n})$.

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Additive ElGamal Algorithms

EG.KeyGen (1^λ):

Sample $sk \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ and compute $pk \leftarrow (g^{sk})$

Return pk, sk

EG.Encrypt (pk, x):

Sample $r \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ and compute $c \leftarrow (g^r, pk^r g^x)$

Return c

EG.Decrypt (sk, c):

Compute $y \leftarrow g^{r \cdot sk + x} \cdot ((g^r)^{sk})^{-1} = g^x$

Then solve the discrete logarithm $g^x \mapsto x$

Return x

Conclusion Denote $\epsilon(\lambda)$ the advantage of \mathcal{A} on the SPADE game. Then, she has at least an advantage $\epsilon(\lambda)$ on the n instances of the ElGamal game. As it is proven to be λ -IND-CPA secure, the advantage on the n ElGamal games is negligible. It follows that $\epsilon(\lambda)$ is negligible, hence SPADE is λ -IND-CPA secure.

7.3.2 Security of the Decryption Key

Now that we have proven the IND-CPA security, we analyze the security of the leakage produced by the decryption key. We intend to prove that SPADE does not produce any additional leakage than the requested query. To this end, we need to proceed in two steps: (i) prove the indistinguishability of the decryption key, and (ii) prove the unforgeability of the decryption key. The latter step is divided into two sub-steps: the unforgeability for another value and the unforgeability for another user.

Indistinguishability of the Decryption Key We rely on the Decisional Diffie-Hellman (DDH) hard problem and assume that an eavesdropper has access to $h_i = g^{\alpha_j + r_i}$, $pk_i = g^{s_i}$ and $dk_{j,v,i} = g^{\alpha_j(s_i - v)}$. To realize the proof, we make the stronger assumption that the adversary \mathcal{ADV} has access to g^{α_j} to consider the DDH triplet $(g^{\alpha_j}, g^{s_i}, g^{\alpha_j s_i})$. With a good choice of parameters, \mathcal{ADV} can distinguish $g^{\alpha_j s_i}$ from $g^a \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{G}$ with negligible probability. Given this triplet, forging $dk_{j,v,i} \leftarrow g^{\alpha_j s_i} \cdot g^{\alpha_j - v}$ is trivial, hence the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} to distinguish $dk_{j,v,i}$ from g^a is also negligible.

Unforgeability for Another Value Consider a PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} that possess a decryption key $dk_{j,v}$ for a user u_j and a value v . We hereby prove that \mathcal{ADV} can not forge $dk_{j,w}$ for the

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same user u_j and value $v \neq w$. In this scenario, we assume that \mathcal{ADV} do not know g^{α_j} . This is a valid assumption as this identifier is known only by the fully-trusted \mathbf{KC} and by the user u_j who only leaks her own data if she colludes with \mathcal{ADV} . Besides, to retrieve g^{α_j} from a ciphertext, \mathcal{ADV} has to be able to compute g^{α_j} from $g^{\alpha_j + r_i}$ that is impossible without knowing g^{r_i} . To prove the unforgeability, we proceed by contrapose and assume that \mathcal{ADV} can forge $g^{\alpha_j (s_i - w)}$ for any v, w . In particular, they can forge it for $w = 0$ hence retrieving $g^{\alpha_j s_i}$ that is $g^{\alpha_j (s_i - v)} \cdot g^{-\alpha_j s_i}$ that is g^{α_j} . Finally, given the DDH triplet $(g^{\alpha_j}, g^{s_i}, g^a)$, \mathcal{ADV} can determine if $g^a = g^{\alpha_j (s_i - v)}$ or if $a \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}$. However, as \mathcal{ADV} can not distinguish these quantities with a non-negligible advantage, it follows that it is not able to forge $dk_{j,w}$ knowing only $dk_{j,v}$.

Unforgeability for Another User Consider a PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} that possess a decryption key $dk_{j,v}$ for a user u_j and a value v . We hereby prove that \mathcal{ADV} can not forge $dk_{k,v}$ for the same value v and user u_k , $k \neq j$. As before, we reasonably assume that \mathcal{ADV} does not know g^{α_k} . Using the same reasoning, forging $dk_{k,v}$ permits to retrieve g^{s_i} hence giving the possibility to distinguish $dk_{j,v}$ from a random value.

7.4 Evaluation

To the best of our knowledge, no other State-of-the-Art work provides a similar solution to SPADE. As such, we utilized Golang v1.21.5 to implement our SPADE scheme and assess its practicality and performance. In this part, we will examine the running time and memory usage of SPADE's different components. We will then present a real-world use case of SPADE in a client-server setting. Our experiments were conducted in a single-threaded environment, with the client operating on a laptop equipped with an Intel Core i5-9300H CPU @ 2.40GHz and 16GB memory, and the server on a PC powered by an Intel Core i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz with 64GB memory. To support open science and reproducible research, we made our implementation source code available online⁶.

7.4.1 SPADE Benchmarks

Following our four algorithms in [subsubsection 7.1.1](#), we implemented SPADE with a modular approach with different components as $\text{SPADE} = \{\text{Setup}, \text{Register}, \text{Encryption}, \text{KeyDerivation}, \text{Decryption}\}$. We separated user registration from setup to benchmark its performance precisely when we have different numbers of users. Furthermore, to get a comprehensive performance comparison for different scales of the scheme, we chose a set of benchmarks as $\text{Benchmarks} = \{\mathbf{B1}, \mathbf{B2}, \mathbf{B3}, \mathbf{B4}\}$. [Table 6](#) shows our scheme average running time and memory usage for each benchmark with the security parameter $\lambda = 128$.

⁶<https://github.com/harpocrates-project/SPADE>

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For instance, in the case of benchmark **B3**, the Setup for 1000 users with input vectors containing 50,000 elements takes 0.32 ms and requires 90 KB of memory to complete. The Register phase for 1000 users also takes 0.0066 ms and uses 1.8 KB of memory. Additionally, the Encryption, KeyDerivation, and Decryption results are for plaintext and ciphertext vectors, each containing 50,000 elements. Encrypting a single vector takes 1.02 ms and requires 275.88 KB of memory. Similarly, key derivation and decryption processes take 0.35 ms and 0.078 ms in running time and require 114.06 KB and 42.93 KB of memory, respectively.

As shown in [Figure 7](#), increasing the number of users and the size of the input vectors results in a linear increase in running time and memory usage. Also, it shows that, as expected, the most expensive step of the SPADE scheme is the Encryption, which takes less than 4 ms even for the largest benchmark and requires only 550 KB memory.

7.4.2 SPADE Use Case

As mentioned previously in [subsection 6.2](#), a user (j) can encrypt a vector of integers (\mathbf{x}) using (mpk, α_j) by utilizing SPADE scheme. This encrypted vector can then be stored on an *untrusted* server for later use. An analyst who holds the corresponding decryption key $(\text{dk}_{j,v})$ can request access to the user's vector of ciphertexts and decrypt it for further analysis. As shown in [Figure 6](#), as the result of decryption, the analyst will have a vector consisting of ones (1) for the indices that match the query value (v) and unknown values ($*$) for the remaining indices.

Figure 6 – Encryption and Decryption in SPADE

Use Case #1: Analysis of Hypnogram Data Studying sleep behavior for sleep medicine has been a focus in healthcare research for a long time [33]. The American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM) provides standardized rules to score sleep stages. The sleep stages are assigned to each 30-second epoch in the recording. The assigned epochs are visualized in a *hypnogram* file, and quantitative measures are extracted to provide more information about the sleep cycle [34]. As an application, assume that an analyst wants to extract information

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Table 6 – SPADE Benchmarks

Component	Time (ms/op)	Memory Allocations (KB/op)
B1: Number of Users=10, Vector Size=1000		
Setup	0.013474	1.798828125
Register	0.000072	0.019531251
Encryption	0.030317	5.520507813
KeyDerivation	0.006535	2.267578125
Decryption	0.002233	0.860351563
B2: Number of Users=100, Vector Size=10000		
Setup	0.072073	17.97949219
Register	0.001419	0.179687511
Encryption	0.216872	55.20800781
KeyDerivation	0.078610	22.66503906
Decryption	0.015531	8.597656252
B3: Number of Users=1000, Vector Size=50000		
Setup	0.326208	89.84765625
Register	0.006678	1.783203125
Encryption	1.024057	275.8828125
KeyDerivation	0.353401	114.0654297
Decryption	0.078852	42.97363281
B4: Number of Users=10000, Vector Size=100000		
Setup	0.65899	179.6943359
Register	0.06459	17.81347656
Encryption	3.90593	551.7138672
KeyDerivation	0.75656	226.5664063
Decryption	0.16835	85.94628906

regarding a specific sleep stage (v) by running a query, over a hypnogram file, to answer the following questions:

- Q1.** How many times does the value v appear in the hypnogram's values? which reveals the total length of the sleep stage for the value v .
- Q2.** How many changes exist where the value v jumps to the other values? that shows the changes from the sleep stage v to other sleep stages.
- Q3.** How many times does the value v appear in a sequence? indicates the length of sleep stage v before a change in sleep stage happens.

To do so, we implemented a client-server scenario utilizing the SPADE scheme with a *Server/Cu-*

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rator and two different types of clients, namely, *User*, and *Analyst*. The trusted entity (*Curator*) generates the system parameters and master public/private keys. Then, it shares the public parameters with all other entities; it transfers the keys to users and takes care of the user's registration phase. The *user* encrypts a hypnogram file and sends it to an untrusted server to be stored. An *analyst* with the corresponding decryption key for value v requests access to the user's encrypted hypnogram to partially decrypt the ciphertexts and extract the information for sleep stage v .

Storage Costs. In our experiments, we used a dataset containing 590 hypnogram files, each with 1000 elements ranging from 1 to 10, indicating different sleep stages. As shown in Table 7, the storage cost for saving a single hypnogram file is around 2 KB, which then increases up to 80.3 KB after being encrypted by SPADE. Likewise, the entire hypnogram dataset requires 1180 KB to be stored, whereas the storage cost for all encrypted hypnograms on the server is 43500 KB. Therefore, the SPADE's storage cost increases by almost $40\times$ for every 1 KB of data for the security parameter $\lambda = 128$.

Table 7 – Storage Costs

Description	Size (KB)
Single Plain Hypnogram	2
Single Encrypted Hypnogram	80.29
Plain Hypnograms	1180
Encrypted Hypnograms	43500

Running Time & Communication Costs. We conducted the experiments using a 1 GB/s LAN connection. On the user side, the process involves sending a request for public parameters $\{q, g, mpk\}$, encrypting hypnogram data, and sending a message that contained $\{id, g^{\alpha id}, c_{id}\}$ to the server. Each user took approximately 36 ms to complete the process, requiring 53 KB of network bandwidth. Similarly, the analyst sends a request to the server for public parameters. Then, the analyst sends a request to the server including the user identifier and the sleep stage value as $\{id, v\}$, respectively. In response, the analyst receives decryption keys and the user's encrypted hypnogram, represented as $\{dk_{id,v}, c_{id}\}$, respectively. The analyst can then partially decrypt the user's hypnogram. It takes approximately 16 ms for each analyst to complete the process, and it requires 53 KB of network bandwidth.

Table 8 – Running Time & Communication Costs

Client	Running Time (ms)	Communication (KB)
User	35.59	52.77
Analyst	15.75	52.71

Figure 7 – Running Time per Benchmark

Figure 8 – Memory Usage per Benchmark

8 Function Encryption Construction 3: Forward and Function Private

8.1 System Model

In this subsection, we present the parties of our construction. In particular, we assume the existence of the three following entities:

Data Owner: The data owner (u_i) keeps a list of unique identifiers for all possible functions supported by the underlying MIFE scheme. In addition to that, u_i is responsible for encrypting her data and creating the necessary indexes. In particular, u_i first parses her data locally before outsourcing it to the CSP. During this process, she generates the following three indexes:

- \mathcal{D} – a dictionary containing mappings between function identifiers and ciphertexts that can be given as input to each function.
- $\text{No.Runs}[f]$ which contains mappings between the unique identifier of each function f , and the number of times f has already been executed.
- $\text{No.Inputs}[f]$ which consists of mappings between function identifiers and the number of inputs for each function f .

$\text{No.Runs}[f]$ and $\text{No.Inputs}[f]$ are kept locally on u_i 's side, while \mathcal{D} is outsourced to the CSP.

Cloud Service Provider (CSP) The CSP storage will consist of the ciphertexts as well as the dictionary \mathcal{D} . Each \mathcal{D} entry is encrypted under a different temporary key tk_f . Thus, given tk_f and the number of inputs for a function f , the CSP can recover all the ciphertexts that will be

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given as input to the MIFE decryption algorithm.

Secure Component (SC): SC is a TEE-protected component that resides in the CSP. We assume that during the deployment phase, SC receives a series of function descriptions, along with their executables. SC is triggered by the CSP, upon receiving a query for a function by a user u_i . SC is responsible for running the MIFE decryption algorithm upon receiving a collection of ciphertexts from the CSP, a functional decryption key sk_f for a function f and the unique identifier of f . SC has the following properties:

Attestation We assume that the TEE offers the feature of attestation. In particular, during attestation, SC generates an attestation report that can be verified by any party. The report is signed with a private key and hence, anyone holding the public key will be in position to verify it.

Sealing When data are stored in untrusted memory, they are encrypted with a key known only to SC. Sealed data can be recovered even if SC is required to restart.

8.2 Formal Construction

For the needs of our construction, we assume the existence of the following building blocks:

1. A key-private MIFE scheme that fulfils the property of message privacy.
2. A first and second pre-image resistant hash function H .
3. A pseudorandom function $G : \{0, 1\}^\lambda \times \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^*$
4. An IND-CCA2 secure public-key cryptosystem PKE such that: $\text{PKE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$.
5. An EUF-CMA secure signature scheme $S = (\text{sign}, \text{ver})$.
6. A synchronized clock between all the parties.

Note here, that we only require the MIFE scheme to be message-private. Hence, our construction can be applied to any message-private MIFE scheme, to further enhance it with the property of function-privacy.

8.2.1 Secure Hardware Formalization

During the execution of the protocol, we assume the existence of a secure hardware (SHW) component SC. In the beginning, SHW.Setup runs to generate a public/secret key pair. SC is then initialized, by loading a program Q and producing an identifier SC. This is done by running

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SHW.Load. After the initialization of SC, HW.Run is executed with different inputs. Finally, SC runs SHW.Run&Report to generate a signed attestation report.

- SHW.Setup(1^λ): Takes an input a security parameter λ and produces a public/secret key pair (pk_{rpt}, sk_{rpt}) , used to sign and verify reports.
- SHW.Load(Q): Takes as input a program Q . A private region of memory, dedicated to execute Q , is allocated. Moreover, an identifier id is created that will be used to identify this particular region of memory.
- SHW.Run(SC, in): Takes as input an identifier id and some input in . It then runs the program in the memory region specified by id , with in as input.
- SHW.Run&Report(id, in): Takes as input an identifier id and some input in and outputs an attestation report rpt signed with sk_{rpt} . The report is verifiable by any party (local or remote) holding the corresponding public key pk_{rpt} .

8.2.2 Forward and Function Private MIFE

We are now ready to proceed with the formal definition of FFP (Forward and Function Private). Our construction consists of four polynomial time algorithms such that $FFP = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Setup}, \text{Query}, \text{Add})$.

FFP.KeyGen: During the execution of KeyGen, the data owner invokes MIFE.Setup to generate a master secret key msk for the message-private MIFE scheme. Apart from that, a key K_G for a PRF G is generated.

FFP.Setup: This is a two-party protocol between a data owner u_i and the CSP. The protocol is initiated by u_i who wishes to encrypt her data. First, u_i locally creates mappings between a sequence of data (x_1, \dots, x_n) and function descriptions. These mappings, simply specify the proper inputs for each function f_i . As a next step, u_i computes a temporary key for each function as $tk_f = G(K_G, f || \text{No.Runs}[f])$. This key will allow u_i to start building the dictionary \mathcal{D} . In particular, for each (x_i, f_i) pair, u_i first invokes MIFE.Enc to encrypt x_i , resulting in a ciphertext c_i , and then further masks the function description as $mf_i = H(tk_f || \text{No.Inputs}[f])$. Then, the pair $\{c_i, mf_i\}$ is added to the dictionary \mathcal{D} . The data owner u_i repeats these steps for all $x_i \in (x_1, \dots, x_n)$. Finally, \mathcal{D} is outsourced to the CSP via $m_1 = \langle t_1, \mathcal{D}, \sigma_{u_i}(h(t_1 || \mathcal{D})) \rangle$ to the CSP, where t_1 is a timestamp and σ_{u_i} denotes the signature of u_i . Upon reception, the CSP can verify u_i 's signature, the freshness and the integrity of the m_1 . FFP.Setup is presented in detail in [Algorithm 9](#).

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Algorithm 9 FFP.Setup

Data Owner:

- 1:
- 2: **for all** (x_i, f_i) pairs **do**
- 3: **if** No.Inputs[f_i] = null **then**
- 4: No.Inputs[f_i] = 0
- 5: **end if**
- 6: **if** No.Runs[f_i] = null **then**
- 7: No.Runs[f_i] = 0
- 8: **end if**
- 9: No.Inputs[f_i] ++
- 10: $tk_{f_i} = G(K_G, f_i || \text{No.Inputs}[f_i])$ ▷ temporary key for f_i
- 11: $mf_i = h(tk_{f_i} || \text{No.Inputs}[f_i])$ ▷ mask the function
- 12: $c_i = \text{MIFE.Enc}(\text{msk}, x_i)$
- 13: Add the (c_i, mf_i) pair into \mathcal{D}
- 14: **end for**
- 15: Outsource \mathcal{D} to the CSP via $m_1 = \langle t_1, \mathcal{D}, \sigma_{u_i}(h(t_1 || \mathcal{D})) \rangle$
- 16: Store No.Inputs[f] and No.Runs[f] locally

FFP.Add: This is a two-party protocol between u_i and the CSP. The procedure is identical to that of FFP.Setup but is applied to only one (x_i, f_i) pair. To add the pair to the dictionary \mathcal{D} , u_i generates an add token as $\tau_a(x_i, f_i) = (c_i, mf_i)$, where c_i and mf_i are generated as discussed in FFP.Setup. Finally, u_i sends $m_2 = \langle t_2, (c_i, mf_i), \sigma_{u_i}(h(t_2 || (c_i, mf_i))) \rangle$ to the CSP. We omit a formal description as it is identical to that of [Algorithm 9](#), without the for loop in line 1.

FFP.Query: This is a three-party protocol between u_i , the CSP and SC. Assume now that u_i wishes to run a function $f \in \mathcal{F}$, on the encrypted data (x_1, \dots, x_n) . To do so, u_i first needs to generate a query token for the function f by following a series of steps:

Step 1. Invokes MIFE.KeyGen to generate a decryption key sk_f .

Step 2. Retrieves the No.Runs[f] and No.Inputs[f] values from her local indexes and calculates the masked version of the function description as described in FFP.Setup.

Step 3. Now, u_i is required to calculate the updated value of mf . To do so, increments the No.Runs[f] values by one, and computes a new temporary key tk_f . Based on this temporary key, u_i calculates the new masked version of f , mf' .

After completing these steps, u_i can simply calculate the query token $\tau_q(f) = (sk_f || mf_i || \text{No.Inputs}[f] || mf' || h(f || \text{No.Runs}[f]))$ which is also forwarded to the CSP via $m_3 = \langle t_3, \text{Enc}_{pk_{SC}}(sk_f), h(f || \text{No.Inputs}[f]), \tau_q(f), \sigma_{u_i}(h') \rangle$ where h' is the following hash: $h(t_3 || \text{Enc}_{pk_{SC}}(sk_f) || h(f || \text{No.Inputs}[f]) || \tau_q(f))$. Upon reception, the CSP uses $\tau_q(f)$ to locate all ciphertexts (c_1, \dots, c_n) that can be given as input to f_i and sends them to SC along with sk_f and $h(f || \text{No.Runs}[f])$

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via $m_4 = \langle t_4, Res, m_3, \sigma_{CSP}(h(t_4, Res, m_3)) \rangle$. Apart from that, the CSP removes all the current masked versions of f , and replaces them with the ones in \mathcal{L} . SC, knowing the hash of the unique id of the executable corresponding to the function f , can locate which is the proper executable. As a result, SC invokes MIFE.Dec and outputs $out = f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ which is sent back to u_i to the CSP via $m_5 = \langle t_5, out, \sigma_{SC}(h(t_5||out)) \rangle$. Finally, the CSP forwards m_5 to u_i . FFP.Query is formally presented in [Algorithm 10](#).

Algorithm 10 Query

Data Owner:

- 1: $sk_f \leftarrow \text{MIFE.KeyGen}(skf, f)$ ▷ generate the decryption key
- 2: $tk_f = G(K_G, f || \text{No.Runs}[f])$
- 3: $mf' = h(tk_f || \text{No.Inputs}[f])$
- 4: $\text{No.Runs}[f] + +$
- 5: $tk'_f = G(K_G, f || \text{No.Runs}[f])$
- 6: $mf'_i = h(tk'_f || \text{No.Inputs}[f])$
- 7: $\tau_q(f) = (sk_f, mf, \text{No.Inputs}[f], mf', h(f || \text{No.Runs}[f]))$
- 8: Send m_3 to the CSP

CSP:

- 9: $Res = \{\}$
- 10: **for** $i = 1$ **to** $i = \ell$ **do** ▷ $\text{No.Inputs}[f] = \ell$
- 11: $c_i = \mathcal{D}(mf, :)$ ▷ find the input ciphertext based on the masked description
- 12: $Res = Res \cup c_i$
- 13: Replace mf with mf'
- 14: **end for**
- 15: Send $m_4 = \langle t_4, Res, m_3, \sigma_{CSP}(h(t_4, Res, m_3)) \rangle$ to SC

SC:

- 16: Find which executable corresponds to the function description
- 17: Update the stored function description by incrementing No.runs by one
- 18: Run $\text{MIFE.Dec}(sk_f, c_1, \dots, c_\ell)$
- 19: Output $out = f(x_1, \dots, x_\ell)$
- 20: Send $m_5 = \langle t_5, out, \sigma_{SC}(h(t_5||out)) \rangle$ to the CSP

CSP:

- 21: Forward m_5 to the Data Owner
-

8.2.3 Leakage Functions

Based on our formal construction, we can now formally quantify the total leakage by providing a concrete definition of the leakage function $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}_{keygen}, \mathcal{L}_{setup}, \mathcal{L}_{query}, \mathcal{L}_{add})$. This is an essential part of our work as this function will be explicitly used during the proof of security in the next subsection. For each step, the leakage function is defined as follows:

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- $\mathcal{L}_{keygen} = \lambda$. The leakage function associated with FFP.KeyGen is restricted to the length of the generated keys.
- $\mathcal{L}_{setup} = (N, m)$, where N is the total number of mappings in \mathcal{D} , and m is the total number of ciphertexts. The leakage function associated with the FFP.Setup leaks the size of \mathcal{D} , and the number of ciphertexts.
- $\mathcal{L}_{query} = (qp[t], ap, |sk_f|, |h_{out}|, out)$. The leakage function associated with FFP.Query leaks the query and access patterns, the size of the functional key, the outputs of the hash function h and the output $out = f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$.
- $\mathcal{L}_{add} = (|c_i|, |f_i|)$. The leakage function associated with FFP.Add leaks the sizes of the added ciphertext and the function description.

Moreover, note that even if we use a different temporary key tk_f for each query, the query pattern is still leaked since the CSP can easily guess that newly re-keyed entries correspond to the input of the queried function. The temporary keys are not used to hide the query pattern, but to provide forward privacy as per [Definition 15](#).

8.2.4 Secure Component Analysis

While in the previous subsection, we provided a detailed presentation of FFP, our approach was agnostic to the TEE-enabled component. In this subsection, we aim to formalize the behaviour of SC by providing an analysis of the programs that are executed by SC. This will help us better understand the role of SC and, subsequently, formalize its security properties. SC is initialized during FFP.Setup as follows: **Initialization:** SC is initialized by generating a public/secret and signing/verification key pairs. To do so, a program Q^{init} is loaded:

Q^{init} :

- On input (“initialize”, 1^λ):
 1. Run $(pk_{SC}, sk_{SC}) \leftarrow \text{PKE.KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$.
 2. Publish pk .Run $SC \leftarrow \text{SHW.Load}(Q^{init})$.

Run: SC is required to run during the execution of FFP.Query to produce an output out . Moreover, SC signs out since it also needs to generate an attestation report. This is done by a program Q^{run} as follows:

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Q^{run} :

- On input (“run”, m_4):
 1. Open m_4 ; Verify the freshness, the integrity of the message and the signature of the CSP; If the verification fails, output \perp .
 2. Compute $sk_f = \text{Dec}(sk_{SC}, \text{Enc}_{sk_{SC}}(sk_f))$.
 3. Compute and output m_5
- Run $m_5 \leftarrow \text{SHW.Run}(SC, (\text{“run”}, m_4))$ and then:
 $\text{rpt} \leftarrow \text{SHW.Run\&Report}(SC, (\text{“run”}, m_4))$

8.3 A Novel Adversarial Model

To capture our new notion of security in FE we rely on the real experiment against ideal experiment formalization. In particular, in the real experiment the adversary \mathcal{ADV} observes the algorithms being executed honestly, while in the ideal experiment a simulator \mathcal{S} simulates the functionalities based on explicit leakage. The leakage is formalized by a function \mathcal{L} such that $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}_{\text{keygen}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{setup}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{query}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{add}})$ where each component corresponds to the leakage associated with the key generation, setup, query and addition algorithms. The idea is the following: \mathcal{ADV} has full control of the client. Thus, she can trigger any operation. \mathcal{ADV} issues a polynomial number of queries, and for each query she records the output. The scheme is said to be \mathcal{L} -adaptively secure if \mathcal{ADV} cannot distinguish between the real and the ideal experiments.

Definition 14. (*\mathcal{L} -Adaptive Security*) Let $\text{FFP} = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Setup}, \text{Query}, \text{Add})$ be as defined in subsection 8.2. Moreover, let $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}_{\text{keygen}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{setup}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{query}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{add}})$ be the leakage function of FFP. We consider the following experiments between an adversary \mathcal{ADV} and a challenger \mathcal{C} :

$\text{Real}_{\mathcal{ADV}}(\lambda)$

\mathcal{ADV} outputs a set of inputs for various functions from a rich function family \mathcal{F} . \mathcal{C} generates a key msk , and runs FFP.Setup . \mathcal{ADV} then makes a polynomial number of adaptive queries $q = \{f, (x_1, f_1)\}$. For each q , she receives back either a query token for f , $\tau_q(f)$, or an add token $\tau_a(x_1, f_1)$ for the pair (x_1, f_1) . Finally, \mathcal{ADV} outputs a bit b .

$\text{Ideal}_{\mathcal{ADV}, \mathcal{S}}(\lambda)$

\mathcal{ADV} outputs a set of inputs for various functions from a rich function family \mathcal{F} . \mathcal{S} gets $\mathcal{L}_{\text{setup}}$ to simulate Setup . $q = \{f, (x_1, f_1)\}$. For each q , \mathcal{S} is given $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}_{\text{keygen}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{setup}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{add}}, \mathcal{L}_{\text{query}})$. \mathcal{S} then simulates the dictionary, the tokens and, in the case of addition, a ciphertext. Finally, \mathcal{ADV} outputs a bit b .

We say that FFP is secure if $\forall \text{PPT } \mathcal{ADV}, \exists \mathcal{S}$ such that:

$$|\Pr[(\text{Real}_{\mathcal{ADV}}) = 1] - \Pr[(\text{Ideal}_{\mathcal{ADV}, \mathcal{S}}) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (16)$$

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Moreover, we further require that from the CSP's point of view, newly added (x_i, f_i) pairs do not leak any information about past queries. This property, makes adaptive attacks a lot less effective [35]. This requirement, forces us to define the property of *Forward Privacy* for FE schemes. Informally, we will say that a scheme is said to be *forward private* if for all file insertions that take place after the successful execution of the Setup algorithm, the leakage is limited to the sizes of the function's input and the function's description. More formally:

Definition 15 (Forward Privacy). *An \mathcal{L} -adaptively FFP scheme is forward private iff the leakage function \mathcal{L}_{Add} can be written as:*

$$\mathcal{L}_{add}(x_i, f_i) = (|x_i|, |f_i|) \quad (17)$$

For the following two definitions, let us assume that the data owner has already issued t queries $\mathcal{Q} = \{q_1, \dots, q_t\}$, up to time t .

Definition 16 (Query Pattern). *The query pattern is defined to be a vector QP that shows which query each function corresponds to. For example, $SP[t] = f_\kappa$ means that a query for the function f_κ was issued at time t .*

Definition 17 (Access Pattern). *We define the Access Pattern to be the set of all ciphertexts that can be given as input to a function f at time t . The set is denoted by $AP_{f,t}$.*

8.4 Security Analysis

We are now ready to prove the security of our construction against the threat model defined in [subsection 8.3](#). To do so, we need to prove the existence of a simulator \mathcal{S} , that given the leakage function \mathcal{L} , simulates a perfect view for an adversary \mathcal{ADV} with all but a negligible probability. Before we proceed with the formal proof of security, we present a high-level overview:

Proof Sketch: We will rely on a constructive proof in the sense that we will prove the existence of \mathcal{S} , by constructing it. This will be achieved through a hybrid argument. More precisely, we will design five hybrids $\mathcal{H}_0, \mathcal{H}_1, \mathcal{H}_2, \mathcal{H}_3$ and \mathcal{H}_4 such that \mathcal{H}_0 is the real experiment and \mathcal{H}_4 the ideal one, as they were defined in [subsection 8.3](#). Each hybrid \mathcal{H}_i , will be constructed by replacing a real functionality with a simulated one given the corresponding leakage function \mathcal{L}_i . Our goal is to prove that no PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} will be able to distinguish between two consecutive hybrids $\mathcal{H}_i, \mathcal{H}_{i+1}$. The hybrids are illustrated in [Table 9](#).

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Table 9 – Hybrid Description

Hybrid	Description
\mathcal{H}_0	This is the real experiment
\mathcal{H}_1	Simulate FFP.KeyGen given \mathcal{L}_{keygen}
\mathcal{H}_2	Simulate FFP.Setup given \mathcal{L}_{setup}
\mathcal{H}_3	Simulate FFP.Add given \mathcal{L}_{add}
\mathcal{H}_4	This is the ideal experiment

It is important to note that simulation-based security definitions for FE already exist [36, 4]. However, in contrast with these works, we address a different problem, as we are more interested in proving the security of a general framework and not that of a FE scheme.

Theorem 5. *Let MIFE be a message-private multi-input functional encryption scheme. Moreover, let G be a secure pseudorandom function and h a first and second pre-image resistant hash function. Then FFP = (KeyGen, Setup, Query, Add), with corresponding leakage function $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}_{keygen}, \mathcal{L}_{setup}, \mathcal{L}_{query}, \mathcal{L}_{add})$ is \mathcal{L} -adaptively secure as per Definition 14.*

Proof. We construct a simulator \mathcal{S} that simulates the real functionality in such a way that no PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} can distinguish between the real and ideal worlds. Note here that \mathcal{ADV} only expects an output from FFP.Query and in this case, apart from simulating the search token, \mathcal{S} also needs to simulate the process executed by SC. \mathcal{S} is given as input $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}_{keygen}, \mathcal{L}_{setup}, \mathcal{L}_{query}, \mathcal{L}_{add})$.

In a pre-processing phase, \mathcal{S} runs SHW.Setup(1^λ) and records (pk_{rpt}, sk_{rpt}) generated during the process.

Hybrid 0 (\mathcal{H}_0) This is the real world.

Hybrid 1 (\mathcal{H}_1) Like \mathcal{H}_0 , but instead of FFP.KeyGen, \mathcal{S} gets as input \mathcal{L}_{keygen} and simulates the real world.

Claim. \mathcal{H}_0 is computationally indistinguishable from \mathcal{H}_1 .

The proof of Claim 8.4 is straightforward as \mathcal{ADV} does not have access to any key generated during this phase. Hence, we can safely assume that:

$$|Pr[(\mathcal{H}_0) = 1] - Pr[(\mathcal{H}_1) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (18)$$

Hybrid 2 (\mathcal{H}_2) Like \mathcal{H}_1 , but instead of FFP.Setup, \mathcal{S} gets as input \mathcal{L}_{setup} and simulates the real

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world.

Claim. \mathcal{H}_1 is computationally indistinguishable from \mathcal{H}_2 .

Proof. \mathcal{S} is given $\mathcal{L}_{setup} = (N, m)$ and proceeds as shown in Algorithm 11.

Algorithm 11 Setup Simulation

```
1: procedure  $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}_{setup})$ 
2:    $k \leftarrow \text{MIFE.KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ 
3:   for  $i = 1$  to  $i = N$  do
4:     Output a simulated masked function description  $sim_{f_i}$ 
5:     Simulate the ciphertexts as  $sim_{c_i} \leftarrow \text{MIFE.Enc}(k, x_j)$ 
6:     Store all  $(sim_{f_i}, sim_{c_i})$  in a dictionary  $\mathcal{D}_S$ 
7:   end for
8:   Create a dictionary  $\text{Keys}$  to store the last temporary key for each function query.
9:   Create a dictionary  $\mathcal{O}$  to reply to random oracle queries.
10:  Create a dictionary  $\text{DecKeys}$  to store the functional decryption keys for different functions.
11:  Output  $\mathcal{D}_S$ 
12: end procedure
```

Since $\mathcal{L}_{setup} = (N, m)$, \mathcal{S} knows exactly both the size of the dictionary \mathcal{D} , as well as the number of resulted ciphertexts. Moreover, as we can assume the hash function h and the security parameter λ to be publicly known, then \mathcal{S} knows the exact sizes of the real masked functions m_{f_i} and ciphertexts c_i . Hence it is straightforward to generate simulations of both the masked functions sim_{f_i} and the ciphertexts sim_{c_i} of correct sizes. What remains to be done, is show that \mathcal{ADV} cannot distinguish between an encryption of a plaintext x_i and that of a random x_j such that $f(x_i) = f(x_j)$ and $|x_i| = |x_j|$. However, recall that we have assumed that MIFE is message-private, which means that an adversary cannot distinguish between the encryptions of two messages x_i and x_j even if she possess functional decryption keys. Hence, we conclude that the encryption of a x_i and that of a x_j such that $f(x_i) = f(x_j)$ are computationally indistinguishable and hence:

$$|Pr[(\mathcal{H}_0) = 1] - Pr[(\mathcal{H}_1) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (19)$$

□

Hybrid 3 (\mathcal{H}_3) Like \mathcal{H}_2 , but instead of FFP.Add , \mathcal{S} gets as input \mathcal{L}_{add} and simulates the real world.

Claim. \mathcal{H}_2 is computationally indistinguishable from \mathcal{H}_3 .

Proof. \mathcal{S} is given as input \mathcal{L}_{add} and proceeds as shown in Algorithm 12:

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Algorithm 12 Addition Simulation

1: **procedure** $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}_{add})$
2: $L = \{\}$
3: $sim_{c_i} \leftarrow \text{MIFE.Enc}(k, x_j)$ for a random x_j such that $f(x_i) = f(x_j)$
4: Simulate a (sim_{f_i}, sim_{c_i}) pair
5: Output $\tau_\alpha = (c_i, m_{f_i})$
6: **end procedure**

Since $\mathcal{L}_{add} = |c_i|, |f_i|$, \mathcal{S} can easily generate a simulated ciphertext sim_{c_i} of the correct size. Similarly, \mathcal{S} generates correctly a simulated masked function description of the correct size. Finally, once again, the message-privacy property of the MIFE scheme, ensures us that \mathcal{ADV} cannot distinguish between the encryptions of an actual plaintext x_i , and that of a random x_j such that $f(x_i) = f(x_j)$. As a result:

$$|Pr[(\mathcal{H}_2) = 1] - Pr[(\mathcal{H}_3) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (20)$$

Moreover, note that since we successfully simulated FFP.Add given only the leakage function \mathcal{L}_{add} , we also proved that FFP preserves our newly defined property of forward privacy in functional encryption. \square

Hybrid 4 (\mathcal{H}_4) Like \mathcal{H}_3 , but instead of FFP.Query, \mathcal{S} gets as input \mathcal{L}_{query} and simulates the real world.

Claim. \mathcal{H}_2 is computationally indistinguishable from \mathcal{H}_3 .

Proof. Proving [Equation 8.4](#) is trickier than the previous ones as addition operations affect query operations. Hence, \mathcal{S} needs to be constructed in such a way that it keeps track of all the additions in order to respond consistently to \mathcal{ADV} . To achieve this, we need to design three more dictionaries:

- $\text{Keys}[f]$, that keeps track of the last temporary key that was used for the function f .
- $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_f][i], i \in \{0, 1\}$, which serves as a random oracle responsible to provide \mathcal{ADV} with consistent query tokens. More precisely, $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_f][0]$ stores the simulated masked function, while $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_f]$ stores the simulated ciphertext that is required to recover c_i .
- DecKeys , that keeps track of the functional decryption key for each function f .

\mathcal{S} is given \mathcal{L}_{query} and simulates the query tokens as shown in [Algorithm 13](#).

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Algorithm 13 Query Simulation

```
1: procedure  $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}_{query})$ 
2:    $\ell$ : Total number of inputs for the function  $f_i$ 
3:   if  $\text{Keys}[f_i] = \text{null}$  then
4:      $\text{tk}_{f_i} \leftarrow \{0, 1\}^\lambda$ 
5:   end if
6:    $\text{tk}_{f_i} = \text{Keys}[f_i]$ 
7:   if  $\text{DecKeys}[f] = \text{null}$  then
8:      $\text{sk}_f \leftarrow \{0, 1\}^\lambda$ 
9:   end if
10:   $\text{sk}_f = \text{DecKeys}[f_i]$ 
11:  for  $i = 1$  to  $i = \ell$  do
12:    if  $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_{f_i}] = \text{null}$  then
13:      if  $x_i$  is added after Setup then
14:        Pick a  $(x_i, (sim_{mf_i}, sim_{ci}))$  pair
15:      else
16:        Pick a  $(sim_{mf_i}, sim_{ci})$  pair
17:      end if
18:       $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_{f_i}][0] = sim_{mf_i}$ 
19:       $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_{f_i}][1] = sim_{ci} \oplus x_i$ 
20:    else
21:       $sim_{mf_i} = \mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_{f_i}][0]$ 
22:       $sim_{ci} = \mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_{f_i}][1]$ 
23:    end if
24:    Delete either  $(sim_{mf_i}, sim_{ci})$  or  $(x_i, (sim_{mf_i}, sim_{ci}))$  from  $\mathcal{D}_S$ .
25:  end for
26:   $\text{NewMap} = \{\}$ 
27:   $\text{tk}_{f_i}' \leftarrow \{0, 1\}^\lambda$ 
28:   $\text{Keys}[f_i] = \text{tk}_{f_i}'$ 
29:  for  $i = 1$  to  $\ell$  do
30:    Simulate a novel  $(sim_{mf_i}, sim_{ci})$  pair and add it into  $\mathcal{D}$ 
31:     $\text{NewMap} = \text{NewMap} \cup ((sim_{mf_i}, sim_{ci}))$ 
32:     $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_{f_i}'][0] = sim_{mf_i}$ 
33:     $\mathcal{O}[\text{tk}_{f_i}'][1] = sim_{ci}$ 
34:  end for
35:  output  $\tau_q(f) = (\text{sk}_f || sim_{mf} || \ell || \text{NewMap})$ 
36: end procedure
```

From the description of [Algorithm 13](#), it is clear that the simulated query token has exactly the same size and format with the real one and hence, no PPT adversary can distinguish between them. What remains to be done is for \mathcal{S} to simulate SC and its response. To do so, \mathcal{S} first

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generates a simulated m'_4 message by replacing the components of the actual m_4 with the simulated ones where $m_4 =$. Having showed that \mathcal{S} can successfully simulate the query token given \mathcal{L}_{query} , generating m'_4 is straightforward. As a result, what we need to show is that:

$$|Pr[(SHW.Run(SC, ("run", m_4))) = 1] - Pr[(SHW.Run(SC, ("run", m'_4))) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (21)$$

and then, for the attestation:

$$|Pr[(SHW.Run\&Report(SC, ("run", m_4))) = 1] - Pr[(SHW.Run\&Report(SC, ("run", m'_4))) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (22)$$

Proving inequalities 21 and 22, requires to prove that given m'_4 , \mathcal{S} can output a simulated m'_5 which is computationally indistinguishable from m_5 . Recall that $m_5 = \langle t_5, \text{out}, \sigma_{SC}(h(t_5|\text{out})) \rangle$. However, since $\text{out} \in \mathcal{L}_{query}$ and \mathcal{S} already possess (sk_{rpt}) , it is straightforward to output a message m'_5 identical to m_5 , and in this case, we have that:

$$|Pr[(SHW.Run(SC, ("run", m_4))) = 1] - Pr[(SHW.Run(SC, ("run", m'_4))) = 1]| = 0 \quad (23)$$

and

$$|Pr[(SHW.Run\&Report(SC, ("run", m_4))) = 1] - Pr[(SHW.Run\&Report(SC, ("run", m'_4))) = 1]| = 0 \quad (24)$$

Moreover, tampering with the report that is produced as part of SHW.Run\&Report, implies that \mathcal{ADV} can forge SC's signature, which can only happen with negligible probability.

Hence, we conclude that:

$$|Pr[(\mathcal{H}_3) = 1] - Pr[(\mathcal{H}_4) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (25)$$

□

By combining inequalities 18-25, and using the triangle inequality and the fact that the finite

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sum of negligible functions is still negligible, we conclude that:

$$|Pr[(\mathcal{H}_0) = 1] - Pr[(\mathcal{H}_4) = 1]| \leq \text{negl}(\lambda) \quad (26)$$

Note that the description of the function is kept hidden and not used at all during the entire simulation. This result is quite remarkable as it signifies that we can simulate a perfect view of the real world, by keeping the description of the function hidden. Hence, starting with any private key MIFE scheme that is also message-private, FFP can further enhance it with the properties of forward and function privacy.

□

Side-Channel Attacks: Recent works [37, 38] have shown that TEEs are vulnerable to software attacks. However, according to [39], these attacks can be prevented if the programs running in the TEE are data-oblivious. Thus, leakage can be avoided if the programs do not have memory access patterns or control flow branches that depend on the values of sensitive data.

8.5 Evaluation

8.5.1 Theoretical Evaluation

Computational Cost Despite having a larger setup time than a generic MIFE scheme, FFP is still characterized by its efficiency as it solves various complex problems by achieving optimal query and addition costs. More precisely, a generic MIFE scheme would have a setup time of $O(n)$ where n is the total number of plaintexts to be encrypted, while FFP has a setup time of $O(N)$, where N is the total number of (x_i, f_i) pairs. Apart from that, the query cost is $O(\ell)$, where ℓ is the number of the resulted ciphertexts. This solution is superior to a naive one in which the whole dictionary would be scanned and the total complexity would be $O(N)$. Reducing the running time from $O(N)$, to $O(\ell)$ is achieved by embedding the $\text{No.Inputs}[f_i]$ into the query token. Hence, the CSP is not required to run a for loop N times (i.e. for the whole dictionary). Apart from that, FFP is also parallelizable - each query can be reduced to locating ℓ independent hashes in \mathcal{D} . Thus, by distributing the load to p processors, we get a total cost of $O(\ell/p)$.

Storage Cost Concerning the three indexes, we get that the size of \mathcal{D} , which is also the biggest index, is $O(N)$. The two indices that are stored locally on the user's side (i.e. $\text{No.Runs}[f]$ and $\text{No.Inputs}[f]$) are $O(m)$ each, where $m = |\mathcal{F}|$. Assuming that \mathcal{F} is an extremely rich family of

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functions such that $\mathcal{F} = 1000$, and knowing that the average size of an integer is about 4 bytes, and the unique identifier of each function (i.e. the function description) is approximately 10 bytes, the total size required for the three indexes is: $1 \times 10^3 \times (10 + 4 + 10 + 4) = 1 \times 10^3 \times 28 = 28 \times 10^3 \text{B} = 28\text{KB}$. Hence, we conclude the user, can easily store the two indexes even on a smartphone.

8.5.2 Experimental Results

Our experiments mainly focused on analyzing the FFP's performance. To do so, we implemented FFP in Python 3.9.4 using the `pandas`, `hashlib` and `numpy` libraries. At the time of writing this document, there are no other generic function privacy frameworks to compare our work to. To test the FFP's overall performance we used function families of different sizes, where each function had a different number of possible inputs. Our experiments focused on three main aspects: (1) Indexing, (2) Retrieving the inputs of a specific function and (3) Updating all the indexes by adding one new function in the function family. The indexes were implemented as `pandas` dataframes that are very common in data analysis. Additionally, as we wanted to evaluate the performance of FFP under realistic conditions, we decided to run our experiments on a commodity laptop. All experiments were executed on a Lenovo T470p with 2.81 GHz Intel Core i7 and 32GB RAM running Windows 10, 64-bit. The reason for measuring the FFP's performance on such a machine and not on a powerful desktop – as is the common practice – was that in a practical scenario, the most demanding processes (e.g. the creation of the dictionaries) take place on a user's machine. Hence, conducting the experiments on a powerful machine would have resulted in a set of non-realistic measurements. Each experiment was executed 100 times, and the average time was calculated.

Our Dataset: As already mentioned throughout the deliverable, FE schemes currently suffer from the absence of rich function families that could support a large number of different functions. However, to test the efficiency of our construction under the most demanding cases, we assumed the existence of such families and took it a step further by including in our experiments hypothetical function families supporting up to 10,000 functions. Since FFP can work with any message-private MIFE scheme, measuring the encryption and decryption times is *not* applicable in our case. To this end, in our evaluation, we treat the function inputs as already encrypted elements of a large finite field.

Indexing: The first part of our experiments consisted of measuring the FFP.Setup time. During this phase, the data owner creates two local indexes (i.e. No.Inputs and No.Runs) and a dictionary \mathcal{D} that will be outsourced to the CSP. Our datasets consisted of function families of different sizes, varying from a function family with 10 functions to function families with up to 10,000 different functions. All functions had an arbitrary number of inputs between 10 and 15,000.

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The functions were implemented as `{key: value}` dictionaries of the form `{function_id: list_of_inputs}`.

1. **Local Indexes** Generating the local indexes was a straightforward process executed through exploiting the structure of python dictionaries. Concerning the No.Inputs index, as for each function we had a `{function_id: list_of_inputs}` dictionary, we simply had to find the length of each `list_of_inputs` value. Moreover, for the No.Runs index, considering this was the setup phase, we only had to fill it with zeros. [Table 10a](#) illustrates the times required to generate the local indexes, in relation with the size of the function family (i.e. number of functions).

Table 10 – Dataset Sizes and Setup Times

Size of Function Family	Time (s)
10	0.0034
100	0.032
1,000	0.33
5,000	1.7993
10,000	3.66

(a) Time required for the generation of the local indexes

Number of Functions	Number of Pairs	Time (s)
10	49,127	0.02254
100	499,819	0.1985
1,000	4,993,007	2.0178
5,000	24,982,443	11.7846
10,000	50,036,227	28.2277

(b) Time required for the generation of the dictionary \mathcal{D}

2. **Remote Index (\mathcal{D}):** Generating \mathcal{D} was by far the most demanding process of as for each `{function_id: list_of_inputs}` dictionary we had to:
 - Retrieve the No.Inputs and No.Runs values corresponding to `function_id` and then mask `function_id` as shown in [Algorithm 9](#) to generate mf , and
 - For each possible input of a function x_i create a pair (mf, x_i) and add it into \mathcal{D} .

The total number of (mf, x_i) pairs, increased dramatically as we increased the size of the function family. In particular, for a function family consisting of 10 functions, we ended up with 49,127 pairs and the time to generate \mathcal{D} was measured at 0.02254s. In contrast, for a function family consisting of 10,000 functions, the total number of pairs was 50,036,227 and the required time to generate \mathcal{D} was 28.227s. [Table 10b](#) illustrates the number of pairs and the required time to generate \mathcal{D} for different function families. Additionally, in [Figure 9](#), we visualize the total time required for the successful completion of the FFP.Setup.

Query: In this part of the experiments we measured the time needed to complete a query over the dictionary \mathcal{D} . In our implementation, the query time was calculated as the sum of the time required to generate a token, find the corresponding matches in the database and update the indexes. The time required for the generation of the query token is independent of both the size of the function family and the size of the dictionary \mathcal{D} . On average, the time needed to generate the query token was measured at $8ms$. It needs to be noted that regarding

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Figure 9 – Total Search Time

Figure 10 – Correlation between search time and size of \mathcal{D}

Figure 11 – Adding a new function with different number of inputs

Figure 12 – Experimental results

the retrieval process, the actual process is equivalent to locating rows in the dataframe. More precisely, finding the inputs for a specific function over a set of 10 distinct functions and 49,127 rows required 0.0029s on average while retrieving the inputs for a specific function over a set of 10,000 functions and 50,036,227 rows took 2.082s. Figure 10 illustrates our results.

New Function Addition: In the last part of our experiments we focused on measuring the time required to add a new function to the function family. This process required updating both the local indexes and \mathcal{D} . As already mentioned, all the indexes were implemented as pandas dataframes and all functions were read as `{function_id: list_of_inputs}` dictionaries. To this end, to update all the indexes we had to: (1) Retrieve both the local indexes and \mathcal{D} , (2) Build two dataframes out of the `{function_id: list_of_inputs}` dictionary, just like in the Setup phase, and (3) Merge the new dataframes with the existing ones. To get a better picture of the computational time required for this process, we ran this experiment for all the different

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size dictionaries \mathcal{D} that we generated in the Setup phase. Another variable in this experiment was the number of inputs for the new function. More precisely, we measured the time required to add a function whose number of inputs varied from 1,000 to 15,000. What we found was that the total time required to add a new function was almost independent of the function's number of inputs, as on average the number of inputs affected the running time by a total of 0,1ms. Conversely, the running time was drastically affected by the size of the existing dictionary \mathcal{D} , as it varied from 0.45ms for a dictionary the size of 499,819 to almost 17.5ms for a dictionary the size of 50,036,227. [Figure 11](#) visualises our results.

8.6 Limitations of FE

Despite being able to be used for secure computation, FE faces the issues of being complex to implement, requiring rigorous analysis to prove its security for each individual usecase. Additionally, this complexity can lead to difficulties performing certain operations and implementing some functionalities. Due to these limitations, we aimed to analyse HE and HHE schemes to find possible alternatives in solving complex tasks, which may not be possible through the use of FE.

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9 Homomorphic Encryption

In this section, we examine the general HE definition and its correctness. Subsequently, we delve into an exploration of the four HE schemes commonly employed across various HHE schemes.

Over the years, researchers have developed three types of HE: Partially Homomorphic Encryption (PHE), Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption (SHE), and Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), with distinct properties and capabilities. Though computationally intensive and resource-demanding, FHE allows any ciphertext computation, including addition, multiplication, and complex operations. PHE permits either addition or multiplication on ciphertexts, it is less intense computationally but lacks FHE's complexity. SHE strikes a balance, supporting limited computations (addition and multiplication), while being more practical than PHE and less resource-intensive than FHE.

Since the groundbreaking work by Gentry [23], numerous HE schemes have emerged to handle diverse data types. Notably, the Brakerski-Gentry-Vaikuntanathan (BGV) [40] supports modular arithmetic over finite fields, enabling computations on vectors of integers in \mathbb{Z}_q with $q \geq 2$. Similarly, the Brakerski/Fan-Vercauteren (B/FV) [41, 42] operates over finite fields and facilitates computations on integer vectors. The Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song (CKKS) [43] allows approximate computations on vectors of real and complex numbers. Additionally, the Torus FHE (TFHE) [44, 45, 46] employs boolean circuits and decision diagrams for low-precision integers [47]. Each HE scheme is meticulously designed to achieve specific optimization goals. BGV, B/FV, and CKKS prioritize minimizing the multiplicative depth in their decryption circuits, while TFHE focuses on reducing the gate count required for decryption operations.

9.1 Background

9.1.1 Notation

Throughout the rest of the sections, vectors are represented in lowercase bold letters, and matrices in capital letters. Let $[n]$ be the set of integers from 1 to n . $[\cdot]$ denotes the nearest integer to a real number, while $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ represents the inner product of two vectors. $[\cdot]_q$ signifies the mod q reduction, and $\|\mathbf{v}\|_p$ denotes the ℓ_p -norm of the vector \mathbf{v} . We denote λ the security parameter of a cryptosystem. For a probability distribution χ , we denote $x \stackrel{\chi}{\leftarrow} S$ if x is sampled from a set S according to the distribution χ , with $\$$ the random distribution. Finally, $\mathcal{D}_{S,\sigma}$ stands for the Gaussian distribution in a set S for width σ . We use \mathbb{G} to denote an additive group, \mathbb{Z}_p to denote the set of integers modulo p , \mathbb{F}_p the field of integers modulo p , and \mathcal{R}_n the quotient ring $\mathbb{Z}_n[X]/(P)$ of polynomials over $\mathbb{Z}_n[X]$ by the ideal generated by an irreducible polynomial

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\mathcal{P} . We use \mathcal{P} to indicate the plaintext space, and \mathcal{C} to indicate the ciphertext space. We use the notation $\mathbf{v}_1 \odot \mathbf{v}_2$ to represent the element-wise product between two vectors. Additionally, $rot_i(\mathbf{v})$ indicates the rotation of a vector \mathbf{v} by i steps to the left. Finally, we use the terms pk , sk , and evk to denote public, secret, and evaluation keys respectively.

9.1.2 Substitution-Permutation Network

Substitution-Permutation Network (SPN) is a cryptographic construction used to design block ciphers [48]. The SPN consists of non-linear substitutions (S-boxes) and linear bit permutations, based on the concept of **confusion** and **diffusion** [49]. In SPN, N represents the block size of a basic SPN consisting of r -rounds of $n \times n$ s-boxes [50].

9.1.3 Permutation

We call permutation any bijection of a set in itself. The permutation of a vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ is a rearrangement of its elements $(x_{\sigma(1)}, \dots, x_{\sigma(n)})$, for $\sigma(i) \in [1, n]$ and $\sigma(i) \neq \sigma(j), i \neq j$.

9.1.4 S-Box

An important part of designing a symmetric cipher is choosing an efficient S-Box for the non-linear layer. Authors in [26] analyzed and compared different S-Boxes. Here we add the missing ones and redefine all with our notation for future usage in [section 10](#).

χ -S-box. It is a non-linear function that takes as input a vector of n elements in \mathbb{Z}_q and outputs a vector of n elements in \mathbb{Z}_q . The χ -S-box is defined as follows:

$$[S_{\chi}(\mathbf{x})]_i = x_i + x_{i+2} + (x_{i+1} \cdot x_{i+2}) = x_i + x_{i+2} \cdot (1 + x_{i+1}).$$

Cube S-Box. Given a prime p , $\gcd(p-1, 3) = 1$, the cube S-Box is defined as follows:

$$[S_c(\mathbf{x})]_i = (x_i)^3.$$

Feistel-Like S-Box via a Quadratic Function. The feistel-like S-Box is defined as follows:

$$[S_{fq}(\mathbf{x})]_i = \begin{cases} x_i & \text{if } i = 0, \\ x_i + (x_{i-1})^2 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

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Feistel-Like S-Box via the χ -Function. The Feistel-like S-Box is defined as follows:

$$[S_{f\chi}(\mathbf{x})]_i = \begin{cases} x_i & \text{if } i \leq 1, \\ x_i + (x_{i-1} \cdot x_{i-2}) & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

LowMC S-Box. For three input bits a , b , and c , the LowMC S-box is defined as follows:

$$S_{mc}(a, b, c) = (a \oplus bc, a \oplus b \oplus ac, a \oplus b \oplus c \oplus ab)$$

9.1.5 Stream Ciphers

As defined in [51] most stream ciphers are a generic construction that can be represented through a finite state machine characterized by the key (K), the initial vector (IV), and the internal state (S). An initialization function expands K and the initial value of IV into an initial internal state. Subsequently, the internal state undergoes updates via an update function, and the output function generates an output based on the final state.

9.1.6 Filter Permutator

As illustrated in Figure 13, a filter permutator (FP) consists of a constant key register (K), a permutation generator, a pseudo-random number generator (PRNG) initialized with a public IV , a pseudo-random permutation (P) and a non-linear filter function (F). Based on the PRNG output, the permutation generator applies a new bit-permutation to K in each cycle. The filtering function F generates a keystream bit from the permuted key, which is then XORed with the plaintext to create ciphertext.

Figure 13 – Filter Permutator Construction [1]

9.1.7 Look-Up Table (LUT)

A look-up table L over a set S is an array of N entries in S , indexed by $i \in [N]$. We denote $L[i] \in S$ the value of L stored in position i . In this work, we only focus on Negacyclic LUT

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(NLUT). Note that if we can define an LUT on any set, an NLUT can only be defined over a group. In this article, this group is the real torus $\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{Z}$.

Definition 18 (Negacyclic Look-Up Table (NLUT)). *A negacyclic look-up table over \mathbb{T} is a look-up table of size $2N$ such that $\forall i \in [N]$,*

$$L[N + i] = -L[i] \in R$$

In practice, an NLUT is represented by a polynomial $P \in \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]$. Denote $P = a_0 + a_1X + \dots + a_{N-1}X^{N-1}$, where $2N$ is the size of the LUT. The value of the i -th entry is given by $(X^{-i} \cdot P) \bmod X$. This polynomial representation allows the homomorphic evaluation of an NLUT presented in [subsubsection 10.2.4](#).

9.1.8 Learning With Errors (LWE)

LWE was introduced and established by Regev in 2009 [52], showcasing its comparable worst-case hardness properties through a quantum reduction. With the diversification of cryptographic protocols, new variants of this problem have emerged, such as RLWE or TLWE. All these variants reduce to the same hardness assumption, which we refer to as GLWE. For the sake of clarity, we formally define only the General LWE (GLWE) problem. Then we informally discuss the particular cases of this problem used in this work.

Definition 19 (GLWE sample). *Let R be a ring and denote $R_N[X] := R[X]/(X^N + 1)$ for N a power of 2. For a positive integer k , a vector $\mathbf{s} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_N[X]^k$ and a polynomial $\mu \in R_N[X]$, we define*

$$\text{GLWE}_{\mathbf{s}}(\mu) = (\mathbf{a}, \mu + \langle \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a} \rangle + e)$$

where $\mathbf{a} \xleftarrow{\$} R_N[X]^k$ and $e \xleftarrow{\chi} R_N[X]$ for an error distribution χ .

Note that the trivial sample $\text{GLWE}_{\mathbf{s}}(0_R) = (\mathbf{a}, \langle \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{a} \rangle + e)$ is called the GLWE distribution.

Definition 20 (GLWE problem). *Let $\mathbf{s} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_N[X]^k$ be a secret vector.*

- *Search GLWE: Given $\text{GLWE}_{\mathbf{s}}(0_R) = (\mathbf{a}, \langle \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{a} \rangle + e)$ and the distribution χ , find \mathbf{s} ;*
- *Decisional GLWE: Given a pair $(\mathbf{a}, b) \in R_N[X]^{k+1}$ and the distribution χ , decide if b is chosen at random, i.e. $b \xleftarrow{\$} R_N[X]$, or if it follows a GLWE distribution that is $(\mathbf{a}, b) = \text{GLWE}_{\mathbf{s}}(0_R)$.*

The classical LWE problem stated by Regev corresponds to the case $N = 1$ and $R = \mathbb{Z}_q$, for q a power of a prime. In short, an LWE sample is given by $\text{LWE}_{\mathbf{s}}(\mu) = ((a_1, \dots, a_k), \mu + \langle \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a} \rangle + e)$, for $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, \dots, a_k) \in \mathbb{Z}_q^k$, $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{Z}^k$, $\mu \in \mathbb{Z}_q$ and $e \xleftarrow{\chi} \mathbb{Z}_q$.

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Learning with errors over a ring. For large values of N , encryption schemes based on LWE are too expensive for practical use in cryptography, especially in HE. To decrease computational complexity, most of the HE schemes rely on the Ring Learning With Errors (RLWE) problem [53], a variant of LWE that samples the keys in a polynomial ring.

This variant corresponds to the case $k = 1$, that is the RLWE sample given by $\text{RLWE}_s(\mu) = (a(X), \mu + a(X) \cdot s(X) + e(X))$, for $a(X) \in \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]$, $s(X) \in \mathbb{Z}_N[X]$, $\mu(X) \in \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]$ and $e(X) \xleftarrow{X} \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]$.

Learning with errors over the torus. While LWE or RLWE over integers have been in the spotlight for the past decades, recent works [46] have been extending this paradigm to another structure: the torus. We define the real torus as the ring $\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{Z}$, that is the set of real numbers between 0 and 1. We justify using this new structure in section 9, where we describe TFHE, a cryptosystem that relies on the following distribution.

Set $R = \mathbb{T}$. A TLWE sample is defined as:

$$\text{TLWE}_s(\mu) = (\mathbf{a}, \mu + \langle \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a} \rangle + e),$$

$\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{T}_N[X]^k$, $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{Z}_N[X]^k$, $\mu \in \mathbb{T}_N[X]$ and $e \xleftarrow{X} \mathbb{T}_N[X]$. In classical LWE, one can define the classical LWE encryption over the torus by setting $N = 1$ or a ring version of TLWE by setting $k = 1$, which are the two types of ciphertexts used in torus-based cryptography.

General Gentry-Sahai-Waters construction A GGSW encryption, named after Gentry *et al.* [54] who first introduced it, is an extension of GLWE. In a nutshell, it is given by a vector of GLWE distributions. Consider an integer plaintext $\mu \in \mathbb{Z}_N[X]^k$ and a vector $\mathbf{s} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_N[X]^k$. For $d > 0$ its *depth* and a basis $\beta > 0$, a GGSW sample is given by

$$\text{GLWE}_s(\mu) = \mathbf{Z} + \mu \cdot \mathbf{G}^{(\beta)} \in \mathbb{T}_N[X]^{d(k+1) \times (k+1)}$$

where \mathbf{Z} is a matrix of $d(k+1)$ GLWE distributions and $\mathbf{G}^{(\beta)}$ is the gadget matrix in $\mathbb{T}_N[X]^{d(k+1) \times (k+1)}$ given by $G_{i,j}^{(\beta)} = \mathbf{I}_{k+1} \otimes \mathbf{g}$ for \mathbf{I}_{k+1} the identity matrix, \otimes the tensor product and \mathbf{g} the vector of size d given by $g_i = \beta^{-i}$, $i \in [d]$.

9.2 General HE scheme

An HE scheme is a tuple of four algorithms $\text{HE} := (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Eval}, \text{Dec})$ defined as follows:

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9.1: General HE Definition

1. $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ takes as input a security parameter λ and outputs the public key pk , the secret key sk and the evaluation key evk ;
2. $\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, \mathbf{m})$ takes as input the public key pk and a message \mathbf{m} and outputs a ciphertext \mathbf{c}_m ;
3. $\text{Eval}(\text{evk}, f, (c_{m_1}, \dots, c_{m_n}))$ takes as input the evaluation key evk , a function f and an n -tuple of ciphertexts $(c_{m_1}, \dots, c_{m_n})$ and outputs a ciphertext \mathbf{c}^f ;
4. $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \mathbf{c}^f)$ takes as input the secret key sk and a ciphertext \mathbf{c}^f and outputs \mathbf{m}^f .

Correctness: An HE scheme is correct if:

$$\Pr \left[\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \mathbf{c}^f) \neq f(m_1, \dots, m_n) \mid \left[(\text{pk}, \text{sk}, \text{evk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda) \right] \wedge \left[\mathbf{c}^f \leftarrow \text{Eval}(\text{evk}, f, (c_{m_1}, \dots, c_{m_n})) \right] \right] = \text{negl}(\lambda).$$

9.3 BGV Scheme

BGV is a SHE scheme based on RLWE that supports modular arithmetic over finite fields [40]. BGV construction is scale-dependent, relying on a predetermined sequence of moduli $\mathcal{Q} = \{q_0, q_1, \dots, q_L\}$. Each modulus is the ciphertext scale for a certain level of operation, and each multiplication requires a modulus switch.

Setup: Given a security parameter λ , generate two integers $t, n > 0$ and $q_0 < \dots < q_L$ a sequence of powers of prime q_ℓ with $\ell \in [L]$. Then set $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{R}_t = \mathbb{Z}_t[X]/(X^n + 1)$ the plaintext space and $\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{R}_{q_\ell} \times \mathcal{R}_{q_\ell}$ the ciphertext space at level ℓ , for $\mathcal{R}_{q_\ell} = \mathbb{Z}_{q_\ell}[X]/(X^n + 1)$. Finally, denote $\mathcal{D}_{q_\ell, \sigma}$ the discrete Gaussian distribution over \mathcal{R}_{q_ℓ} of width σ . The BGV algorithms are illustrated in 9.2.

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9.2: BGV

1. $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ takes as input a security parameter λ . Sample $\text{sk} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathcal{R}$ with coefficients in $\{-1, 0, 1\}$, $a \xleftarrow{\$} \mathcal{R}_{q_L}$, and $e \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_{q_L, \sigma}$; set $\text{pk} = (b, a) \in \mathcal{R}_{q_L}^2$, where $b \leftarrow [-a \cdot \text{sk} + t \cdot e]_{q_L}$, and $\text{evk} = (b', a) \in \mathcal{R}_{q_L}^2$, where $b' \leftarrow [-(a \cdot \text{sk} + e) + \text{sk}^2]_{q_L}$; outputs $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk})$;
2. $\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m)$ takes as input the public key pk and a plaintext $m \in \mathcal{P}$. Sample $u \xleftarrow{\$} \mathcal{R}$ with coefficients in $\{-1, 0, 1\}$, and $e_1, e_2 \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_{q_e, \sigma}$. Set $c_1 \leftarrow [b \cdot u + t \cdot e_1 + m]_{q_e}$ and $c_2 \leftarrow [a \cdot u + t \cdot e_2]_{q_e}$; outputs $c = (c_1, c_2)$;
3. $\text{EvalAdd}(c^{(1)}, c^{(2)})$ takes as input two ciphertexts $c^{(1)}, c^{(2)}$ and computes $c_1^{\text{add}} \leftarrow [c_1^{(1)} + c_1^{(2)}]_{q_e}$ and $c_2^{\text{add}} \leftarrow [c_2^{(1)} + c_2^{(2)}]_{q_e}$; outputs $c^{\text{add}} = (c_1^{\text{add}}, c_2^{\text{add}})$;
4. $\text{EvalMult}(c^{(1)}, c^{(2)})$ takes as input two ciphertexts $c^{(1)}, c^{(2)}$ and computes $\bar{c} = (\bar{c}_1, \bar{c}_2, \bar{c}_3) \leftarrow \left([c_1^{(1)} \cdot c_1^{(2)}]_{q_e}, [c_1^{(1)} \cdot c_2^{(2)} + c_2^{(1)} \cdot c_1^{(2)}]_{q_e}, [c_2^{(1)} \cdot c_2^{(2)}]_{q_e} \right)$. Set $c^{\text{mult}} \leftarrow \text{Relinearize}(\text{evk}, \bar{c})$; outputs c^{mult} ;
5. $\text{Relinearize}(\text{evk}, \bar{c})$ takes as input the evaluation key $\text{evk} = (b', a)$ and $\bar{c} = (\bar{c}_1, \bar{c}_2, \bar{c}_3)$, compute $c_1 \leftarrow [\bar{c}_1 + b' \cdot \bar{c}_3]_{q_e}$ and $c_2 \leftarrow [\bar{c}_2 + a \cdot \bar{c}_3]_{q_e}$; outputs $c = (c_1, c_2)$;
6. $\text{ModSwitch}(\text{evk}, c)$ takes as input the evaluation key evk , a ciphertext c encrypted modulo q_e ; computes $c' \leftarrow \left\lfloor \frac{q_e}{q_{e-1}} \cdot c \right\rfloor$; outputs c' ;
7. $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, c)$ takes as input the secret key sk and the ciphertext c . Compute $m' \leftarrow [c_1 + c_2 \cdot \text{sk}]_{q_e}$. If $\|m'\|_\infty \geq \frac{q_e}{2}$, outputs \perp ; otherwise computes $m \leftarrow [m']_t$ and outputs m .

From this point onward, for simplicity and due to space constraints, we will not redefine functions for other HE schemes that share the same principles as BGV.

9.4 B/FV Scheme

B/FV is another SHE scheme that supports modular arithmetic over finite fields [41, 42]. B/FV is scale-independent, meaning the ciphertext modulus remains constant during homomorphic evaluation. The plaintext and the ciphertext spaces are defined over two polynomial rings denoted by $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{R}_t = \mathbb{Z}_t[X]/(X^n + 1)$, and $\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{R}_q \times \mathcal{R}_q$, where $\mathcal{R}_q = \mathbb{Z}_q[X]/(X^n + 1)$, respectively. Unlike the BGV scheme, in B/FV, the plaintext is placed on the most significant bits of the data structure. This is achieved by utilizing a scale factor, denoted as Δ , and adjusting the message's scale both before encryption and after decryption. The BFV is outlined in 9.3.

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9.3: B/FV

1. $\text{ScaleUp}(m, \Delta = \lfloor \frac{q}{t} \rfloor)$ takes as input the message m and scale factor Δ and outputs $m' = \Delta \cdot m$;
2. $\text{ScaleDown}(m', \Delta^{-1} = \lfloor \frac{t}{q} \rfloor)$ takes the scaled-up message m' and reverse scale factor Δ^{-1} , and outputs $m = \Delta^{-1} \cdot m'$.
3. $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ outputs $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk})$;
4. $\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m')$ outputs c ;
5. $\text{EvalAdd}(c^{(1)}, c^{(2)})$ outputs c^{add} ;
6. $\text{EvalMult}(c^{(1)}, c^{(2)})$ outputs c^{mult} ;
7. $\text{Relinearize}(\text{evk}, \bar{c})$ outputs c ;
8. $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, c)$ outputs m' .

9.5 CKKS Scheme

CKKS is a SHE scheme permitting approximate computation on vectors of real and complex numbers [55]. CKKS operates as a scale-dependent HE scheme, where the ciphertext modulus adapts throughout homomorphic evaluation, akin to the BGV scheme. The plaintext and ciphertext spaces are defined in the same way as $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{R}$ and $\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{R}_q^2$, where $\mathcal{R}_q = \mathbb{Z}_q[X]/(X^n + 1)$.

Encoding: We consider a message as a vector of complex numbers $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{C}^{n/2}$ and provide an encoding to convert \mathbf{z} into a suitable plaintext. This method relies on a scaling factor Δ and the canonical embedding $\pi : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{n/2}$. This construction is detailed in [43].

9.4: CKKS

1. $\text{Encode}(\mathbf{z}, \Delta)$ takes as input a vector $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{C}^n$ and the scale factor Δ . Maps \mathbf{z} into element $w \in \mathcal{R}$, where $w \leftarrow \lfloor \Delta \cdot \pi^{-1}(\mathbf{z}) \rfloor$; outputs w ;
2. $\text{Decode}(w, \Delta)$ takes a plaintext ring element $w \in \mathcal{R}$, and computes $\mathbf{z} \leftarrow \pi(\Delta^{-1} \cdot w)$; outputs \mathbf{z} ;
3. $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ outputs $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk})$;
4. $\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m)$ outputs c ;
5. $\text{EvalAdd}(c^{(1)}, c^{(2)})$ outputs c^{add} ;
6. $\text{EvalMult}(c^{(1)}, c^{(2)})$ outputs c^{mult} ;
7. $\text{Relinearize}(\text{evk}, \bar{c})$ outputs c ;
8. $\text{Rescale}(c_{qe}, \Delta)$ scale the input ciphertext c down by Δ such that $c'_{qe-1} = \Delta^{-1} \cdot [(c_1, c_2)]_{qe}$. Rescale is similar to BGV ModSwitch, outputs c'_{qe-1} ;
9. $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, c)$ outputs m' .

9.6 TFHE Scheme

TFHE is an FHE scheme founded on bootstrapping. Unlike the *leveled* HE schemes, TFHE is *fully* homomorphic, enabling support for any logical circuit and, consequently, any function. The particularity of TFHE is that it uses two types of encryption: the classical LWE ciphertext and the so-called General-GSW ciphertext. The latter permits efficient homomorphic multiplications.

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Bootstrapping: To define a proper cryptosystem, one has to guarantee that any ciphertext can be decrypted correctly. As homomorphic operations tend to make the noise grow, it is necessary to provide a method to keep the noise of a ciphertext under a given bound. This can be achieved with a technique known as bootstrapping, which consists of refreshing the encryption of a message into a new ciphertext, hence resetting the noise to an acceptable level.

Let $\mathbb{B} = \{0, 1\}$, and \mathbb{T} be the real Torus, *i.e.* the set of real numbers modulo one. For $q, N > 0$ two powers of 2, we denote $\mathbb{T}_N[X] = \mathbb{T}_N[X]/(X^N + 1)$, $\mathbb{B}_N[X] = \mathbb{B}[X]/(X^N + 1)$ and $\mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X] = \mathbb{Z}_q[X]/(X^N + 1)$. Let $\beta > 0$ and $d \in \mathbb{Z}$ be two integers, called respectively the base and the depth.

9.5: TFHE

1. $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ takes as input a security parameter λ . Sample $k = k(\lambda)$ polynomials $\text{sk} := (s_1, \dots, s_k) \xleftarrow{\$} (\mathbb{B}_{q,N}[X])^k$. Set $\text{pk} := (\mathbf{a}, b) \leftarrow \text{GLWE}_{\text{sk}}(\mathbf{0})$, output the keys (pk, sk) .
2. $\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m)$ takes as input the public key pk and a message $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]$. Compute $\mathbf{c} \leftarrow (\mathbf{a}, b + m + e) = \text{GLWE}_{\text{sk}}(m) \in (\mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X])^{k+1}$, for $e \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]$ and outputs \mathbf{c} ;
3. $\text{EvalMult}(\mathbf{G}, \mathbf{c})$ takes as input a GGSW ciphertext \mathbf{G} and a GLWE ciphertext \mathbf{c} . First compute $(\mathbf{c})_\beta \leftarrow ((a_1)_\beta, \dots, (a_k)_\beta, (b)_\beta) \in \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]^{d(k+1)}$ where $(\cdot)_\beta$ is the decomposition in basis β . Compute the GLWE ciphertext $\mathbf{c}^{\text{mult}} \leftarrow (\mathbf{c})_\beta \cdot \mathbf{G}$; outputs \mathbf{c}^{mult} ;
4. $\text{KeySwitch}(\text{sk}', \mathbf{c})$ takes as input a new secret key sk' and a GLWE ciphertext $\mathbf{c} = (\mathbf{a}, b)$. Define the key-switching key $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{Z}_{q,N}[X]^{d \cdot k \times (k+1)}$ as the first $d \cdot k$ rows of $\text{GGSW}_{\text{sk}'}(1)$. Compute the GLWE ciphertext $\mathbf{c}' \leftarrow (\mathbf{0}, b) - \text{EvalMult}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{a})$ encrypted under sk' ; outputs \mathbf{c}' ;
5. $\text{CMux}(\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{c}_0, \mathbf{c}_1)$ takes as input two GLWE ciphertexts $\mathbf{c}_0, \mathbf{c}_1$ of plaintexts m_0, m_1 and a GGSW ciphertext \mathbf{B} of a bit b . Compute the GLWE ciphertext $\mathbf{c}_3 \leftarrow \text{EvalMult}(\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{c}_1 - \mathbf{c}_0) + \mathbf{c}_0$, which is an encryption of m_b with fresh noise; outputs \mathbf{c}_3 ;
6. $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \mathbf{c})$ takes as input the secret key sk and a ciphertext \mathbf{c} . Compute $b - \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot s_i = m + e$. Then round to the nearest integer to output the message m .

Mark that a GLWE ciphertext mentioned in 9.5 is an LWE ciphertext if $N = 1$ and an RLWE ciphertext if $k = 1$.

As this method is usually too slow to be practical, TFHE introduces a novel idea that consists of running the bootstrapping together with the evaluation of a look-up table. Given as input \mathbf{G} , a GGSW encryption of an NLUT L , and \mathbf{c} the LWE encryption of a message m , one can compute directly a fresh ciphertext \mathbf{c}' of $L[m]$. This method requires a heavy usage of the CMux algorithm that can be optimized using *programmable bootstrapping*. We refer the reader to the articles of Chillotti *et al.* [46] and Cosserson *et al.* [56]

9.7 HE Semantic Security

In this part, we recall the definition of semantic security for HE schemes.

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Definition 21 (HE Indistinguishability-Based Security). For an HE scheme $HE = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Eval}, \text{Dec})$ a challenger \mathcal{C} and a PPT algorithm \mathcal{ADV} , define the following security game:

HE-IND-CPA Security

Initialize:

Run $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ and give pk, evk to \mathcal{ADV} .

Query:

\mathcal{ADV} encrypts a polynomial number of chosen plaintexts with pk . Eventually, she submits two messages m_0, m_1 to \mathcal{C} .

Challenge:

\mathcal{C} picks a random bit $\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, 1\}$, encrypts $c_\beta \leftarrow \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m_\beta)$, and sends c_β to \mathcal{ADV} .

Evaluation Query:

\mathcal{ADV} encrypts a polynomial number of chosen plaintexts m_3, \dots, m_t with pk . She performs n evaluations for functions f_1, \dots, f_n with key evk and entries c_β and c_{m_3}, \dots, c_{m_t} .

Guess:

\mathcal{ADV} outputs a guess $\beta' \in \{0, 1\}$ on β with an advantage $\varepsilon(\lambda)$.

HE is said to be λ -HE-CPA secure if and only if the advantage $\varepsilon(\lambda) = \left| \frac{1}{2} - \Pr[\beta' = \beta] \right|$ is negligible. More generally, HE is HE-CPA secure if it is λ -HE-CPA secure for a polynomial security parameter λ .

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10 Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption

In this section, we introduce a novel definition for HHE schemes, which overviews the core algorithms of them. Additionally, we conduct a literature analysis to enhance our understanding of the diverse techniques and design approaches employed in creating HHE schemes. Our study is divided into two parts: a brief history of HE-friendly symmetric ciphers (subsection 10.1), and an examination and evaluation of state-of-the-art HE-friendly ciphers and their characteristics (subsection 10.2). After the evaluation, we use our novel definition for HHE schemes to define the semantic security of HHE (subsection 10.4). Finally, we overview the attacks which are known on HHE schemes (subsection 10.5).

Within the realm of HE, high computational costs and significant ciphertext expansion are two major challenges faced by real-world applications. To tackle these issues, researchers in [27] proposed a hybrid approach, where the plaintext m is symmetrically encrypted using a randomly chosen key K by a client. The resulting ciphertext c_m is much smaller in size, with an encryption ratio of $|c_m|/|m| \approx 1$. The client then sends c_m along with homomorphically encrypted K to a remote location, such as a cloud service provider. Here, c_m is transformed into a homomorphic ciphertext c^{evl} by evaluating the SKE decryption circuit. With this in mind, we provide a formal definition of HHE that takes up the construction provided by Dobraunig *et al.* [26]. However, we believe that the definition of the encryption algorithm they proposed was misleading. Therefore, we extend the definition of HHE with an *encapsulation* algorithm (Encap). This algorithm specifically manages the generation of the symmetric key and its encryption into a homomorphic ciphertext.

In an HHE scheme, the algorithm Encap is responsible for both the generation and the homomorphic encryption of K . Let $\text{HE} := (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec}, \text{Eval})$ be a homomorphic encryption scheme and $\text{SKE} := (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ be a symmetric cipher. A hybrid homomorphic encryption scheme is a tuple of the six algorithms $\text{HHE} := (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Encap}, \text{Enc}, \text{Decomp}, \text{Eval}, \text{Dec})$ as follows:

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10.1: Our HHE Definition

1. $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ takes as input a security parameter λ and generates the homomorphic keys $(\text{pk}, \text{sk}, \text{evk}) \leftarrow \text{HE.KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$, outputs $(\text{pk}, \text{sk}, \text{evk})$;
2. $\text{Encap}(\text{pk}, 1^\mu)$ takes as input the public key pk , a security parameter μ and computes the symmetric key $K \leftarrow \text{SKE.Gen}(1^\mu)$ and its homomorphic encryption $c_K \leftarrow \text{HE.Enc}(\text{pk}, K)$, outputs (K, c_K) ;
3. $\text{Enc}(K, \mathbf{m})$ takes as input, the symmetric key K and a message \mathbf{m} and computes the ciphertext $\mathbf{c}_m \leftarrow \text{SKE.Enc}(K, \mathbf{m})$, outputs \mathbf{c}_m ;
4. $\text{Decomp}(\text{evk}, c_K, \mathbf{c}_m)$ takes as input the evaluation key evk , the homomorphically encrypted symmetric key c_K and a symmetric ciphertext \mathbf{c}_m , computes $\mathbf{c}_m^{\text{evl}} \leftarrow \text{HE.Eval}(\text{evk}, \text{SKE.Dec}, (c_K, \mathbf{c}_m))$, outputs $\mathbf{c}_m^{\text{evl}}$;
5. $\text{Eval}(\text{evk}, f, (c_{m_1}^{\text{evl}}, \dots, c_{m_n}^{\text{evl}}))$ takes as input the evaluation key evk , a function f defined in the ciphertext space of HE and a n -tuple of homomorphic ciphertexts $c_{m_i}^{\text{evl}}$ and computes $\mathbf{c}^f \leftarrow \text{HE.Eval}(\text{evk}, f, (c_{m_1}^{\text{evl}}, \dots, c_{m_n}^{\text{evl}}))$, outputs \mathbf{c}^f ;
6. $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \mathbf{c}^f)$ takes as input the homomorphic secret key sk and a ciphertext \mathbf{c}^f and computes $\mathbf{m}^f \leftarrow \text{HE.Dec}(\text{sk}, \mathbf{c}^f)$, if the message \mathbf{m}^f is valid, outputs \mathbf{m}^f ; otherwise outputs \perp .

Correctness: Additionally, an HHE scheme is correct if:

$$\Pr \left[\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, \mathbf{c}^f) \neq f(\mathbf{m}) \mid \left[(\text{pk}, \text{sk}, \text{evk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda) \right] \wedge \left[\mathbf{c}^f \leftarrow \text{Eval}(\text{evk}, f, \mathbf{c}_m^{\text{evl}}) \right] \wedge \left[\mathbf{c}_m^{\text{evl}} \leftarrow \text{Decomp}(\text{evk}, c_K, \mathbf{c}_m) \right] \wedge \left[(K, c_K) \leftarrow \text{Encap}(\text{pk}, 1^\mu) \right] \right] = \text{negl}(\lambda, \mu).$$

The correctness of HHE is achieved if both HE and SKE are correct.

10.1 A History of HE-friendly Symmetric Ciphers

Initially, traditional symmetric ciphers such as AES [57, 58] were used in different HE applications [59, 60, 61, 62]. However, these schemes had high computational costs due to the extensive multiplicative depth in their circuit. Authors in [2] indicated the need for new symmetric ciphers with a lower multiplication complexity and smaller multiplicative depth while maintaining the same level of security and even surpassing the previous security and efficiency level of classic symmetric ciphers. Many HHE schemes have been proposed in recent years, most of which are based on one of two main design approaches for HE-friendly ciphers: SPN-based ciphers (mainly utilizing s-boxes and matrix multiplication) and register-based stream ciphers (employing filter permutation functions). We briefly introduce these two main design approaches and their historical improvements by studying the first generation of HHE schemes. We then provide more detail for their successors.

SPN-based approach. In 2015, **LowMC** [2], the first HE-friendly cipher, was introduced. LowMC is designed to minimize the number of nonlinear operations by using efficient s-boxes while depending on a robust linear layer to ensure its security. Figure 14 shows a single round of

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LowMC. Subsequently, the authors in [63] expanded on the concept of incorporating a robust

Figure 14 – LowMC single round encryption [2]

linear layer, further developing the idea by proposing **Rasta** and **Agrasta**. Rasta uses a publicly chosen and fixed substitution layer. The affine layers are formed using a public *nonce* and a *counter*, ensuring that no affine layer is likely ever to be reused under a single key. This makes a large part of the computation nonce-dependent but key-independent. Agrasta is the aggressive variant, whose key and block sizes are equal to the security level proposed to explore Rasta's limits. Let N , i , r , S_χ , and x be the nonce, block counter, round counter, s-box, and input vector, respectively. Let $M_{j,N,i}$, $c_{j,N,i}$ be the $n \times n$ binary matrix and round constant, generated by an extendable output function (XOF). Rasta's affine layer $A_{r,N,i}$ is as follows:

$$A_{r,N,i} = M_{j,N,i} \cdot x \oplus c_{j,N,i}$$

Given K and (N, i) , Rasta's keystream is $ks_{N,i} \leftarrow K \oplus P_{N,i}(K)$, where

$$P_{N,i} = A_{r,N,i} \circ S_\chi \circ A_{r-1,N,i} \circ \dots \circ S_\chi \circ A_{1,N,i} \circ S_\chi \circ A_{0,N,i}.$$

Authors in [64] found that using XOF to generate random matrices makes the pre-computation phase slower because of the costly restriction of checking matrix invertibility. Therefore, they designed a variant of Rasta that avoids the use of XOF, dubbed **Dasta**. Instead of randomly generated linear layers, that is random invertible binary matrices, the authors consider linear layers that are split into two parts, (1) a variable bit permutation and (2) a fixed linear transformation. Another variant of Rasta called **Masta** [65] employed modular arithmetic to support HE schemes over a non-binary plaintext space. Its advantage over Rasta lies in the reduced computational cost on the client side. This is achieved by defining affine layers with finite field multiplication, resulting in improved performance. **FASTA** [66] as a variant of Rasta designed for efficient homomorphic *packed* evaluation over BGV schemes. Its linear layer, a rotation-based transformation is combined with five parallel calls of a specific Rasta instance. Each of these instances operates with the 329-bit key and contributes to generating a portion of the keystream. **Chaghri** [67], a recently proposed SPN-based cipher, follows the *Marvellous* design strategy [68]. It operates in rounds, with each round comprising three layers: S-box,

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linear, and subkey injection. The subkeys for injection are derived from the master key using a key schedule algorithm. In the S-box layer, a power map x^a is applied to each state element, followed by an invertible affine transformation. Regrettably, Chaghri fails to surpass other HHE schemes in performance. Consequently, we have left it out of the state-of-the-art schemes.

Register-based approach. In 2015, the authors of **Kreyvium** [3] proposed a completely different approach, relying on tailor-made stream ciphers. Kreyvium is a variant of the Trivium [69] stream cipher, designed to deliver 128-bit security, while preserving its performance attributes. Trivium itself is a stream cipher that has garnered recommendation within the eSTREAM portfolio of stream ciphers [70]. The authors introduced a new HHE structure (Figure 15) consisting of two phases: the **offline** and **online** phases. The offline phase is independent of the plaintext and can be completed in advance, while the online phase is executed upon receiving the symmetric ciphertext, which is dependent on the plaintext input.

Figure 15 – Kreyvium HHE framework [3]

As shown in Figure 15, the plaintext space has been considered as $\{0, 1\}$, and the stream cipher is a combination of an expansion function G which maps ℓ_{IV} -bit strings to strings of arbitrary size, and a fixed-size parametrized function F with input size ℓ_x , parameter size ℓ_K and output size N . The expansion function G is a CTR mode counter defined as $G(IV, t \cdot \ell_x) = (IV, IV \boxplus 1, \dots, IV \boxplus (t - 1))$ where $a \boxplus b = (a + b) \bmod 2^{\ell_x}$. Additionally, F is designed to generate the keystream using a synchronization function that takes the IV and K and outputs

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an n -bit initial state, a transition function that computes the next state, and a filtering function that takes the internal state and computes the keystream based on that.

An alternative method with a similar objective was proposed by the authors of **FLIP** [1]. FLIP stream cipher incorporates a filter permutator using a forward PRNG [71] based on AES-128, the Knuth shuffle [72] bit permutation generator, and a filter function. This design achieves consistent noise reduction when integrated with HE schemes. FLIP's authors propose a boolean filtering function optimized for FHE schemes like GSW [54] and FHEW [73]. The authors introduced a novel framework, named Homomorphic Encryption-Symmetric Encryption (HE-SE), comprising of five steps, as illustrated in Figure 16. FLIP has shown certain security weak-

Figure 16 – General HHE framework [1]

nesses [74]. In response to these vulnerabilities, the authors introduced **FiLIP** [75], an enhanced iteration of FLIP, adopting the Improved Filter Permutator (IFP) paradigm. The main advantage of IFPs is that they can apply to any filtering function and register size, providing a general framework for determining the security of IFP instances. FiLIP's authors coined the term *transciphering*, adopted widely among other HHE schemes.

Note that the process of homomorphic evaluation for the decryption circuit is known as *transciphering*, and it is the most resource-intensive aspect of HHE frameworks. It is noteworthy that *transciphering* is denoted by terms such as *decompression* or *decomp* in the context of HHE

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schemes.

In light of various design approaches for HHE schemes, recent advancements have suggested schemes like PASTA, HERA, and Rubato, leveraging robust linear layers and S-boxes. In addition, Elisabeth follows the FP design paradigm. The subsequent sections delve into the specifics of these diverse HHE schemes.

10.2 State-of-the-Art HE-friendly Symmetric Ciphers

10.2.1 Pasta

Pasta [26] is a new stream cipher optimized for integer use cases over \mathbb{F}_p . Pasta's authors provide an extensive comparison of different existing symmetric ciphers in the context of HHE spanning several libraries. Their results show that Pasta achieves a better balance between ciphertext expansion and computational efficiency compared to existing symmetric ciphers. This is achieved by using a combination of techniques such as S-boxes, and linear layers that are specifically tailored for integer arithmetic over \mathbb{F}_p . The design of PASTA is based on the Rasta design strategy, namely splitting the cipher into two parallel branches to optimize the linear layer. Taking \mathbf{k} as an input, Pasta's permutation is as follows:

$$P_{N,i} = A_{r,N,i} \circ S_c \circ A_{r-1,N,i} \circ S_{fq} \circ A_{r-2,N,i} \circ \dots \circ A_{1,N,i} \circ S_{fq} \circ A_{0,N,i}$$

It utilizes two types of S-boxes, as previously defined in [subsection 9.1](#). Further, similar to Rasta, Pasta's affine layer was defined as follows:

$$A_{j,N,i} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \cdot I & I \\ I & 2 \cdot I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} M_{j,L,N,i}(\mathbf{x}_L) + \mathbf{c}_{j,L,N,i} \\ M_{j,R,N,i}(\mathbf{x}_R) + \mathbf{c}_{j,R,N,i} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $I, M \in \mathbb{F}_p^{t \times t}$, and $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{F}_p^t$ represent the identity matrix, invertible matrix, and constant for each round, respectively. It is worth noting that FASTA was introduced after Pasta; however, the authors abstained from a direct comparison between FASTA and Pasta. Instead, they asserted that the design of FASTA signifies an improvement over the Rasta and Dasta schemes.

10.2.2 HERA

HERA [76] is an HE-friendly stream cipher with a Randomized key schedule designed for approximate computation. HERA's author proposed a new transciphering framework called RtF (Real-to-Finite-field) for efficient computation over encrypted data of real numbers using HE. The framework combines the CKKS and BFV homomorphic encryption schemes and uses HERA stream cipher with modular arithmetic in between. Following the design paradigm of

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Kreyvium, RtF also incorporates two distinct phases for offline and online computation. Using the new framework combined with HERA, real numbers can be encrypted without significant ciphertext expansion or computational overload on the client side. HERA encrypts a real message vector $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ on the client side and converts the ciphertexts into the corresponding CKKS ciphertexts on the server side. The framework allows for real numbers to be encrypted without significant ciphertext expansion or computational overload on the client side, making it efficient for practical use cases. The main idea behind the HERA cipher is to use a simple randomized key schedule to generate a set of polynomials over \mathbb{Z}_t in unknowns $\{k_0, \dots, k_{15}\}$, where $k_i \in \mathbb{Z}_t$ denotes the i -th component of the secret key $K \in \mathbb{Z}_t^{16}$. HERA is designed to have a low multiplicative depth, making it efficient for homomorphic encryption schemes. Taking K as an input, HERA's permutation is as follows:

$$P_N = Fin_{r,N} \circ RF_{r-1,N} \circ \dots \circ RF_{1,N} \circ KSD_{0,N}$$

where Fin , RF , and KSD denote the final round function, round function, and key scheduler, respectively. For each round $1 < i < r - 1$, the round function is defined as $RF_{i,N} = KSD_{i,N} \circ S_c \circ MixRows \circ MixColumns$. Additionally, the final round function operates on the final round r as $Fin_{r,N} = KSD_{r,N} \circ MixRows \circ MixColumns \circ S_c \circ MixRows \circ MixColumns$. Finally, the key scheduler component is a product between a uniformly random value $\mathbf{rc} \in (\mathbb{Z}_t^{16})^{r+1}$ obtained from an XOF function fed by a nonce N , and K , denoted as $KSD_{i,N}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} + K \odot \mathbf{rc}_i$. Compared to other HE-friendly ciphers such as FLIP and Rasta using randomized linear layers, HERA requires a smaller number of random bits, which significantly improves its efficiency on both the client and server sides.

10.2.3 Rubato

Rubato [77] is a family of noisy ciphers for approximate homomorphic encryption based on HERA design. Rubato introduces noise to a symmetric cipher of low algebraic degree, resulting in a significant reduction in multiplicative complexity without compromising security. Rubato operates in the same transciphering framework as RtF. It takes a symmetric key and a nonce as input and returns a keystream. The keystream is generated by applying a series of linear and non-linear transformations to the input key and nonce. The noise is introduced during the encryption process, resulting in a noisy cipher that is not suitable for the transciphering of exact data. Same as HERA, Rubato uses a randomized key schedule to generate a set of polynomials over \mathbb{Z}_q in unknowns $\{k_0, \dots, k_n\}$, where $k_i \in \mathbb{Z}_q$ denotes the i -th component of the secret key $K \in \mathbb{Z}_q^n$. Taking K as an input, Rubato's permutation is as follows:

$$P_N = NF \circ Fin_{r,N} \circ RF_{r-1,N} \circ \dots \circ RF_{1,N} \circ KSD_{0,N}$$

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where NF , Fin , RF , and KSD denote the adding noise, final round, round functions, and key scheduler, respectively. For each round $1 < i < r - 1$, the round function is defined as $RF_{i,N} = KSD_{i,N} \circ S_{fq} \circ MixRows \circ MixColumns$. Additionally, the final round function operates on the final round r as $Fin_{r,N} = Tr_{n,l} \circ KSD_{r,N} \circ MixRows \circ MixColumns \circ S_{fq} \circ MixRows \circ MixColumns$, where $Tr_{n,l} : \mathbb{Z}_q^n \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q^l$ is the truncation function. Same as HERA, the key scheduler denoted as $KSD_{i,N}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} + \mathbb{K} \odot \mathbf{rc}_i$, where $\mathbf{rc} \in (\mathbb{Z}_q^n)^{r+1}$. Finally, Gaussian noise is added to the output of the final round (x_1, \dots, x_l) as $NF(x) = (x_1 + e_1, \dots, x_l + e_l)$, where (e_1, \dots, e_l) are l elements sampled from a one-dimensional discrete Gaussian distribution. For a given message vector $\mathbf{m} \in (\mathbb{R}^l)^b$, Rubato encryption is defined as $c = \lfloor \Delta \cdot \mathbf{m} \rfloor + \mathbf{ks} \pmod q$, where $\mathbf{ks} \in (\mathbb{Z}_q^l)^b$ is the keystream of b -block generated by the Rubato cipher, and $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}$ is the scaling factor. Compared to Pasta and HERA, Rubato exhibits lower multiplicative depth and demands fewer random bits for linear layers.

10.2.4 Elisabeth

Elisabeth [56] is a stream cipher optimized for the TFHE scheme. It provides a variety of server-side operations for homomorphic evaluation, especially for neural network inference. It uses a Group Filter Permutator (GFP) paradigm. The filters in Elisabeth's design use the fewest levels possible of NLUT to parallelize computation efficiently. Taking $\mathbb{K} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^n$ as input, with q a power of two, Elisabeth's i -th keystream is as follows:

$$\mathbf{ks}_i = F(P_i(S_i(\mathbb{K})) + w_i),$$

where $S_i : \mathbb{Z}_q^n \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q^k$ is a subset extraction function that picks at random k elements in \mathbb{Z}_q^n , P_i is a random permutation and $w_i \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \mathbb{Z}_q^k$ is a random mask. $F : \mathbb{Z}_q^k \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q$ is the filter function, defined as:

$$F(x_1, \dots, x_k) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^{k/t} f(x_1, \dots, x_t)$$

with \bigoplus the direct sum over \mathbb{Z}_q , t a divisor of k , and $f : \mathbb{Z}_q^t \mapsto \mathbb{Z}_q$ a sequence of additions and NLUT evaluations. The choice of t and the definition of f are key parameters towards the optimization of Elisabeth stream cipher. We refer the reader to the complete analysis provided by Cosseron *et al.* [56] for more detail on the NLUT choices and the construction of f .

10.3 HHE Evaluation

We commence by examining the specifications of various HHE ciphers to provide a comprehensive overview of their distinct properties. Our analysis summarizes the implementation of each HHE scheme, based on the authors' claims and their support for open science. Subsequently,

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we assess the performance of three cutting-edge HHE schemes: PASTA, HERA, and Rubato, in a real-world setting, employing our implementation. The source codes for both the client and server sides are composed in Golang version 1.21.5, leveraging the Lattigo library [78] version 5.0.2. This library presently supports B/FV, BGV, and CKKS schemes. Our experiments were conducted in a single-threaded environment, with the client side operating on a laptop equipped with an Intel Core i5-9300H CPU @ 2.40GHz and 16GB memory, and the server side on a PC powered by an Intel Core i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz with 64GB memory.

Implementations of HHE Ciphers. As depicted in Table 11, a variety of HHE ciphers, each with different properties, have been proposed. Most of these ciphers are designed to operate with one or more HE schemes, depending on the plaintext space and data type. To incorporate these HHE ciphers into an HHE framework, it is necessary to implement the decryption circuit using a library that provides an Application Programming Interface (API) to support the requisite HE scheme. There are numerous libraries available for implementing HE schemes. We direct the reader to [79], where the authors have undertaken a thorough analysis of these diverse libraries to ascertain their respective strengths and weaknesses.

Table 11 – HHE Ciphers Properties

Cipher	Type	Supported HE	Security (bits)	Main Tool	Field
LowMC	Block	B/FV, BGV, TFHE	80, 128, 256	S-box	\mathbb{F}_2
Kreyvium	Stream	B/FV, BGV, TFHE	128	FP	\mathbb{F}_2
FLIP	Stream	B/FV, BGV, TFHE	80, 128	FP	\mathbb{F}_2
Rasta and Agrasta	Stream	B/FV, BGV, TFHE	80, 128, 256	S-box	\mathbb{F}_2
FiLIP	Stream	B/FV, BGV, TFHE	80, 128	FP	\mathbb{F}_2
Dasta	Stream	B/FV, BGV, TFHE	80, 128, 256	S-box	\mathbb{F}_2
Masta	Stream	B/FV, BGV	80, 128	S-box	\mathbb{F}_p
PASTA	Stream	B/FV, BGV	80, 128	S-box	\mathbb{F}_p
FASTA	Stream	B/FV, BGV	128	S-box	\mathbb{F}_2
HERA	Stream	CKKS	80, 128, 256	S-box	\mathbb{F}_p
Rubato	Stream	CKKS	80, 128	S-box	\mathbb{F}_p
Elisabeth	Stream	TFHE	128	FP	$\mathbb{F}_{16}, \mathbb{F}_2$
Chaghri	Block	BGV	128	S-box	\mathbb{F}_2

We have examined the available implementations for various HHE schemes to comprehend the proposed HHE framework and ensure the fairness of their experiments. Our findings, which are presented in Table 12, illustrate the availability of various cipher implementations that support open science, and it also compares these ciphers with their counterparts. As Table 12 illustrates, recent schemes such as PASTA, HERA, and Elisabeth are accompanied by open-source implementations, enabling comparisons with numerous other HHE schemes. The authors of PASTA provide a comprehensive framework named hybrid-HE-framework [80], which includes implementations for comparing 8 ciphers across three different libraries. The authors of HERA

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implemented their RtF-Transciphering framework [81] using the Lattigo library, providing implementations only for HERA and Rubato. However, they claim to compute comparison metrics with other works directly from the Dasta paper, which is *not* implemented in the same programming language, leading to an *unfair comparison*. The authors of Elisabeth used the Concrete Library to implement their scheme in Rust [82], implementing only the FiLIP cipher and using the results from PASTA’s benchmarking framework to compare their work with others. Our study reveals that among all these implementations, PASTA’s framework offers implementations for other schemes in the same language. However, they did not benchmark the symmetric cipher on a restricted device (client) and the HHE transciphering part on the server with a real-world setting and large data vectors. Elisabeth’s implementation encountered a similar issue. Likewise, the author of PASTA did not implement Rubato, which is claimed to be more efficient than HERA for client-side computations.

Table 12 – HHE Ciphers with Open-Source Implementation

Cipher	Comparison	Library	Language	Open-source
C1: LowMC	AES, PRINCE	HElib	C/C++	✓
C2: Kreyvium	C1, Trivium	HElib	C/C++	✗
C3: FLIP	C1, C2	HElib	C/C++	✗
C4: Rasta, Agrasta	C1, Trivium, C2, C3	HElib	C/C++	✓
C5: FiLIP	C1, C3, C4	HElib	C/C++	✗
C6: Dasta	C4	HElib	C/C++	✗
C7: Masta	C4	HElib	C/C++	✗
C8: PASTA	C1, C2, C4, C5, C6, C7, C9	HElib, SEAL, TFHE	C/C++	✓
C9: HERA	C1, C3, C4, C6, C7	Lattigo	Golang	✓
C10: Fasta	C4	HElib, TFHE, PALISADE	C/C++	✓
C11: Rubato	C7, C8, C9	Lattigo	Golang	✓
C12: Elisabeth	C1, C2, C5, C6, C7, C8, C9	Concrete	Rust	✓
C13: Chaghri	AES	HElib	C/C++	✗

✓ denotes that the implementation is open-source and available for benchmarking.

✗ denotes that the implementation is not publicly available.

Our HHE Benchmarking Approach. To the best of our knowledge, none of the existing HHE implementations are intended for use in real-world scenarios, with *independent* client and server implementations. Furthermore, past works’ comparisons have always been conducted on *powerful* devices with no resource constraints. To ensure a fair and realistic comparison, our implementation includes two primary components, client and server, that can be executed *independently*. We implemented PASTA in Lattigo and *reproduce* the results of the HERA and Rubato ciphers. Unfortunately, as Lattigo does not yet support TFHE, we could *not* implement Elisabeth and include it in our comparison. However, according to the comparison provided in the original paper [56], PASTA and HERA outperform Elisabeth regarding running time per bit for 128-bit security. We utilized the standard Golang benchmarking tool to evaluate several metrics of HHE schemes, such as average execution time, total memory allocation, and number of allocations per operation throughout each iteration of the benchmark function. A lower value

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for each metric is preferred to achieve an efficient scheme. To ensure a fair comparison, we provided parameters in [Table 13](#) that yield the same security level (128-bit). For simplicity, each set of parameters is named and will be used to present results.

In our implementation, the execution flow of HHE schemes is divided into five functions: *KeyGen*, *Encap*, *Enc*, *Decomp*, and *Relinearization* and *Rotation* (R&R) *KeyGen* (also known as halfboot keys in HERA and Rubato schemes). The first four functions are explained in [10.1](#). In principle, the R&R *KeyGen* is considered part of *KeyGen*; however, in practice, it operates on the *server-side* to produce the requisite keys for *Decomp*, due to its high resource consumption. The client uses *KeyGen*, *Encap*, and *Enc* to generate HE keys, then creates a master symmetric key K and encrypts it with the respected HE scheme. She then encrypts her data using K . Upon receiving encrypted data and homomorphically encrypted c_K , the server uses the R&R *KeyGen* and *Decomp* functions to *transcipher* symmetrically encrypted data into homomorphic data. This approach allows the server to perform HE operations on the data.

Client-Side: The results of the client-side experiment, including *keystream generation* and *encrypting* a vector of 128 plaintexts, are presented in [Table 14](#). The results indicate that Rubato outperforms HERA, PASTA-4, and PASTA-3 by an average factor of $1.2\times$, $42\times$, and $500\times$ respectively regarding running time per operation. Furthermore, Rubato surpasses PASTA-4 and PASTA-3 by an average factor of $710\times$ and $56\times$ respectively in terms of memory allocation per operation. However, it should be noted that Rubato consumes more memory per operation ($20\times$) than HERA while having a better number of allocations per operation for R3-2516 and R2-2516.

Table 13 – Benchmarking Parameters

Param	#Rounds	#Key (words)	#Blocks (words)	$\log_2 P$	$\log_2 N$
PASTA					
P3-1614	3	256	128	16	14
P3-3215	3	256	128	32	15
P3-6015	3	256	128	60	15
P4-1614	4	64	32	16	14
P4-3215	4	64	32	32	15
P4-6016	4	64	32	60	16
HERA					
H5-2816	5	16	16	28	16
H5-2516	5	16	16	25	16
Rubato					
R5-2616	5	16	12	26	16
R3-2516	3	36	32	25	16
R2-2516	2	64	60	25	16

Server-Side: The results of server-side experiments for PASTA, HERA, and Rubato are summarized in [Table 15](#), aligning with the metrics used on the client side. To ensure a fair comparison and maximize the potential of the HE scheme, random plaintext vectors of size N were

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Table 14 – Benchmark Results for Symmetric Ciphers

Param	Time (ms/op)	Memory Allocations (MB/op)	#Allocations (allocs/op)
P3-1614	35.892229	17.64820862	859835
P3-3215	42.308982	21.32488155	860274
P3-6015	49.060421	27.65648174	860290
P4-1614	2.910659	1.417246819	69212
P4-3215	3.405685	1.698161125	69222
P4-6016	3.964417	2.198654175	69257
H5-2816	0.075601	0.01574707	858
H5-2516	0.084632	0.01574707	858
R5-2616	0.143319	0.049766541	1229
R3-2516	0.084013	0.026374817	691
R2-2516	0.052809	0.017601013	483

generated, where N represents the maximum number of coefficients for the corresponding HE parameter set. The results reveal that for R&R KeyGen, PASTA-3 exceeds PASTA-4, HERA, and Rubato by an average factor of $3.1\times$, $5.2\times$, and $5.4\times$ in regards to running time. Likewise, PASTA-3 outperforms PASTA-4, Rubato, and HERA by an average of $3\times$, $7.8\times$, and $7.9\times$, respectively, in terms of memory allocation. However, Rubato surpasses HERA, PASTA-3, and PASTA-4 by an average factor of $1.1\times$, $15.7\times$, and $29.4\times$, respectively, in terms of running time. HERA outperforms Rubato, PASTA-3, and PASTA-4 by an average of $1.5\times$, $29.9\times$, and $35.6\times$ in memory allocation, respectively.

Overall Findings: Our comparison concentrated on memory allocation and execution time metrics for both client and server. While detailed results are available in [Figure 17](#) and [Figure 18](#), below is a summary of our key findings:

- F1.** Utilizing the **B/FV** scheme, PASTA variations perform faster and need less memory than HERA and Rubato variations for both KeyGen and Encap.
- F2.** In Enc , HERA marginally outperforms Rubato, while both surpass PASTA regarding execution time and memory utilization.
- F3.** The R&R KeyGen function appears to be more memory-intensive and time-consuming in HERA and Rubato than in PASTA.
- F4.** Rubato and HERA's Decomp function surpasses PASTA in execution time and memory consumption by a significant order of magnitude, respectively. The advantage is ascribed to their low multiplicative depth for the decryption circuit, data encoding techniques particularly when the **CKKS** is employed as the underlying HE scheme.
- F5.** We discovered an out-of-memory problem with **P4-6016**. As a result, our analysis excludes the server-side results for P4-6016. It is worth mentioning that these findings underscore a certain level of impracticality. More precisely, despite being on the server side and assuming unlimited resources, it is essential to acknowledge that these resources are paid for. Therefore, running these experiments in the cloud would incur significant costs, rendering

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it financially unsustainable for many users.

For a deeper understanding of these benchmarks please see [subsubsection 10.3.1](#).

Complexity. Initially, we intended to augment our experiments with a comprehensive comparison of the complexity of the examined schemes. We believed this would provide an additional, insightful metric for evaluating the efficiency of various HHE schemes. However, upon commencing the complexity analysis, we determined that a practical assessment is the only pertinent method to evaluate scheme efficiency. This observation may also explain why such an analysis is often absent in many HHE papers. This work does not cover the complexity of the protocols. While the theoretical complexity analysis can be meaningful to evaluate algorithms for arbitrary values, our implementation considers a narrow set of parameters suited for real-world use cases. Therefore, we believe that a practical analysis is the only relevant way to evaluate the efficiency of the schemes.

Open Science and Reproducible Research. To support open science and reproducible research and provide other researchers with the opportunity to use, test, and hopefully extend our implementation, the source codes used for our evaluations have been published online⁷.

10.3.1 Benchmarks

This section offers a comprehensive examination of the benchmarking metrics and results obtained from our implementation of the core three HHE schemes (PASTA, HERA, and RUBATO). We begin by elucidating the standard benchmark metrics provided by Golang. Subsequently, we delve into a detailed discussion of the results, focusing on the efficiencies and inefficiencies brought to light by our implementation of the underlying HHE schemes.

Golang Benchmarking Tool. Golang incorporates built-in tools for crafting comprehensive benchmarks, offering statistics for each run of a process. These statistics encompass the following metrics:

- M1.** *Average Latency* represents the average execution time per operation.
- M2.** *Memory allocation* indicates the total number of bytes allocated per operation on the heap.
- M3.** *Number of (memory) allocations* denotes the number of memory allocations required for each operation.

Average Latency. Latency refers to the duration of an operation from its initiation to either success or failure. Average Latency measures the average execution time per operation. The

⁷<https://github.com/hosseinabdin/HHESoK>

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benchmarking tool attempts to perform a sufficient number of test runs to meet the configured requirements for the number of runs or test time.

Memory Allocations. Memory blocks are the fundamental units of memory allocation, representing contiguous portions of memory. During runtime, a single memory block stores a valued chunk. A single memory block can hold many valued sections, ensuring that its size is equal to or greater than that of any portion it includes. When a memory block contains a valuable piece, the portion is said to reference the memory block. Memory allocation operations require CPU resources to locate the proper memory chunks. As a result, a rise in the number of memory blocks created for memory allocations corresponds to a higher CPU resource consumption. To optimize code execution performance, efforts should be made during the scheme's implementation to reduce excessive memory allocations [83]. Thus, measuring such a metric is critical for developing new memory-efficient HHE schemes.

Benchmarking Results. Following subsection 10.3, our implementation comprises two primary components for independently benchmarking the client and server sides. Pursuing the definition of HHE schemes in Definition 10.1, an HHE scheme consists of six algorithms: $KeyGen$, $Encap$, Enc , $Decomp$, $Eval$, and Dec . The client generates homomorphic key pairs using $KeyGen$. Then, the client performs $Encap$ that generates a symmetric master key K and encrypts it using the underlying HE scheme as $c_K = HE.Enc(pk, K)$ (supported HE schemes for each HHE scheme have been presented in Table 11). Subsequently, by running Enc function, it encrypts data using the symmetric HE-friendly cipher (e.g., PASTA, HERA, Rubato). Finally, the client transmits the symmetrically encrypted data and c_K to the server.

Upon reception of the encrypted data and c_K , the server generates the required keys for *Relinearization* and *Rotation* (R&R) (also known as halfboot keys in HERA and Rubato schemes). In theory, these are considered evaluation keys evk generated by the $KeyGen$ function. However, in practice, generating these keys depends on the data size (as it requires generating rotation indices and proper Galois Elements for Row and Column rotations), necessitating significant resources. Therefore, the R&R $KeyGen$ *must* be performed on the server side. In our implementation, we benchmarked it as a separate functionality on the server side. After generating R&R and evaluation keys, the server executes the $Decomp$ function to *transcipher* the symmetric ciphertexts into homomorphic ciphertexts by running the decryption circuit of the HE-friendly cipher. Finally, the server executes the $Eval$ function based on the user's application request and returns the results, which the user then decrypts through the Dec function.

Client side benchmarking. The primary objective of HHE schemes is claimed to be efficient computation and preventing ciphertext expansion on the client side, by proposing HE-friendly

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ciphers. To benchmark the client side we focused on the following: (1) measure the performance of the symmetric cipher (SKE) when encrypting data and (2) the symmetric cipher in combination with HE for the client side.

First, we conducted individual measurements of the SKE performance for each cipher, assessing its performance independently is crucial as it should function autonomously as an encryption scheme for $SKE.Enc()$. The results for symmetrically encrypting a vector of 128 plaintexts, illustrated in Table 14, reveal that Rubato outperforms HERA and PASTA. However, integrating the SKE with HE, the augmentation of data volume occurs on the client side. In our experiment, we opted to generate random plaintext vectors of size N , where N denotes the maximum number of coefficients, also referred to as the maximum number of slots for plaintext and ciphertext, corresponding to the HE parameters. To measure SKE combined with HE on the client side the following functions were performed and the outcomes are:

KeyGen: As presented in Figure 17, the PASTA scheme (not the symmetric cipher but the HHE scheme) outperforms HERA and Rubato regarding the average execution time. Similarly, Figure 18 shows that PASTA's KeyGen is more efficient than HERA and Rubato regarding memory consumption. The reason is that PASTA utilizes the B/FV scheme, which is more efficient than CKKS in key generation. CKKS requires careful parameter selection to balance security and performance, particularly regarding the precision of plaintext values and the modulus size. In contrast, B/FV may have more straightforward parameter selection requirements, leading to easier optimization and adequate performance.

Encap: The same applies to the Encap function, where the user encrypts K using the corresponding HE scheme because the homomorphic encryption function $HE.Enc$ in B/FV is more rapid than the one for CKKS. Therefore, as the average execution time and memory consumption of Encap depicted in Figure 17 and Figure 18, PASTA outperforms HERA and Rubato even by having a larger K .

Enc: As shown in Figure 17, the average execution time of Enc indicates that HERA cipher outperforms Rubato, and they both surpass PASTA by a significant margin. Likewise, as shown in Figure 18, HERA requires less memory allocation for data encryption compared to Rubato and PASTA. Note that running Enc using PASTA will significantly increase memory, CPU, and power consumption. After reviewing the benchmark results of the SKE presented in Table 14 and comparing it with the benchmark results of SKE combined with HE presented in Table 15, we came to the conclusion that Rubato is faster than the other schemes when using only SKE parameter sets. However, when dealing with large data and HE parameter sets, HERA is the fastest scheme for encrypting data.

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Server side benchmarking. Considering that using HHE schemes also increases server-side computation and memory consumption, understanding the resource consumption for and differences between the two primary functions HHE adds to the server side, namely R&R KeyGen and Decomp, is crucial.

R&R KeyGen: As illustrated in Figure 17, the process of generating R&R and evaluation keys is more efficient in different variations of PASTA than in HERA and Rubato due to the complexity of CKKS approximation. According to Figure 18, the HERA and Rubato schemes require significantly more memory allocation than PASTA due to the CKKS approximation's extensive set of evaluation keys.

Decomp: We presented the average execution time and memory consumption for performing Decomp in Figure 17 and Figure 18, respectively. The results indicate that Rubato and HERA schemes surpass PASTA by a significant order of magnitude. The advantage is ascribed to their low multiplicative depth for the decryption circuit, data encoding techniques, and the use of all coefficients in the ciphertext polynomial rings. The encoding techniques combined with transferring data from coefficient to slots and back for decoding in the CKKS scheme cause the evaluation of the symmetric circuit, the most expensive part of HHE schemes, to be more efficient. Finally, based on our analysis results presented in Table 15, it can be concluded that the Rubato and HERA schemes are more efficient than PASTA.

10.4 HHE Semantic Security

Within this part, we address the theoretical security of HHE construction. To do so, we recall the definition of semantic security for SKE schemes.

Definition 22 (Symmetric Indistinguishability-Based Security). *For an SKE scheme*

$SKE = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$ *a challenger* \mathcal{C} *and a PPT algorithm* \mathcal{ADV} , *define the following security game:*

SKE-IND-CPA Security

Initialize:

\mathcal{C} runs $K \leftarrow \text{Gen}(1^\lambda)$.

Challenge:

\mathcal{ADV} submits two messages m_0, m_1 and sends them to \mathcal{C} , who picks a random bit $\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, 1\}$. \mathcal{C} encrypts $c_\beta \leftarrow \text{Enc}(pk, m_\beta)$ and sends c_β to \mathcal{ADV} .

Guess:

\mathcal{ADV} outputs a guess $\beta' \in \{0, 1\}$ on the value of β with an advantage $\varepsilon(\lambda)$

SKE is said to be λ -SKE-CPA secure if and only if the advantage $\varepsilon(\lambda) = \left| \frac{1}{2} - \Pr[\beta' = \beta] \right|$ is

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Figure 17 – Execution Times of various functions for HHE schemes

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Figure 18 – Total Memory Allocation of various functions for HHE schemes

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Table 15 – Benchmark results for HHE schemes in full-coefficient mode

Param	Benchmark	Time (s/op)	Memory Allocations (MB/op)	#Allocations (allocs/op)
P3-1614	KeyGen	0.0397791	51.08751678	21873
	R&R KeyGen	7.287907	1808.771645	71191
	Encap	0.0265839	4.968841553	243
	Enc	3.7912274	2258.974701	110063048
	Decomp	780.66732	384619.065	91051940
P3-3215	KeyGen	0.0785246	101.573555	21877
	R&R KeyGen	27.1918257	6608.258629	99038
	Encap	0.0560374	9.921966553	243
	Enc	8.9038207	5453.794571	220208763
	Decomp	3269.26386	1532179.02	181687981
P3-6015	KeyGen	0.0793637	101.5717239	21872
	R&R KeyGen	27.0965226	6608.259872	99042
	Encap	0.0557442	9.921966553	243
	Enc	10.4351284	7079.774445	220202696
	Decomp	3278.80850	1533410.287	181062228
P4-1614	KeyGen	0.041437	51.08769989	21875
	R&R KeyGen	26.4933591	6206.03894	152984
	Encap	0.0251192	4.968841553	243
	Enc	1.2451438	725.6864471	35442042
	Decomp	1747.36410	550370.2523	55599409
P4-3215	KeyGen	0.0791121	101.5734787	21876
	R&R KeyGen	101.6135308	24378.86888	264367
	Encap	0.0532069	9.921966553	243
	Enc	2.8978117	1743.103241	70890711
	Decomp	7371.90987	2195520.681	110678564
H5-2816	KeyGen	1.1824637	1570.83329	375771
	R&R KeyGen	106.4032398	40065.93994	140442
	Encap	9.2174537	3818.448524	8531
	Enc	0.56478	125.0019531	6881377
	Decomp	179.68644	40091.24128	6509545
H5-2516	KeyGen	1.0762753	1427.113785	390495
	R&R KeyGen	110.6379293	39143.16187	136406
	Encap	8.6461869	3610.431923	8115
	Enc	0.57781	125.0019531	6881377
	Decomp	165.19297	36903.18815	6502104
R5-2616	KeyGen	1.0813324	1427.113632	390477
	R&R KeyGen	111.3192927	39143.16061	136400
	Encap	9.2465584	3610.431946	8116
	Enc	0.81869	324.5014648	7929929
	Decomp	91.76728	25918.47347	6452755
R3-2516	KeyGen	1.0676216	1427.111946	390487
	R&R KeyGen	110.9901145	39143.16535	136418
	Encap	20.9380585	8085.594765	18161
	Enc	1.24966	415.5039139	10682562
	Decomp	148.61062	56542.57570	9692901
R2-2516	KeyGen	1.0687663	1427.111885	390482
	R&R KeyGen	111.11005	39143.15746	136383
	Encap	36.6681119	14341.22204	32208
	Enc	1.66919	512.5073242	13631849
	Decomp	224.21408	98637.28681	12964543

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negligible. More generally, SKE is SKE-CPA secure if it is λ -SKE-CPA secure for a security parameter λ .

In Definition 23, we extend the classical definition of HE (mentioned in subsection 9.7) and SKE security to HHE. It requires introducing two security parameters λ, μ , the first for the HE scheme and the second for the symmetric cipher.

Definition 23 (HHE Indistinguishability-Based Security). *For an HHE scheme*

$\text{HHE} = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Encap}, \text{Enc}, \text{Decomp}, \text{Eval}, \text{Dec})$ *a challenger \mathcal{C} and a PPT algorithm \mathcal{ADV} , define the following game:*

HHE-IND-CPA Security

Initialize: \mathcal{C} runs $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk}) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ and $(K, c_K) \leftarrow \text{Encap}(1^\mu)$ and sends $\text{pk}, \text{evk}, c_K$ to \mathcal{ADV} .

Query: \mathcal{ADV} encrypts a polynomial number of chosen plaintexts with pk . Eventually, she submits two messages m_0, m_1 to \mathcal{C} .

Challenge: \mathcal{C} picks a random bit $\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, 1\}$, encrypts $c_\beta \leftarrow \text{Enc}(K, m_\beta)$, and sends c_β to \mathcal{ADV} .

Evaluation Query: \mathcal{ADV} encrypts a polynomial number of chosen plaintexts with pk . She then performs n evaluations for functions f_1, \dots, f_n with key evk and entries c_β and queried ciphertexts.

Guess: \mathcal{ADV} outputs a guess $\beta' \in \{0, 1\}$ on the value of β with an advantage $\varepsilon(\lambda, \mu)$.

HHE is said to be (λ, μ) -HHE-CPA secure iff the advantage $\varepsilon(\lambda, \mu) = \left| \frac{1}{2} - \Pr[\beta' = \beta] \right|$ is negligible. More generally, HHE is HHE-CPA secure if it is (λ, μ) -HHE-CPA secure for a couple of parameters λ and μ .

Finally, we provide the following Theorem 6 that ensures the theoretical security of HHE, given that HE and SKE are secure.

Theorem 6. *Let HHE be an HHE scheme built from an HE and an SKE scheme that are HE-CPA and SKE-CPA secure respectively. Then HHE is HHE-CPA secure.*

Proof. We demonstrate Theorem 6 with a sequence of games starting with the real HHE game and ending with a game where the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} is negligible. We denote ε_i the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} for game \mathcal{G}_i and $\varepsilon(\lambda)$ (resp. $\varepsilon(\mu)$) its advantage for the HE (resp. SKE) game.

\mathcal{G}_0 : This is the genuine HHE game described in definition 23. We consider that \mathcal{C} has chosen security parameters λ, μ so that HE is λ -HE-CPA secure and SKE is μ -SKE-CPA secure. At the end of the game, \mathcal{ADV} outputs a guess β' with an advantage ε_0 .

\mathcal{G}_1 : In this game, \mathcal{C} runs $(K, c_K) \leftarrow \text{Encap}(1^\mu)$ but does not send c_K to \mathcal{ADV} . Instead she generates a different symmetric key $K' \leftarrow \text{Gen}(1^\mu)$ and sends $c_{K'} \leftarrow \text{HE.Enc}(\text{pk}, K)$ to \mathcal{ADV} .

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The ciphertexts c_K and $c_{K'}$ are computed following the same distribution hence \mathcal{ADV} can not distinguish \mathcal{G}_0 from \mathcal{G}_1 . Additionally, \mathcal{ADV} is not able to gain information from the evaluation algorithm anymore. Indeed, $\text{Decomp}(\text{evk}, c_{K'}, c_\beta)$ outputs a valid element of HE ciphertext space, but an invalid encryption of m_β due to the replacement of K by K' . Therefore, any further computation outputs an erroneous result, that can not be detected as HE is IND-CPA. Finally, every homomorphic parameter pk, evk being unusable by \mathcal{ADV} , \mathcal{G}_1 is in fact the security game for SKE. Hereby, the overall advantage of \mathcal{ADV} is $\varepsilon(\mu)$, which is negligible. \square

10.5 Attacks on HHE

First, we summarize recent attacks on HE-friendly symmetric ciphers. Next, we explore three primary attack categories applicable to these ciphers: algebraic-based, differential-based, and linear-based attacks. Additionally, we discuss LWE-based attacks within the context of HHE frameworks. Finally, we present a concise summary of the security evaluation in [Table 16](#), covering each scheme's claims and recent attacks on state-of-the-art HHE schemes.

Attacks on HE-friendly ciphers. Initially resistant to both differential and linear cryptanalysis, LowMC encountered challenges, exposing vulnerabilities to algebraic attacks and linearization techniques [84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 51]. In [74], the authors demonstrated that an adversary can break the FLIP cipher using a guess-and-determine strategy based on a fixed internal state. Additionally, in their study [89], authors successfully executed trivial linearization attacks on Rasta and Dasta through algebraic cryptanalysis. Furthermore, a recent technique known as coefficient grouping [90] evaluated the algebraic degree of Chaghri, resulting in the breaking of its full 8-round with low complexity. The 4-round instance of Elisabeth fell victim to a known- IV linearization attack [91], leading to key recovery. Thereafter, Elisabeth's authors proposed a patch [92] to address security weaknesses. A new attack strategy, **SASTA** [93], utilizes Differential Fault Analysis (DFA) to break PASTA, achieving complete key recovery. SASTA extends to other HHE schemes, such as RASTA, MASTA, and HERA, resulting in a unique key recovery. Rubato remains secure against SASTA due to the addition of random noise from a Gaussian distribution to the keystream. However, in a recent study [94], authors showed that it is possible to overcome the noise by using a brute force attack. They then recovered the positions of keystream bits without introducing additional noise. As a result, the Rubato cipher became vulnerable to full-key recovery through a linearization attack. In their recent work, Meaux et al. [95] proposed a novel technique for conducting DFA attacks on the FLIP and FiLIP. This technique enables successful key recovery for both of these schemes. Importantly, the new approach is applicable to any filtering function, provided that only a limited number of keystream bits are involved.

Algebraic-based attacks. **Algebraic attacks** [96, 97] represent a class of cryptographic at-

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tacks that utilize an algebraic system of equations to extract the key stream. In such attacks, an attacker, armed with (plaintext/ciphertext) pairs, formulates key-stream outputs as multivariate polynomials over the secret key elements. The key can be recovered by solving this system of equations. Techniques for solving these algebraic systems span from simple linearization to sophisticated methods employing Gröbner bases. Our understanding of algebraic attacks on stream ciphers has been enhanced by recent proposals like the extreme algebraic attack [98], which shows significant applicability to ciphers such as FLIP and FiLIP. In the case of **Trivial Linearization**, the technique involves replacing all monomials with new variables, thereby transforming a system of polynomial equations into a linear form. The effectiveness of algebraic attacks can be influenced by the **Number of Monomials**, particularly when the cipher has a limited number of them. An attacker could resort to key guessing to decrease the number of monomials, thereby enhancing the likelihood of linearization and facilitating the solution of the system. The **Gröbner Basis Attack** [99, 100, 101] is a more advanced technique that solves a polynomial system by computing a Gröbner basis. Once the basis is computed, variables can be systematically eliminated by altering the order of monomials. Another strategy is the **GCD Attack** [77], which calculates the greatest common divisor (GCD) of univariate polynomials. This attack is typically used in ciphers that operate over a large field where the representation is a polynomial in a single variable. For multivariate polynomial equations, this attack can be extended by guessing all key variables except one. The **Guess and Determine Attack** [74] commences by *guessing* specific bits of the internal state or the key, and then uses information from keystream bits to *determine* the unknown bits. Assisted by algebraic attacks, guess-and-determine attacks are often feasible. In FP-based HHE schemes, such as FLIP, an adversary might employ a guess-and-determine strategy due to the use of a fixed internal state. Moreover, in schemes where the internal state remains constant, like FLIP and the register is unaltered, guessing a single bit at any moment can provide information about another bit at a different time. Additionally, the FP in these schemes is characterized by a limited number of high-degree monomials. The **Cube Attack** [102] is utilized to tackle the complex problem of solving multivariate systems of nonlinear equations over a finite field. The fundamental principle behind the cube attack lies in the observation that polynomial equations generated by many symmetric-key cryptosystems are not arbitrary and unrelated. Instead, they often originate from a single *master polynomial*, with *tweakable variables* that the attacker can set to any desired value during a chosen plaintext attack. Given a symmetric-key cipher with $n + m$ input bits of secret and public variables, the goal is to determine the algebraic normal form of the output over \mathbb{F}_2 , denoted by P . This normal form represents a sum of monomial products. The cube attack consists of two distinct phases: preprocessing and online. During preprocessing, the attacker can analyze the cipher by running it with various keys and plaintexts. Subsequently, in the online phase, the n secret values are set to unknown, allowing the attacker to assign val-

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ues to the m public variables as desired and evaluate P on the combined input. The **Integral Attack** [103] is used to predict the values in the integrals after a certain number of encryption rounds. For any multiset S comprising elements in \mathbb{F}_2^n , the integral over S is precisely defined as the sum of all its elements, denoted as $\bigoplus_{e \in S} e$. Integral attacks exploit the specific value obtained by integrating a function F over a carefully selected input set \mathcal{X} . This is mathematically expressed as the integral of $F(\mathcal{X}) : \bigoplus_{x \in \mathcal{X}} F(x)$. Notably, when \mathcal{X} forms a linear or affine subspace, this integral aligns with the value of a higher-order differential of the function.

Differential-based attacks. **Differential Cryptanalysis** [104] is a type of attack that uses chosen plaintexts and evaluates the probability of differentials, denoted by a pair (α, β) . Here, α is the difference between a pair of distinct inputs m_1 and m_2 , while β is a potential difference for the resulting outputs $c_1 = f(m_1)$ and $c_2 = f(m_2)$. The primary goal is to identify input pairs (m_1, m_2) with the same difference α that, upon encryption, yield output pairs (c_1, c_2) with the same difference β at an unusually high probability. A well-constructed differential can be used to mount distinguishing attacks and key recovery attacks on the cipher. Typically, the differential needs to cover all but one or a few rounds of the cipher to achieve this goal. **Truncated Cryptanalysis** [105, 106] is a generalization of Differential Cryptanalysis that focuses on differentials predicting only parts of an n -bit value, allowing the other bits to take any possible value. This is referred to as a *truncated differential*. More formally, if (α, β) represents an r -round differential, and α' is a subsequence of α while β' is a subsequence of β , then the pair (α', β') is termed an r -round truncated differential. **Boomerang Attack** [107] is a variant of differential cryptanalysis designed specifically for ciphers where identifying high-probability differentials is challenging. The Boomerang attack constructs a distinguisher with two short differentials (α_1, β_1) and (α_2, β_2) . Initially, it dissects the cipher $E : \mathbb{F}_2^n \times \mathbb{F}_2^k \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_2^n$ into two sub-ciphers denoted as $E = E_1 \circ E_2$. For an r -round block cipher, E_1 contains the first r_1 rounds, while E_2 handles the remaining $r_2 = r - r_1$ rounds. By combining these two differential characteristics, the Boomerang attack is effective against ciphers that might resist conventional differential cryptanalysis. This method has been successful in breaking ciphers previously thought to be secure against traditional differential cryptanalysis techniques. **Invariant Subspace (Trail) Attacks** [108, 109, 110] exploit a structural property inherent in block ciphers. Specifically, they leverage the property that a partition of the plaintext space into a set and its complement is preserved under the application of the block cipher. If an invariant subspace (V) exists for both the round function (F) and the key schedule function (f) , an invariant subspace trail attack can be effectively deployed to establish a rapid distinguisher and facilitate key recovery. By deriving round keys from a master key K as $(k_0, \dots, k_n) = f(K)$ and considering a coset $V \oplus a = \{v \oplus a \mid \forall v \in V\}$, where V is a subspace of a vector space W and a is an element of W , such that $F(V \oplus a) = V \oplus a'$; if the master key K resides in $V \oplus (a \oplus a')$, then it logically follows that $F(V \oplus a') \oplus K = V \oplus a$, allowing the derivation of an iterative invariant subspace. A

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subspace trail of length r is then essentially a set of $r + 1$ subspaces (V_1, \dots, V_{r+1}) that satisfy $F(V_i \oplus a_i) \oplus K \subseteq (V_{i+1} \oplus a_{i+1})$. **Higher-order Differential Cryptanalysis** [111] employs higher-order derivatives to extend Differential Cryptanalysis for deriving the secret key when more than two inputs are provided. As mentioned in [111], “if a (nontrivial) i -th derivative of $(r - 1)$ round function takes on a value with a high probability, then it is possible to derive the key for the last round from the known 2^i outputs and from the value of the anticipated derivative.” **Interpolation Attack** [112] involves determining the polynomial representation of a state bit. By combining knowledge about the restrictions of this polynomial with a sufficient number of evaluations of the polynomial function, the attacker reconstructs the polynomial representation using (plaintext/ciphertext) pairs through Lagrange interpolation. With the algebraic representation of the system as the function $f(x, k)$, linking the key-independent integral to the ciphertext x and the last round key k , interpolation attacks express f as a function of known ciphertext bits with unknown coefficients. This results in an equation of degree 1 in the unknown coefficients for any values of the ciphertext, recoverable by solving a linear system. The interpolation attack is commonly employed to exploit cryptographic algorithm vulnerabilities by scrutinizing the behavior of the polynomial functions used for generating cryptographic keys. **Differential Fault Analysis (DFA)** [113] is a physical attack where the attacker gains access to public information, such as nonce, IV , inputs, and outputs of the device running the cipher for a limited time. The attacker injects a fault into the cipher’s input to obtain a different result for the final state and then employs differential analysis to uncover the key. In [93], the author introduces a new DFA model, SASTA, tailored for HHE schemes. SASTA initially targets PASTA and subsequently achieves successful key recovery in other schemes like RASTA, MASTA, and HERA. Similarly, authors in [95] targeted the FLIP and FiLIP schemes with a DFA attack.

Linear-based attacks. **Linear Cryptanalysis** [114, 115] is a commonly used method for analyzing the security of a cipher. The cryptanalyst seeks to identify affine approximations of the cipher that hold with substantial accuracy. This process involves uncovering linear characteristics, which are sequences of linear approximations applied to consecutive rounds of the cipher. These linear characteristics significantly impact **S-boxes**, playing a crucial role in the approximations. Similar to differential cryptanalysis, linear cryptanalysis can be employed to initiate distinguishing and key recovery attacks. **Correlation Attacks** [116] are primarily applicable to stream ciphers for extracting information on secret key bits. These attacks, specifically key-recovery attacks, can be executed when a straightforward dependency between the keystream sequence $ks = (ks_0, ks_1, \dots, ks_n)$ and the state s or key K is identified. Typically, correlation attacks focus on state recovery, utilizing a single keystream sequence. In **Fast Correlation Attacks** [117], the approach involves attempting to discover a low-weight parity check polynomial of the linear part of the system, followed by the application of an iterative decoding procedure. Additionally, a category of correlation attacks targets filter generators [118], where the objec-

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tive is to invert the nonlinear function and recover the initial state. **Time-Memory Trade-Off (TMDTO) attacks** [119, 120] constitute a generic approach for the inversion of one-way functions, applicable to both stream and block ciphers. In the context of stream ciphers, vulnerability to TMDTO arises when the length of the IV is shorter than that of the key. Significantly, this vulnerability remains regardless of the size of the internal state. Additionally, chosen plaintext TMDTO presents a threat to block ciphers across various modes of operation. **Higher-Order Correlation Attacks** [121] primarily target stream ciphers and employ linear approximations of the output function to mount an attack on the cipher. The filtering function is approximated with a degree- d polynomial, and the corresponding algebraic system is solved using Gröbner basis algorithms. The efficiency of the attack depends on the closeness of the function to a degree- d polynomial. It can be integrated with guess-and-determine attacks, but its complexity consistently exceeds that of fast algebraic or correlation attacks. **Augmented Function attacks** [122] involve considering x as an n -bit internal state for a stream cipher, with an update function U and output function f producing a single bit of keystream in a single iteration. The augmented function $S_m : \mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}^m$ is then defined as $S_m(x) = (f(x), f(U(x)), \dots, f(U^{m-1}(x)))$. The update function may exhibit linearity, resembling a filter generator, or non-linearity. The output y corresponds to an m -bit block of the known keystream. The objective of this attack is to recover the initial state x through algebraic or correlation approaches, utilizing conditional equations $F_y(x) = 0$ of degree d for the output y of the augmented function S_m . This approach emphasizes multiple outputs of the function rather than a singular one, to identify coefficients that enable the exploitation of a relationship between the key and the outputs.

LWE-based attacks. In addition to symmetric cryptanalysis, as mentioned in [77], **LWE cryptanalysis** can also be applied to HHE frameworks. The naive approach for solving LWE hard problems is *exhaustive search*. The *meet-in-the-middle (MITM)* [123] approach, a variant of the TMDTO attack, can assist exhaustive search. Another method is the *primal attack* [124], which reduces the LWE problem to the unique-SVP through embedding and then employs lattice reduction techniques such as BKZ [125, 126] to find the shortest vector. Additionally, a *dual attack* [127, 128] can be utilized to distinguish between the uniform distribution and the modular discrete Gaussian over \mathbb{Z}_q . The *BKW-like Attack* [129] is a lattice version of Gaussian elimination parametrized by a and b . Assuming an LWE distribution $L_{\mathbf{s}, \chi}$, where $\chi = D_{\alpha q}$ is parameterized by dimension N and modulus q , the BKW attack first reduces A to a block diagonal matrix and then employs it to solve a lattice problem. The *Arora-Ge attack* proposed in [130] is an algebraic algorithm designed to solve the search-LWE problem. It leverages the idea that, given LWE samples $\{(\mathbf{a}_i, b_i)\}_i$, the errors fall into some interval $[-t\alpha q, t\alpha q]$ for a sufficiently large t , ensuring that the equations $\prod_{e=-t\alpha q}^{t\alpha q} (b_i - \langle \mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{s} \rangle - e) = 0$ hold.

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Table 16 – Security evaluation of HHE symmetric ciphers against common attacks

Attacks/Scheme	LowMC	Keyvrium	FLIP	Rasta	FILIP	Dasta	Masta	Pasta	FASTA	HERA	Rubato	Elisabeth	Chaghril
Algebraic Attacks	X	✓	X	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X
Trivial Linearization	X	*	*	*	*	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X
Number of Monomials	*	*	*	✓	*	*	✓	*	✓	*	*	X	*
Gröbner basis attack	X	*	*	✓	✓	*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	*	✓
GCD attack	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	✓	✓	✓	*	*
Differential Cryptanalysis	✓	✓	*	✓	*	*	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	*	*
Higher-order Differential Attacks	✓	*	*	✓	*	*	✓	✓	*	*	*	*	✓
Truncated Cryptanalysis	✓	*	*	*	*	✓	*	*	✓	✓	✓	*	✓
Cube Attack	✓	✓	✓	✓	*	*	✓	*	✓	✓	✓	*	*
Invariant Subspace Trail	X	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	✓	✓	*	✓
Linear Cryptanalysis	✓	*	*	✓	*	✓	✓	*	*	✓	✓	*	✓
Interpolation Attack	X	*	*	*	*	*	✓	*	✓	✓	✓	*	✓
Boomerang Attacks	✓	*	*	*	*	*	✓	*	*	*	*	*	*
Time-Memory Trade-Off (TMDTO)	*	✓	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Correlation attacks	*	*	✓	*	✓	*	*	*	*	*	*	✓	*
Guess and Determine Attacks	*	*	X	✓	✓	X	*	*	✓	*	*	✓	*
Augmented Function attacks	*	*	✓	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
BKW-like Attack	*	*	✓	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	✓	*	*
Differential Fault Analysis (DFA)	*	*	X	X	X	*	X	X	*	X	✓	*	*

✓ denotes that the scheme is resistant to that attack.

X denotes the vulnerability of the scheme to the attack.

* denotes that the authors did not claim security against the specified attack.

11 Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption Construction: GuardML

To make use of the benefits of HHE and show its overall efficiency and applicability, we applied the capabilities of PASTA in a PPML scenario. This led to the construction of GuardML, an efficient PPML application through HHE. Through this construction, we leverage HHE as the fundamental building block to enable secure learning of classification outcomes over encrypted data, all while preserving the privacy of the input data and the model itself.

With GuardML, we aimed to provide a tool, which allows analysis of one dimensional data through the use of PPML. As such, GuardML is a PPML protocol, which makes use of HHE to allow an Analyst (or doctor) to securely and privately analyse data, without it being directly revealed to them. Through this construction we provide a solution applicable to a variety of sensitive data analysis tasks, such as those in the healthcare sector.

11.1 System Model

In this subsection, we introduce our system model used in our two protocols, 2GML and 3GML, by explicitly describing our protocol's main entities and their capabilities.

- **User:** Let $\mathcal{U} = \{u_1, \dots, u_n\}$ be the set of all users. Each user generates a unique symmetric key K_i locally and encrypts their data. Then the generated ciphertexts are outsourced

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to the CSP along with an HE encryption c_{κ_i} of the underlying symmetric key.

- **Cloud Service Provider (CSP):** Primarily responsible for gathering symmetrically encrypted data from multiple users. The CSP is tasked with converting the symmetrically encrypted data into homomorphic ciphertexts and, upon request, performing blind operations on them.
- **Analyst (A):** In the 3GML protocol, there exists an analyst who owns an ML model and is interested in learning the output of ML operations on the encrypted data stored at the CSP. In this protocol, A decrypts the encrypted data from the HE evaluation of collected encrypted data and, thus, may gain insights from user data.

11.2 GuardML

In this subsection, we discuss in detail the construction of GuardML – our Hybrid Homomorphic Privacy-Preserving protocols that constitute the core of our contributions in HHE. GuardML is comprised of two protocols, 2GML and 3GML. The primary differences between the protocols mentioned above lie in the presence of an **analyst** and support for a **multi-user** scenario. Each protocol may be suitable for different use cases. For example, 2GML can be used in commercial ML applications where the **CSP**, such as AWS, Azure, etc., owns the ML models. While 3GML, on the other hand, would be ideal for a setting where the analyst is owner of the model and does not wish to reveal the contents to **CSP**. In this setting, the **CSP**'s role is reduced to simply performing operations on encrypted data and models.

Building Blocks: Before proceeding to describe each protocol, we first define the building blocks used in our constructions.

- A secure symmetric cipher $SKE = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$.
- A BFV-based HHE scheme $HHE = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec}, \text{Decomp}, \text{Eval})$.

Additionally, to provide secure communication, we define a public key encryption scheme, which supports message encryption and decryption, a signature scheme used for message signing and verification, and a secure cryptographic hash function to verify message integrity. We make the following assumptions:

- A CCA2 secure public-key encryption scheme $PKE = (\text{Gen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$.
- An EUF-CMA secure signature scheme $\sigma = (\text{sign}, \text{ver})$.
- A first and second pre-image resistant cryptographic hash function $H(\cdot)$.

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11.2.1 GuardML: 2-Party Setting

High-Level Overview: The first version of GuardML is 2GML – a 2-party protocol that consists of a CSP and a user u_i . In this setting, we assume that the CSP is the owner of a trained ML model with parameters (w, b) , while u_i provides the input data x_i to the model. Initially, the user u_i generates the necessary HHE keys $(pk_{u_i}, sk_{u_i}, evk_{u_i})$. It then publishes the public key pk_{u_i} and sends the evaluation key evk_{u_i} to the CSP. Subsequently, u_i generates a unique symmetric key K_i . On completing the key generation phase, u_i begins the data upload phase by first generating c_{K_i} , a homomorphic encryption of the symmetric key K_i , and then calculates a symmetric encryption of the data x_i with K_i . The data upload phase concludes with the sending of both ciphertext values to the CSP. Upon reception, the CSP begins the secure evaluation phase by first transforming the symmetrically encrypted data c_{x_i} into a homomorphic ciphertext c'_{x_i} . On successful run, CSP uses evk_{u_i} , c'_{x_i} and f to produce an encrypted prediction c_{res} . The encrypted result is then sent to u_i for decryption.

Formal Construction: Figure 19 provides an overview of the 2GML protocol, which is divided into four distinct phases, namely 2GML.Setup, 2GML.Upload, 2GML.Eval, and 2GML.Classify. Figure 19 shows the most relevant steps in our constructions, with some arbitrary steps, not being shown, to reduce clutter and provide a clearer image of our protocol's construction.

2GML.Setup: In the setup phase, both parties generate their respective signing/verification key pairs for the signature scheme σ and publish the verification keys. The **CSP** runs the PKE.Gen algorithm to generate a public/private key pair (pk_{CSP}, sk_{CSP}) . On the other hand, u_i runs the HHE.KeyGen algorithm to generate the public, private and evaluation keys $(pk_{u_i}, sk_{u_i}, evk_{u_i})$ used for HHE operations. Finally, u_i publishes pk_{u_i} and outsources evk_{u_i} to the **CSP** through m_1 .

$$m_1 = \langle t_1, \text{Enc}(pk_{CSP}, evk_{u_i}), \sigma_{u_i}(\text{H}(t_1 || evk_{u_i})) \rangle,$$

where σ_{u_i} is a signature created by u_i . Upon reception, the **CSP** verifies the signature by using u_i 's verification key and the freshness of the message through the timestamp. If the verification fails, the **CSP** aborts the protocol and outputs \perp . Otherwise, the **CSP** stores evk_{u_i} locally.

2GML.Upload: In this phase, u_i runs the HHE.Enc algorithm to generate a symmetric encryption key K_i through SKE.Gen and then encrypts the plaintext data x_i into ciphertext c_{x_i} using the SKE.Enc algorithm, which takes (K_i, x_i) as an input. After encrypting the data, u_i also runs HE.Enc to homomorphically encrypt K_i into c_{K_i} with their pk_{u_i} . After both encryptions are finished u_i sends both ciphertexts to the **CSP** with m_2 :

$$m_2 = \langle t_2, c_{x_i}, c_{K_i}, \sigma_{u_i}(\text{H}(t_2 || c_{x_i} || c_{K_i})) \rangle,$$

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On receiving m_2 , the **CSP** verifies the signature by using u_i 's verification key and the freshness of the message through the timestamp. If the verification fails, the **CSP** aborts the protocol and outputs \perp . Otherwise, the **CSP** continues to the secure evaluation phase.

2GML.Eval: The secure evaluation phase begins with the **CSP** transforming the received symmetric ciphertext c_{x_i} into HE ciphertext c'_{x_i} by running the HHE.Decomp algorithm. HHE.Decomp uses HE.Eval which takes as an input $(\text{evk}_{u_i}, \text{SKE.Dec}, c_{K_i}, c_{x_i})$, where SKE.Dec is the symmetric cipher decryption algorithm to transform the ciphertext. Afterwards, the **CSP** takes c'_{x_i} and their ML model parameters (w, b) and inputs both of them into the HHE.Eval along with the evk_{u_i} to compute an encrypted prediction c_{res} from the encrypted data. Finally, the **CSP** securely sends the encrypted result back to u_i via m_3 :

$$m_3 = \langle t_3, c_{res}, \sigma_{CSP}(\text{H}(t_3 || c_{res})) \rangle,$$

Upon reception, u_i verifies the integrity and the freshness of the message. If the verification fails, u_i aborts the protocol and outputs \perp . Otherwise, continues to the final phase.

2GML.Classify: In the final phase of the protocol, u_i decrypts the received ciphertext to gain insight into the data. This is done by u_i running the HHE.Dec algorithm with inputs sk_{u_i}, c_{res} and outputs the prediction res .

11.2.2 GuardML: 3-Party Setting

High-Level Overview: We note that 2GML is unsuitable for multi-user scenarios, where data is collected from multiple users and stored at the **CSP**. In such a scenario, each user would be required to generate a unique set of HHE keys, while the **CSP** would need to store the evk_{u_i} of each user to run the protocol successfully. To resolve this, we present 3GML – an extended version of 2GML for the multi-client model. 3GML consists of three parties: a set of users \mathcal{U} , **CSP**, and an analyst **A**. The protocol's steps are primarily the same as in 2GML (subsubsection 11.2.1). The fundamental distinction is that under the three-party setting, the HHE keys are generated by **A** instead of u_i . In the 3GML setting, we assume that an analyst **A** owns the ML model with parameters (w, b) , while a user u_i provides the data x_i . **A** generates the required HHE keys $(\text{pk}_A, \text{sk}_A, \text{evk}_A)$, publishes pk_A , and sends evk_A to the **CSP**. Each u_i generates a symmetric key K_i and encrypts their data x_i locally to output a symmetric ciphertext c_{x_i} . Additionally, u_i also generates c_{K_i} – a homomorphic encryption of the symmetric key K_i using **A**'s public key and sends both the encrypted data c_{x_i} and c_{K_i} to the **CSP**. Upon reception, the **CSP** stores the values locally. In the evaluation phase, **A** can request a prediction to be performed on the stored c'_{x_i} by first sending to the **CSP** their homomorphically encrypted pre-trained ML model parameters (c_w, c_b) . On receiving the request from **A**, the **CSP** transforms c_{x_i} into homomor-

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Figure 19 – 2GML

phic ciphertext c'_{x_i} . **CSP** produces an encrypted result c_{res} and sends the results back to **A**. Finally, **A** decrypts the prediction result res using sk_A .

Formal Construction: The overall flow of the protocol remains the same as in the two-party protocol. Figure 20 provides a visual overview of the protocol.

3GML.Setup: Each party generates their respective signing/verification key pair for the signature scheme σ and publishes the verification keys. **A** executes the HHE.KeyGen algorithm to output the public, private and evaluation keys (pk_A, sk_A, evk_A) . The steps of the phase are summarized below.

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Figure 20 – 3GML

<p>u_i computes:</p> $(pk_{u_i}, sk_{u_i}) \leftarrow \text{PKE.Gen}(1^\lambda)$	<p>A computes:</p> $(ver_A, sign_A) \leftarrow \text{PKE.Gen}(1^\lambda),$ $(pk_A, sk_A, evk_A) \leftarrow \text{HHE.KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$
<p>CSP computes:</p> $(pk_{CSP}, sk_{CSP}) \leftarrow \text{PKE.Gen}(1^\lambda)$	

A then publishes pk_A and sends evk_A to **CSP** via m_1 .

$$m_1 = \langle t_1, \text{Enc}(pk_{CSP}, evk_A), \sigma_A(H(t_1 || evk_A)) \rangle$$

3GML.Upload: With the three-party setting, there can be multiple users, namely $u_i \in \mathcal{U}$. Hence, each u_i independently runs HHE.Enc, to generate a unique symmetric key K_i through SKE.Gen. Then, u_i encrypts their data by computing SKE.Enc, which takes K_i and x_i as input and outputs c_{x_i} . Additionally, each u_i homomorphically encrypts its symmetric key K_i using

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HE.Enc with inputs pk_A and K_i and output c_{K_i} . The steps of this phase are summarized as:

$$\begin{aligned} K_i &\leftarrow \text{SKE.Gen}(1^\lambda), \\ \text{SKE.Enc}(K_i, x_i) &\rightarrow c_{x_i}, \\ c_{K_i} &\leftarrow \text{HE.Enc}(pk_A, K_i) \end{aligned}$$

Finally, u_i sends the encrypted values (c_{x_i} and c_{K_i}) through m_2 .

$$m_2 = \langle t_2, c_{x_i}, c_{K_i}, \sigma_{u_i}(\text{H}(t_2 || c_{x_i} || c_{K_i})) \rangle$$

3GML.Eval: The secure evaluation phase in the three-party protocol is initiated by **A** to gain insight into the data provided by any user u_i . First, **A** homomorphically encrypts their ML model parameters (w, b) by running the HE.Enc algorithm, which takes as input $(pk_A, (w, b))$ and outputs encrypted parameters (c_w, c_b) . **A** then sends m_3 to the **CSP** (Figure 20). Upon receiving the encrypted model, the **CSP** transforms c_{x_i} into homomorphic ciphertext c'_{x_i} by running the HHE.Decomp algorithm which takes as input evk_A, c_{x_i} , and c_{K_i} , and outputs c'_{x_i} . Subsequently, the **CSP** runs the HHE.Eval algorithm, which takes as input $(evk_A, (c_w, c_b), c'_{x_i})$ to output an encrypted prediction c_{res} . Afterwards, c_{res} is sent through m_4 . The phase is summarized below.

A computes:

$$(c_w, c_b) \leftarrow \text{HE.Enc}(pk_A, (w, b)),$$

CSP computes:

$$\begin{aligned} c'_{x_i} &\leftarrow \text{HHE.Decomp}(evk_A, c_{x_i}, c_{K_i}), \\ c_{res} &\leftarrow \text{HHE.Eval}(evk_A, (c_w, c_b), c'_{x_i}) \end{aligned}$$

$$m_3 = \langle t_3, (c_w, c_b), \sigma_A(\text{H}(t_3 || (c_w, c_b))) \rangle$$

$$m_4 = \langle t_4, c_{res}, \sigma_{CSP}(\text{H}(t_4 || c_{res})) \rangle$$

11.3 Threat Model and Security Analysis

In this subsection, we define the threat model used to prove the security of GuardML by formalizing the capabilities of an adversary \mathcal{ADV} . The PASTA [131] scheme we adopt as our underlying cryptographic scheme has been proven to be resilient against differential and linear statistical attacks and their variations. The cipher construction incorporates changing linear

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layers during encryption, which ensures defence against statistical attacks. The authors provide rigorous proof that this layer instantiation is secure, ensuring full diffusion throughout the entire scheme, even in the best-case scenario for an attacker [131]. PASTA is also secure against algebraic attacks, such as Linearization and Gröbner Basis Attacks. To this end, we define a threat model focusing on the communication between entities in our protocols and not the underlying scheme itself. We consider a powerful adversary \mathcal{ADV} capable of performing a variety of attacks aiming at breaking the security and privacy of the protocols. In general, \mathcal{ADV} is capable of corrupting any number of users and the **CSP**. However, for 3GML, we assume that **A** does not collude with the **CSP**. Additionally, we assume that each entity can verify the owner of a public key. With this assumption, we eliminate the possibility of basic man-in-the-middle attacks. From these definitions and assumptions, we present the following possible attacks:

Attack 3 (Ciphertext Substitution Attack). *Let \mathcal{ADV} be a malicious adversary. \mathcal{ADV} successfully launches a Ciphertext Substitution Attack if she manages to replace the generated ciphertexts sent by any entity in an indistinguishable way.*

Attack 4 (ML Model Unauthorized Access Attack). *Let \mathcal{ADV} be a malicious adversary. \mathcal{ADV} successfully launches the ML model unauthorized access attack if she manages to learn information about the underlying ML model utilized by either the **CSP** or the analyst **A**.*

11.3.1 Security Analysis

We now prove the security of our protocols in the presence of the adversary defined in 11.3.

Proposition 1 (Ciphertext Substitution Attack Soundness). *Let σ be an EUF-CMA secure signature scheme and PKE an INC-CPA public key encryption scheme. Then \mathcal{ADV} , cannot successfully launch the Ciphertext Substitution Attack against GuardML.*

Proof. To successfully perform the Ciphertext Substitution Attack, \mathcal{ADV} needs to successfully attack the 2GML/3GML.Upload, 2GML.Eval or 3GML.Eval phase of GuardML by substituting the actual ciphertexts with a sequence of \mathcal{ADV} generated ciphertexts. To this end, we categorize the attacks into the following cases:

Option 1 (2GML/3GML.Upload): When a user u_i outsources data to the **CSP** via $m_2 = \langle t_2, c_{x_i}, c_{K_i}, \sigma_{u_i}(H(t_2 || c_{x_i} || c_{K_i})) \rangle$, \mathcal{ADV} needs to replace c_{x_i} with c'_{x_i} and c_{K_i} with c'_{K_i} . By successfully performing this attack, \mathcal{ADV} can control the outcome of a query to the **CSP** to manipulate **A**. To do this, \mathcal{ADV} must:

- Generate a symmetric key $K_{\mathcal{ADV}}$;
- Use $K_{\mathcal{ADV}}$ to generate a series of ciphertexts c' ;

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- Encrypt K_{ADV} with pk_A or pk_{u_i} to get $c'_{K_{ADV}}$;
- Tamper with m_2 in an indistinguishable way.

The first three tasks are straightforward to achieve. Additionally, substituting c_{x_i} with c'_{x_i} and c_{K_i} with c'_{K_i} in the non signature part of m_2 is trivial. However, both c_{x_i} and c'_{x_i} are included in the signature; hence, successfully substituting the terms is equivalent to forging u_i 's signature. Given the EUF-CMA security of the signature scheme σ , this can only happen with negligible probability in the security parameter λ of σ .

Option 2 (2GML.Eval): When **CSP** returns the results of a secure classification to u_i via $m_3 = \langle t_3, c_{res}, \sigma_{CSP}(H(t_3 || c_{res})) \rangle$, ADV needs to replace c_{res} with c'_{res} for this instance of the attack to be successful. More specifically, since c_{res} is encrypted with pk_{u_i} , ADV simply encrypts fictitious results res' with pk_{u_i} to produce c'_{res} . However, c_{res} is included in the signature part of m_3 ; hence tampering with m_3 requires forging the signature of **CSP**. Given the EUF-CMA security of the signature scheme σ , this can only happen with negligible probability.

Option 3 (3GML.Eval): When **A** initiates secure classification via $m_3 = \langle t_3, (c_w, c_b), \sigma_A(H(t_3 || (c_w, c_b))) \rangle$, and **CSP** responds with the secure evaluation via $m_4 = \langle t_4, c_{res}, \sigma_{CSP}(H(t_4 || c_{res})) \rangle$, ADV needs to replace (c_w, c_b) with (c'_w, c'_b) and c_{res} with c'_{res} to successfully perform this attack. The proof for this attack is similar to the one provided for the attack on 2GML.Eval with the only difference being that ADV attacks both m_3 and m_4 instead of just m_3 . Using the same reasoning (i.e., the negligible probability of forging the signature), we conclude that ADV has a negligible probability of tampering with m_3 and m_4 ; hence this attack fails.

□

Proposition 2 (ML Model Unauthorized Access Attack Soundness). *Let f be a multi-layered ML model and HE semantically secure encryption scheme. Then ADV cannot successfully launch the ML Model Unauthorised Access attack for any of the GuardML protocols.*

Proof. To successfully launch the ML Model Unauthorized Access attack, ADV must collude or corrupt multiple entities in GuardML depending on the use case. More specifically, ADV can either attack 2GML by colluding with multiple users $(u_j)_{j \in S}$ where $S \subseteq [n]$ or attack 3GML by colluding with a user u_i and the **CSP**. To this end, we distinguish the attack into the following;

Option 1 (Attacking 2GML): Let f be a multi-layered ML model owned by **CSP**, and assume that ADV colludes with $n' = \text{card}(S)$ users. On completion of the secure evaluation

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phase (Figure 19), each user receives $res_i = f(x_i)$, where x_i is the input from the user. \mathcal{ADV} successfully launches this attack if with the help of the n' colluding users, \mathcal{ADV} can solve for f given $(res_j)_{j \in S}$ and $(x_j)_{j \in S}$. With the assumption that f is a multi-layered ML model, the likelihood of this attack is negligible.

Option 2 (Attacking 3GML): Let f be a multi-layered ML model owned by **A** with (c_w, c_b) as the HE encrypted parameters sent to **CSP** via $m_3 = \langle t_3, (c_w, c_b), \sigma_A(\mathcal{H}(t_3 || (c_w, c_b))) \rangle$. \mathcal{ADV} successfully launches this attack if given a corrupt user u_i and a corrupt **CSP**, \mathcal{ADV} successfully retrieves f in the form of (w, b) . HE has been proven semantically secure; hence, the likelihood of \mathcal{ADV} decrypting the ciphertext (c_w, c_b) is considered negligible.

□

11.4 Experiments

In this subsection, we report the process and results of building a privacy-preserving inference protocol on sensitive medical data (ECG), named `ecgPPML`, based on our 3GML construction (subsubsection 11.4.1). Additionally, we provide an extensive overview of our PPML application as well as the dataset we use to gain our experimental results (subsubsection 11.4.2). Subsequently, we extensively evaluated the computational performance of the 2GML and 3GML protocols (subsubsection 11.4.3). For these evaluations, we utilized a dummy dataset where each data input was a vector of four random integers, and the weights and biases were also integer vectors of length four. Finally, to provide concrete evidence of the efficiency of our protocols, we compared the performance of our constructions against a basic BFV HE scheme (subsubsection 11.4.4). For these experiments, our primary testbed was a commercial desktop with a 12th Generation Intel i7-12700 CPU with 20 cores and 32GB of RAM running on an Ubuntu 20.04 operating system. Furthermore, in all the evaluations, we utilized the SEAL cryptographic library⁸ for basic HE operations and PASTA library⁹ to implement the secure symmetric cipher. To ensure statistical significance, each experiment was repeated 50 times, with the average results considered to provide a comprehensive overview of the performance of each algorithm under evaluation. We provide our implementation online^{10,11}.

⁸<https://github.com/microsoft/SEAL>

⁹<https://github.com/IAIK/hybrid-HE-framework>

¹⁰https://github.com/iammrgerie/hhe_ppml

¹¹<https://github.com/khoaguin/PocketHHE>

11.4.1 PPML Application

In the first phase of our evaluations, we demonstrated the real-world applicability of our 3GML protocol by applying it to a PPML application with a sensitive heartbeat dataset to classify whether a heartbeat is subjected to heart disease or not. More specifically, we employed the MIT-BIH dataset [132], which is a dataset of human heartbeats obtained from 47 subjects from 1975 to 1979.

Figure 21 – Example heartbeats from the MIT-BIH dataset.

11.4.2 MIT-BIH dataset

In total, the dataset contains 48 half-hour excerpts of two-channel ECG recordings. We used the processed ECG data from [133], which contains a train split and a test split, each comprising 13,245 ECG examples that belong to five classes: normal heartbeat (N), right bundle branch block (R), left bundle branch block (L), atrial premature contraction (A), ventricular premature contraction (V). Each ECG example is a float 1D time series signal of length 128 with values in the range of $[0, 1]$. We further grouped all ECG examples from the later four classes (L, R, A, V) into one super-class called “diseased heartbeats” (Figure 21). By doing so, we simplified our problem into a binary classification problem. Based on the input ECG signal, we tried to classify if it was a normal or diseased heartbeat. As previously discussed, our HHE protocols are based on the BFV scheme, which only works with integer data and arithmetic. However, our ECG data are floating-point numbers in the range of $[0, 1]$, and normally, training neural networks also produce models with weights and biases in floating-point numbers. To this end, we first quantized the ECG data into 4-bit integer data with values in the range of $[0, 15]$ (Figure 22).

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Figure 22 – Quantizing ECG data into 4-bit integers. Top: Floating-point ECG data. Bottom: Corresponding quantized ECG data.

On preparing the data, we trained a simple neural network with one fully connected (FC) layer with a sigmoid activation function on the floating-point ECG dataset. The neural network can be written as $f(\theta) = \text{sigmoid}(wx + b)$, where $\theta = (w, b)$ are the model's weights and biases, and x is the training data. For the integer ECG data, we used the PocketNN framework [134] to train the same neural network in integer arithmetic. In both cases, we trained until the models' predictive accuracy on the test data split no longer improved. Training in floating-point arithmetic produced the best train accuracy of 89.36% at epoch 482 and the best test accuracy of 88.93% at epoch 500. With respect to training in integer arithmetic, we got the best train accuracy of 86.65% at epoch 42 and the best test accuracy of 87.06% at epoch 31. From these results, we observed that the test accuracy of the integer neural network was only 1.87% lower than the test accuracy produced by the floating-point neural network. Note that when training in integer arithmetic, we constrained the values of the weight and biases to be in the range of $[-2047, 2048]$, or $[-2^{11} + 1, 2^{11}]$. The reason for this is that the HHE protocol works in \mathbb{Z}_q where $q = 2^{16} + 1$; therefore, all computation results need to be in the range of $[-2^{15} + 1, 2^{15}]$; otherwise they will be wrapped around by the modulo operation and produce incorrect predictions. As mentioned above, our ECG data are 4-bit integers and in the range

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of $[0, 2^4 - 1]$. In the 1 FC neural network, we needed to do one encrypted element-wise matrix multiplication between the data and the weights, and hence, if the weights are in $[-2^{11} + 1, 2^{11}]$, the results will be constrained in $[-2^{11} + 1, 2^{11}] \times 2^4 = [-2^{15} + 2^4, 2^{15}] \approx [-2^{15} + 1, 2^{15}]$, which is what we needed. After training and getting the trained integer model, we built `ecgPPML` – a privacy-preserving inference protocol on the quantized integer ECG data based on our 3GML protocol construction and ran the experiments with the results reported below.

To begin our evaluations, we ran the encrypted inference protocol on a different number of examples from the test split, then compared the predictions with the ground-truth outputs to get the encrypted test accuracy. For each experiment, we also made inferences on plaintext ECG data in floating point and integer arithmetic to compare the results. [Table 17](#) shows the encrypted and plaintext accuracies on a different number of data inputs. Overall, the accuracy of plaintext inference in integer arithmetic is very similar to encrypted inference accuracies. When the number of input examples is low (1-500), integer arithmetic and encrypted accuracies are comparable or even higher than plaintext floating-point inference. When the number of data inputs increases (1000-2000 examples), plaintext integer and encrypted inference produce slightly lower accuracies (0.5-0.8% lower). For 1000-2000 input data samples, encrypted inference had higher accuracy than plaintext integer inference but with a minimal margin (0.1-0.15%). We note that this is due to HE noise which helps make a few more correct predictions.

Data Inputs	Plaintext (Float)	Plaintext (Integer)	Encrypted
1	100 %	100 %	100 %
10	90 %	90 %	90 %
20	90 %	95 %	90 %
50	88 %	92 %	90 %
100	86 %	91 %	90 %
500	87 %	87.2 %	86.8 %
1000	87.9 %	87.3 %	87.4 %
2000	88.2 %	87.4 %	87.55 %

Table 17 – Accuracy Analysis – `ecgPPML`

Subsequently, we evaluated the computational overhead of the `ecgPPML` protocol ([Table 18](#)). In the integer and float plaintext inference protocol, the client and analyst are not required to perform any computation as they outsource all their data and neural network model to the CSP. Therefore, in [Table 18](#), the client and analyst only have a single column for the encrypted inference results. Looking at these results (i.e. across all data input examples for the encrypted inference protocol), we observed that the CSP is responsible for the most computational overhead (99% or even more), which increased linearly with the number of data inputs. Compared to plaintext inference, encrypted inference is more computationally expensive. However, encrypted inference for one data sample takes 12.18 seconds on a commercial desktop, which is a promising result. Furthermore, these experimental results align with our goal and expect-

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tation for the HHE protocol, as we want the client and analyst to do minimal work, and most of the computations take place in the CSP. Finally, we analyzed the communication cost of the `ecgPPML` protocol and reported the results in [Table 19](#). For the communication between the client and the CSP, we observed that when the number of data inputs was low (1-500), the encrypted communication cost was very high compared to the plaintext costs due to the size of the HE ciphertext of the symmetric key (1.8 Mb). However, once the number of input examples increased, the size of the symmetrically encrypted data being sent to the CSP increased linearly, similar to the plaintext size, making this difference unimportant. There is no communication between the client and the analyst in plaintext protocols, while in the encrypted inference protocol, the client only transfers the HE public key to the analyst, which has a fixed size of 2.06 Mb. Overall, the communication cost for the client was minimal and increased linearly with the number of data inputs submitted to the CSP. The communication cost between the analyst and CSP was also minimal for plaintext inference since the plaintext weights, biases, and results were small. On the other hand, the majority of the communication cost for the encrypted inference protocol was incurred between the analyst and CSP. This increased cost is caused by the HE-encrypted output of the linear layer that needs to be sent from the CSP to the analyst. Hence, if the number of data inputs increases, the communication cost between the analyst and CSP will increase linearly. We observed that the communication cost for 2000 data input examples is 5548.21 Mb, or about 5 Gb of data, which is a reasonable result for today's internet bandwidth.

Data Inputs	Client	Analyst	CSP		
	Encrypted	Encrypted	Plaintext (float)	Plaintext (integer)	Encrypted
1	0.16	0.52	0	0.23	12.18
10	0.18	0.58	0	0.24	120.44
20	0.2	0.63	0	0.23	241.21
50	0.27	0.803	0	0.25	601.95
100	0.4	1.091	0	0.24	1212.38
500	1.31	3.38	0.05	0.24	6021.98
1000	2.46	6.2	0.1	0.25	12058.2
2000	4.8	11.92	0.2	0.27	24153.5

Table 18 – Computation Analysis – `ecgPPML`. (all numbers in Seconds)

These experimental results show that our `ecgPPML` protocol produces comparable results in accuracy compared to inference on plaintext data. Furthermore, the CSP is responsible for most of the computation costs, and the majority of communication costs also occur between the CSP and the analyst. These results align with our vision of using HHE for PPML applications and show the potential for HHE when applied in real-world PPML applications.

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Data Inputs	Client - CSP			Client - Analyst	Analyst - CSP		
	Plaintext (float)	Plaintext (integer)	Encrypted	Encrypted	Plaintext (float)	Plaintext (integer)	Encrypted
1	0.0002	0.0002	1.8	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	72.46
10	0.002	0.002	1.8	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	97.11
20	0.005	0.005	1.81	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	124.51
50	0.012	0.012	1.81	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	206.692
100	0.029	0.029	1.83	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	343.643
500	1.1	1.1	2.9	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	1439.27
1000	2.3	2.3	4.1	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	2809.02
2000	4.6	4.6	6.4	2.06	0.0017	0.000734	5548.21

Table 19 – Communication Analysis – ecgPPML. (all numbers are in Megabytes)

11.4.3 Computational Analysis

This subsection focused on the computational performance of the core algorithms executed by each entity in the 2GML and 3GML protocols. More precisely, we measured the time taken to execute each HHE algorithm in each protocol phase by the responsible party. For both the 2GML.Setup and 3GML.Setup phases, we observed the time taken to generate a set of HHE keys for the user and the analyst, respectively. For implementation purposes, the HHE.KeyGen algorithm involved the generation of encryption parameters $parms$, secret key sk , public key pk , relinkey rk , and a Galois key gk , and took 243 milliseconds to execute. Subsequently, in the 2GML.Upload and 3GML.Upload phases, we measured the time taken to homomorphically encrypt a symmetric key K using the HE.Enc and the time taken to execute the SKE.Enc for various inputs ranging from 1 to 300 (each input is an integer vector of length 4). HE.Enc took 7 milliseconds to run. For a single data input, SKE.Enc executed in 2 milliseconds and 600 milliseconds for 300 data inputs (Table 20).

Inputs	SKE.Enc	HHE.Decomp	HHE.Eval (2P)	HHE.Eval (3P)	HHE.Dec
1	2 ms	11.9 s	7 ms	0.038 s	3 ms
50	100 ms	599.1 s	350 ms	1.96 s	150 ms
100	200 ms	1197.7 s	700 ms	3.93 s	300 ms
150	300 ms	1794.5 s	1050 ms	5.77 s	450 ms
200	400 ms	2394.2 s	1400 ms	7.69 s	600 ms
250	500 ms	2989.2 s	1750 ms	9.61 s	750 ms
300	600 ms	3595.6 s	2100 ms	11.61 s	900 ms

Table 20 – Computational Analysis

When evaluating the 2GML.Eval phase; we measured the cost of executing the HHE.Decomp algorithm for various numbers of symmetric ciphertexts from 1 to 300, and the cost of executing the HHE.Eval algorithm for various homomorphic ciphertexts (1 to 300). For a single input,

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HHE.Decomp took 11.9 seconds, while HHE.Eval took 7 milliseconds. On the other hand, for 300 inputs, HHE.Decomp took 3595.6 seconds, while HHE.Eval took 2100 milliseconds (Table 20). When evaluating 3GML.Eval, we first measured the performance of HE.Enc at **A** and then the performance of the HHE.Decomp and HHE.Eval algorithms on various number of symmetric ciphertext inputs from 1 to 300 at the **CSP**. HE.Enc took 16 milliseconds to execute, while the results for HHE.Decomp were similar to those from 2GML.Eval. For a single input, HHE.Eval took 38 milliseconds to execute and 11.6 seconds for 300 inputs.

Phase	User	Server	Total
2GML.Setup	243 ms	–	243 ms
2GML.Upload	607 ms	–	607 ms
2GML.Eval	–	3597.7 s	3597.7 s
2GML.Classify	900 ms	–	900 ms

Table 21 – Total Computation Cost – 2GML for 300 data inputs

Finally, in both 2GML.Classify and 3GML.Classify phases, we focused primarily on measuring the cost of HHE.Dec for a range of homomorphic ciphertext inputs from 1 to 300. For a single input, HHE.Dec ran in 3 milliseconds, and for 300 inputs, it ran in 900 milliseconds (Table 20). Table 21 and Table 22 provide the computational analysis of 2GML and 3GML protocols respectively for 300 inputs.

Phase	Analyst	User	Server	Total
3GML.Setup	243 ms	–	–	243 ms
3GML.Upload	–	607 ms	–	607 ms
3GML.Eval	16 ms	–	3607.21 s	3607.23 s
3GML.Classify	900 ms	–	–	900 ms

Table 22 – Total Computation Cost–3GML for 300 data inputs

11.4.4 Comparison with plain BFV

To provide concrete evidence of the efficiency of our proposed construction, we implemented a plain BFV scheme with a similar architecture to 3GML and compared the results. More precisely, we measured the performance of a plain BFV scheme, where a user continuously encrypts data input homomorphically before outsourcing them to the **CSP**. The same encryption parameters were used for all implementations. For these experiments, we only focused on comparing the total computational and communication costs of running the 3GML.Upload phase of our protocol, with the cost of continuously using HE encryption in the plain BFV. We varied the number of data inputs from 1 to 300 (each data input is an integer vector of length 4).

For a single data input, 3GML.Upload took 9 milliseconds to execute, while the plain BFV

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Figure 23 – Computation Costs

Figure 24 – Communication Costs

scheme took 7 milliseconds to perform a single HE encryption. It is worth noting that the plain BFV scheme is marginally faster for a single data value. However, this is due to the fact that `3GML.Upload` involves two operations (a symmetric encryption operation and an HE encryption operation), while the plain BFV scheme involves just one HE encryption operation. However, when the number of data values was increased to 300, `3GML.Upload` ran in 0.608 seconds, while the plain BFV scheme ran in 2.2 seconds. Figure 23 provides an overview of the computational comparison results obtained from this phase of our experiments. It is worth pointing out the fact that, in most cases, uploading just one single input is unrealistic since most PPML services will require a plethora of data to properly evaluate a problem. Subsequently, we compared the communication expenses by measuring the total size of transferable ciphertext data in bytes from a user u_i to **CSP**. Overall, `3GML.Upload` sent approximately 1.8 MB of ciphertext data for both a single input and 300 inputs. This is primarily because the size of a symmetric ciphertext is almost negligible as compared to that of a homomorphic ciphertext. The plain BFV, on the other hand, sent approximately 1.82 MB of ciphertext data for a single data input and 547.8 MB for 300 data inputs. Figure 24 provides an overview of the comparison of the communication costs for 1 to 300 different inputs. From these results, it is evident that `GuardML` reduces the communication and computational burden of u_i and transfers them to **CSP**.

11.5 Open Source Framework Implementation

An open-source software framework was developed¹² to support the distributed testing environment required by the HARPOCRATES sleep demonstrator partners to conduct a diverse array

¹²The source code is available from the HARPOCRATES GitHub repository https://github.com/harpocrates-project/distributed_hhe_ppml

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of experiments on HHE and privacy-preserving ML. Various programmable software components within the framework implement the functionalities of the parties involved in the GuardML privacy-preserving inference protocol. These components can be instantiated as separate processes (hosted on different machines) communicating over the network. To minimise data transmission and computation overhead [135], the framework's components interwork and expose relevant functionalities via an internal *gRPC* interface, with exchanged data serialised as *Protocol Buffers* [136]. At the same time, the framework was conceptualised to be coupled with external software systems seamlessly. The ongoing development activities aim to integrate some of the framework's software components with the HARPOCRATES demonstrators through widely adopted interfaces, such as *JSON over HTTP/REST* [135].

The framework was engineered for high adaptability, enabling existing and future HHE schemes and PPML settings developed as part of GuardML to be easily incorporated and utilised with minimal or no modifications. This design aspect is crucial to support open science and allow other researchers to use, possibly extend, and experiment with HHE schemes and privacy-preserving inference protocols in real-world settings. The current framework implementation provides a distributed version of the 3GML, built on the code developed for the performance evaluation described in subsection 11.4. It includes three component types representing the parties involved in the 3GML settings: *Users*, *Analysts*, and *Cloud Service Providers (CSP)*. These components comprise two modules, each implemented as a C++ class, to separate the cryptographic operations from those required for inter-component communication via *gRPC*.

In *gRPC*, a client application can directly call a method on a server application on a different machine, as if it were a local object, to create distributed applications and services. This concept is based on defining a *service* and specifying the methods that can be called remotely with their parameters and return types. On the server side, the server implements this interface and runs a *gRPC* server to handle client calls. On the client side, the client has a stub that provides the same methods as the server. Our open-source framework relies on this model to implement the 3GML steps of Figure 20 in a distributed fashion. For example, Listing 1 reports the RPC service that a CSP exposes to allow both the User and the Analyst components to perform the *3GML.Upload* phase of the protocol shown in the figure.

Listing 1 – The *gRPC* service provided by the CSP

```
1  service CSPService {
2      rpc addPublicKeys (PublicKeySetMsg) returns (Empty) { }
3      rpc addMLModel (MLModelMsg) returns (Empty) { }
4      rpc addEncryptedKeys (EncSymmetricKeysMsg) returns (Empty) { }
5      rpc addEncryptedData (EncSymmetricDataMsg) returns (Empty) { }
6  }
```

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Specifically, the Analyst can remotely invoke the `addPublicKeys` and `addMLModel` methods to upload the public keys and the encrypted model to the CSP. Similarly, Users can invoke the `addEncryptedKeys` and `addEncryptedData` methods to send their encrypted symmetric key and data for model evaluation to the CSP.

By default, gRPC uses Protocol Buffers—a technology that perfectly fits our requirements of minimal data size and communication overhead during remote method invocations [137]. Protocol buffer data is structured as *messages*, where each message is a small logical record of information containing a series of name-value pairs called *fields*. The gRPC service example in Listing 1 is based on method parameters and return types specified as protocol buffer messages. For instance, the `addPublicKeys` method on line 2 accepts a `PublicKeySetMsg` parameter, whose definition is shown in Listing 2 on line 8.

Listing 2 – The messages exchanged when invoking the CSPService methods

```
1  message Empty { }
2
3  message PublicKeyMsg {
4      bytes data = 1;
5      int32 length = 2;
6  }
7
8  message PublicKeySetMsg {
9      PublicKeyMsg pk = 1;
10     PublicKeyMsg rk = 2;
11     PublicKeyMsg gk = 3;
12 }
```

The listing shows that a protocol buffer message can be based on a nested structure where its fields are, in turn, defined as messages. Such recursive organisation is highlighted by the fields `pk`, `rk` and `gk` of `PublicKeySetMsg` being of the type `PublicKeyMsg`, whose definition consists of an array of bytes and 32-bit integer (reported in Listing 2 on line 3). Like the other methods of the `CSPService` definition, `addPublicKeys` does not return any values to the caller; hence, an `Empty` message type was defined and used as the return value. Similar service and protocol buffers were devised for the Analyst to allow the CSP to send the outcome of an encrypted model evaluation. Whilst the complete *proto* file containing those service and protocol buffer definitions is not reported here, it can be found in the online project repository.

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12 Conclusion

Throughout this deliverable, we covered how modern cryptographic techniques, like HE and FE, can add an important layer of security and privacy for users and enable them to analyze their data without directly sharing it with untrusted parties. Accordingly, we presented three FE constructions, namely Need for Speed, SPADE and FFS. We first proposed and implemented an efficient and lightweight FE scheme using ECC primitives. Our construction is capable of running on resource-constrained devices without causing excessive energy consumption or computational overhead. Additionally, we provided SPADE, an FE construction based on ElGamal, which allows analysis of the occurrence of specific values in an encrypted vector without revealing the entire vector. Finally, we provided an FE scheme agnostic framework FFP, which yields a function-private FE scheme, based on any message-private one and proved its security and robustness. We extended our work by analysing how HE and HHE can be used as an alternative to FE to allow for use cases that are too complex to be implemented on current hardware with FE. We analysed the security, efficiency and constructions of various HHE schemes and provided a realistic HHE solution, GuardML, that carefully considers the vagaries of PPML. The designed approaches are able to carefully balance ML functionality and privacy so as to allow the use of PPML techniques in a wide range of areas. By using HHE, we managed to overcome the main difficulties of PPML application in real-life scenarios, where the majority of data is collected and processed by constrained devices.

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